

HEALTH AND WELLBEING - THE RESPONSIBILITY OF
ALL? AN INVESTIGATION INTO PERCEIVED LEVELS OF
PREPAREDNESS IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION GRADUATES

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FEBRUARY 2024

THESIS SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT OF THE
REQUIREMENTS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF
SCOTLAND FOR THE AWARD OF MASTER OF
PHILOSOPHY.

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Word Count: 43970

6th February 2024.

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Acknowledgements

'Thank goodness for the good souls, if it wasn't for the good souls life would not matter' (Starsailor).

This project would not have been possible without a tremendous amount of support from the 'good souls' who are part of the many 'teams' that have been part of this journey.

My dissertation team: Rowena, Donald, Stephen and Lisa - I could not have navigated this journey without your expertise, enthusiasm, patience and understanding. Thank for all that you have done.

My viva team: especially my examiners Dr Andrew Killen, Dr Nollaig McEvilly and Dr Victoria Randall - I appreciate your time and your support.

The dream team: Jennifer, Louise and Yvonne – You have helped me in unmeasurable ways to persevere and to get to heart of what matters, our students, I am filled with gratitude for your support and friendship.

Team PE: the participants and Steven – without whom this research study would not have been possible. The willingness of the participants to give up their time to contribute to the study and their genuine interest in participating in the research to strengthen our programme was unbelievable and I shall be forever grateful to you. Steven, a tremendous colleague and friend who was always first to say, 'what can I do to help', thank you and good luck with your own thesis!

Team Awesome: my school of education colleagues – your support, encouragement and positivity have been a constant source of solace, laughter and inspiration throughout my journey. Special mention to the wonderful human beings that are Louise Scott-McKie and Abi Ledwith for all that you have done and will continue to do.

Team PhD: well technically the PhD Group – thank you for listening, considering, challenging and inspiring. Special mention to Michelle, Hayley and Khadija for the coffees and chats in the corridor that helped to provide me with the confirmation that I am not alone in this journey.

Team McCulloch: my extended family and my friends - thank you for always being there for me to commiserate and distract when necessary! And yes, mum, I promise I am done being a student now!

The other half of team McSpoon: Stuart - my husband, my partner in crime, my rock - thanks for putting up with me throughout it all.

Team Killie! - there have been many ups and downs being a supporter of Kilmarnock FC for over 30 years but the one thing it has taught me that if I can survive being a Killie fan I can survive anything ... even this PHD!

Abstract

Curriculum for Excellence (CfE) has resulted in health and wellbeing (HWB) becoming the responsibility of all teachers (Scottish Government, n.d) and has increased responsibility for physical education (PE) teachers (Gray and Mitchell, 2015). The initial teacher education (ITE) of PE teachers must ensure that they are able to meet the challenges associated with changing societal trends and government priorities (AIESEP, 2014). This study examined how PE graduates from an ITE programme in Scotland view their levels of preparedness for meeting their responsibility for HWB. It investigated factors that impact perceived preparedness of probationary teachers and early-phase practitioners through qualitative methods (focus groups and interviews). These were analysed using the inductive method of Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA), which allows the researcher to focus on the interpretation of meanings (Smith et al., 2009).

This thesis extends the work of Menter et al. (2010) by establishing that the stages which a beginning professional travels through during their career development may be more complex than originally set out in the literature. Building on the work of Gray and Mitchell (2015), the study has shown that participants see PE and HWB as being closely linked, and this has increased and changed the responsibilities as physical educators. The study also demonstrates that teachers' understanding of HWB and its implications for their practice can mould their perception of their preparedness. This study indicates that the understanding of the HWB policy is varied, and its implementation is inconsistent for participants, giving further substance to the idea that how policy is enacted in practice is rarely uncomplicated (Thorburn and Gray, 2009). Building on the work of Mayer (2016), this project shows that knowledge of context is significant and that a range of 'unknowns' has an influence on perceived preparedness. It provides the basis for an understanding of the experiences of participants within a context and suggests that the respondents in this study felt prepared for some but not all aspects of their responsibility for HWB, and that these feelings were influenced by factors such as experience and context.

List of Acronyms

CfE - Curriculum for Excellence

GIRFEC - Getting it Right for Every Child

GTCS - General Teaching Council for Scotland

HWB - Health and Wellbeing

IPA - Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis

ITE - Initial Teacher Education

NQT - Newly Qualified Teacher

PE - Physical Education

PETE - Physical Education Teacher Education

PGDE - Professional Graduate Diploma in Education

PIS - Participant Information Sheet

PST - Pre-service teacher

TEI - Teacher Education Institutes

TP21 - A Teaching Profession for the 21st Century

SHANARRI - Indicators of HWB: Safe, Healthy, Active, Nurtured, Achieving, Respected, Responsible and Included

UNESCO - United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

WHO - World Health Organisation

Research Outputs

Barnd, S. and Wotherspoon, E. (2019) Preservice teacher's perceptions of personal physical education experiences: pre-service teachers' beliefs and dispositions'. Paper presented at: AIESEP International Conference, Garden City, United States, 19/07/19 - 22/07/19.

McCulloch, E. (2018) 'It's just what we do!': physical educators views on preparedness to deliver health and wellbeing. Paper presented at: AIESEP International Conference, Edinburgh, United Kingdom, 25/07/18 - 28/07/18.

McCulloch, E. (2018) Topography of teachers: what kinds of teachers are we graduating from initial teacher education? Paper presented at: European Conference on Educational Research, Bolzano, Italy, 4/09/18 - 7/09/18.

McCulloch, E. (2017) Ready to teach or just ready to move on? an investigation into levels of preparedness in physical education graduates. Paper presented at: European Conference on Education Research, Copenhagen, Denmark, 21/08/17 - 22/08/17.

Barnd, S., and McCulloch, E. (2017) 'Star jumps and sandshoes': the lasting impact of personal physical education experiences on preservice teachers. Paper presented at: Scottish Educational Research Association Annual Conference, Ayr, United Kingdom, 22/11/17 - 24/11/17.

McCulloch, E. (2017) Where the 'real' learning happens: the role of the placement in preparing physical education graduates. Paper presented at: Scottish Educational Research Association Annual Conference. Ayr, United Kingdom, 22/11/17 - 24/11/17.

McCulloch, E. (2016) Ready? Set? Teach? an investigation into physical education teachers' perceived preparedness. Paper presented at: SERA 41st Annual Conference, 2016, Dundee, United Kingdom, 23/11/16 - 25/11/16.

McCulloch, E. (2016), Teacher preparedness in health and wellbeing. Paper presented at European Conference on Education Research - Emerging Researchers' Conference, Dublin, Ireland, 22/08/16 - 23/08/16.

McCulloch, E. (2015) Health and wellbeing - responsibility for all: Are all ready for the responsibility? Paper presented at: AIESEP International Conference, Madrid, Spain, 8/07/15 - 11/07/15.

Context and significance of the study

The implementation of CfE in 2010 led to significant reform of the Scottish school curriculum and all teachers became responsible for incorporating three cross-cutting themes – Literacy, Numeracy and HWB – into their daily practice (Smith, 2018). This thesis explores the perceived preparedness of Professional Graduate Diploma in Education (PGDE) PE graduates to meet the responsibilities associated with promoting, developing, and teaching HWB as part of the secondary school curriculum. This chapter outlines the historical context in which the CfE reforms sit and situates the study within the prevailing educational policy landscape. It details the personal and professional relevance of the study for the researcher and PE practice. The chapter concludes with the aims, objectives, and research questions for the study.

Historical context

Education is a devolved power and in Scotland is a function of the Scottish government with the duty to provide school education falling on the country's 32 local authorities (Smith, 2018). Despite influences from other UK education systems (and vice versa) 'the breadth of [The Scottish] curriculum, a separate legislative framework, no formal prescribed national curriculum and one national examining body' demonstrate the uniqueness of Scottish education (Humes and Bryce, 2008, p.99). However, there are significant parallels between the new curriculum for Wales and that of CfE, both of which were instigated a result of a review by Graham Donaldson. By contrast, the curriculum within Northern Ireland has remained similar to that of England, using similar language in the design of the curriculum and offering the same qualifications system of GCSEs and A-levels with only a few minor differences (Department of Education, 2013.).

Education is central to the construction of 'Scottish-ness' (Humes and Bryce, 2008, p.971) with pride in the system seemingly well placed, with inspectors reporting an atmosphere that promotes learning and with 'school ethos' and the 'commitment and teamwork' of the staff being seen as key strengths within the education system (Gatherer, 2008, p.894). Alongside this, performance in national and international assessments (PISA) continues to be

considered good (Bryce and Humes, 2018). However, there are challenges with primary to secondary transitions, as well as how the system gauges the overall success of CfE (Smith, 2018) with tensions between educationalists and politicians seen as being of great concern (Gillies, 2013). Educational issues and legislation have become a hallmark of the Holyrood parliament (Packard, 2008) and there continues to be a significant 'political edge', particularly because policies pertaining to education are set by politicians but are enacted by schools and teachers (Gillies, 2018, p.86).

Contemporary Scottish education is rooted in earlier reforms, and this is mirrored within the context of PE (Thorburn and Gray, 2009). More than 95% of pupils are educated in the country's 359 state-funded comprehensive schools, and the remainder educated in the 37 independent schools (Smith, 2018). CfE has an overarching aim 'to ensure that all children and young people in Scotland develop the attributes, knowledge and skills they will need to flourish in life, learning and work' (Scottish Government, 2009, n.p) so that they become successful learners, confident individuals, responsible citizens, and effective contributors (Scottish Executive, 2006). CfE reforms introduced National Qualifications with the aim to provide additional flexibility, a wider range of academic and vocational subjects, and a variety of ways to cater for additional support needs (Bryce and Humes, 2018). Furthermore, these reforms brought the curriculum in line with other educational policies designed to instil equality of consideration, which takes account of pupils' needs, views and interests and provides education provision accordingly (Bryce and Humes, 2018). Whilst both the secondary and primary sectors face challenges from this curriculum reform, it is seen as a positive shift for pupils and has been viewed as 'the most significant curricular change in Scotland for a generation' (McAra et al., 2013, p.223).

National debate on education priorities arose from The Standards in Schools Etc. Act (2000) (Gillies, 2018) and a review of teachers' pay and conditions was commissioned (Humes, 2009) which set out a commitment to continuous professional development for all teachers (Scottish Executive, 2001). This review also made significant recommendations for ITE, including a two-stage review and an induction scheme that provided support to newly qualified teachers during their first year of teaching (Menter et al., 2010). This also stimulated a review of the General Teaching Council for Scotland's (GTCS) professional standards and

procedures covering ITE, induction and beyond (Kennedy, 2008). Views regarding the effect of these changes on the landscape of secondary schools are varied but, often, they are negative, due to teachers' perception of an excessive workload associated with the myriad of changes (Bryce and Humes, 2018). Collectively, these developments cohere around a conception of teaching as a learning profession and of schools as learning organisations that have a commitment to self-evaluation and continuous improvement (HMIE, 2006). It is also widely acknowledged that all these initiatives are intended to improve the educational effectiveness of schools and arguably depend on the quality of the nation's teachers (Kirk, 2000). As education continues to evolve, so must the institutions and programmes entrusted with preparing teachers to work within this system.

Professional context

In Scotland, entry into the teaching profession is exclusively via university-based graduate degree programmes either a four-year undergraduate programme with a teaching qualification or a one-year PGDE programme following the successful completion of an undergraduate degree (Scottish Government, 2019).

Participants in this study were PE students on a PGDE Secondary Education programme which also has students from five other secondary subject areas in its cohort. Entry requirements are stipulated by the GTCS (detailed in next chapter) and the number of students who can be accepted for any given subject is set by the Scottish Government. ITE programmes for PE attract more qualified applications than can be offered places (Kirk et al., 2018) and as a result the PGDE had a highly selective entry during the research study. The 36-week PGDE is split evenly between university and school-based learning and has three modules: Subject Studies, School Experience and School and Professional Studies. During the first of these modules, students studied in their PE subject group and the twice weekly sessions focussed on curriculum, pedagogy, assessment, and content knowledge in PE, it also considered how PE can contribute to HWB and vice versa. The module was taught by two PE lecturers (one of whom is the researcher) and complemented by external partners in a small

number of sessions. The module was assessed via the submission of a practitioner enquiry assignment assessed by one of the PE lecturers.

In School Experience, participants explored more general aspects of curriculum, pedagogy, and assessment alongside their peers from all secondary subjects in classes of 30-120. The module prepared students for undertaking their placements and developed professional qualities and capabilities in a range of areas such as HWB and the methods and underlying theories for effective teaching of this curricular priority. A range of education lecturers (between 10 and 12) and external partners contributed to the twice-weekly teaching in this module. This included the researcher, who led sessions on positive behavioural management, HWB, higher-order thinking and questioning. Other colleagues also contributed to areas related to HWB. The two PE lecturers were responsible for the three university assessments of the PE students on placement.

The School and Professional Studies module involved studying alongside peers from both the PGDE Secondary and PGDE Primary programmes in mixed groups, with the number of people ranging from 6-120. The module focused on students developing a thorough understanding of the Scottish education system and supported students in developing professional qualities and capabilities for their probationary year, with a particular emphasis on a critical understanding of socially just, inclusive education. With reference to HWB, this module included consideration of elements such as the GIRFEC policy. The module included a wide range of university staff teaching across the weekly sessions, with support from school-based colleagues in some instances. The researcher participated in two sessions as part of this module, both of which were related to reflective practice and interdisciplinary learning. The module was assessed via assignment investigating the complex issues studied in the module with papers randomly assigned to markers, including the researcher.

The combination of these modules was planned to support achievement in the key areas of the Standard for Provisional Registration (SPR) (GTCS, 2012), which underpinned the overall aims of the PGDE programme. Though these standards have now been updated, being replaced in 2021, all participants in the study worked towards the 2012 version of the SPR. Alongside this, the programme aims included a focus on lifelong learning, autonomous

practice, and team-working. This overview presents a context where students engaged with a range of colleagues and peers across the three modules to develop their practice and work towards achieving the SPR during their PGDE. A fuller overview of the programme content can be seen in Appendix 17.

Professional Significance

The quality of teaching and learning is of key importance in determining the performance of pupils in schools (European Commission, 2012). Alongside this, HWB is now the responsibility of all teachers (Scottish Government, n.d) and is seen as a way of challenging health inequalities (Chief Medical Officer, 2011) which has resulted in increased responsibility for PE teachers (Gray and Mitchell, 2015). As a result, PE needs to undertake a profound transformation (Fletcher and Casey, 2014) and ITE programmes must meet the challenges associated with changing societal trends and government priorities (AIESEP, 2014).

Health is a 'state of complete physical, mental and social wellbeing and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity' (World Health Organisation, 1948, p.2). For some, 'wellbeing' is an 'ill-defined' term (Spratt, 2017, p.35) that has a malleable definition linked to different agendas (Weare, 2010; Ereaut and Whiting, 2008). For Scotland, the HWB curriculum focuses on:

- Holistic health and wellbeing (mental, emotional, social, and physical)
- Six organisers, including PE, physical activity, and sport
- Eight principles included in the SHANARRI wheel that indicate health and wellbeing within pupils

(Scottish Government, n.d)

It is important to consider whether the next generation of teachers are prepared to deliver 'Learning through health and wellbeing that promotes confidence, independent thinking and positive attitudes and dispositions' (Scottish Executive, 2006, n.p). As such this study will investigate PGDE PE students' understanding of HWB and their perceived preparedness to

meet the responsibilities associated with promoting, developing, and teaching HWB in secondary education.

Preparedness in teachers is understood to be the ability to demonstrate competence in the practical setting, as well as the possession of curricular knowledge and teaching skills (Noelle-Parks and Wager, 2015). Within Scotland, preparedness in graduates is measured by achieving the SPR and demonstrating the expected features of these in three key areas:

- Values and personal commitment
- Knowledge and understanding
- Skills and abilities

(GTCS, 2012).

Preparedness is emphasised as one of the key constructs of an effective teacher, leading to confidence or 'teacher efficacy' in terms of their ability to promote pupils' learning (Hoy, 2000). Preparedness and teacher efficacy are linked to experiences (Protheroe, 2008) with mastery experiences - experiences of an individual's performance of tasks related to the efficacy focus (Bandura, 1997) - being the most important factor for Pre-Service Teachers (PSTs) during ITE, and the induction year (Hoy, 2000). Given the importance placed on teacher efficacy and the links to preparedness, it is essential to examine the levels of preparedness in probationary and early-phase teachers. As such this study will investigate the participants' views of their experiences and any potential impact on feelings of preparedness to effectively meet their responsibility for HWB.

In the initial framing of the research study, the four categories of teacher, as presented by Menter et al. (2010), were used as lenses for examining students' perceptions.

Commissioned by the Donaldson Review, this report examined 21st-century teacher education internationally, with a focus on comparative studies between home countries and international teacher education. The report suggested that four influential paradigms of teacher professionalism exist within international literature: the effective teacher; the reflective teacher; the enquiring teacher; and the transformative teacher, with each

contributing to the contemporary context of the teaching profession (Menter et al., 2010, pp.21-25).

Personal Significance

This study has been shaped by my experiences in school and my interest in teacher education in general and, more specifically, developing PE teachers to be the best they can be. I was part of a PE department that interpreted, planned for, and delivered the curriculum following the introduction of CfE, and a motivation for the current study, in part, comes from a desire to consider whether ITE programmes have adapted to this change. I was also involved in supporting student and probationary teachers and became interested in ITE and the level of preparedness it provided. In some ways, this was influenced by personal experience as a graduate of a four-year Bachelor of Education programme, I supported students and probationary teachers who had come through the shorter PGDE programme. I often wondered if the length of the course had an impact on how prepared students were – at times, I was convinced this was the case.

This was expanded when I undertook my master's studies and researched levels of perceived preparedness in probationary teachers for my dissertation. At the time, my supervisor advised looking at all subject areas and across secondary/primary sectors; reflecting on the above, I wish I had focused on PE teachers, as this is where my passion lies. I wanted to research something that matters not only to me, but also to my work and the wider education field. Therefore, this experience solidified my interest in PE teachers and their levels of preparedness and in no small part underlies the motivation for the present study. Whilst listening to Diane Mayer speak in 2014, I began to wonder what factors might influence feelings of perceived preparedness. Mayer suggested that ITE only had a small influence on preparedness in Australian PE graduates, which piqued my interest in questioning whether the same was true for PE graduates in Scotland. This is particularly relevant to my current role where I oversee the ITE of PE student teachers on a PGDE Secondary programme.

These personal and professional motivations, along with the current Scottish Education context, led to the major concept, and indeed question, of the research being formed – what feelings of perceived preparedness do PE graduates have and what factors influence those feelings of preparedness?

Research Questions

The research questions for this study are:

- How do practitioners view their levels of preparedness to meet their responsibility for Health and Wellbeing as:
 - o a probationary teacher and;
 - o an early-phase practitioner?
- What are the reported factors that contribute to perceived levels of preparedness within physical education graduates of ITE?

Literature Review

Introduction

This literature review outlines the global focus on health and defines both PE and HWB within the current context, illustrating the value of PE and critiquing the position of PE as a contemporary solution to health promotion. Consideration will be given to the impact of global health trends on ITE as well as examining what is meant by the term preparation. The chapter will illuminate the importance of ITE in laying the foundations for the quality of teachers and in shaping the future of Scotland's education system, and, more importantly, the success of the country's pupils.

Health and Wellbeing

The Ottawa Charter introduced health promotion as the 'process of enabling people to increase control over and to improve their health', showing health as a positive entity and health promotion as being the responsibility of more than just the health sector – something that 'goes beyond healthy lifestyles to wellbeing' (WHO, 1986, p.1). This indicates that others, including teachers, have a responsibility for the promotion of health, and this means that schools face a substantial challenge when it comes to enacting the vision of HWB throughout the curriculum (Porciani, 2013) as HWB is a vast curricular area and it can be problematic (Spratt, 2017). The WHO (1948) definition of health - a state of complete physical, mental and social wellbeing and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity - is widely cited though sometimes criticised for its idealistic definition of 'complete' health (Blair et al., 2003; Antonovsky, 1996). It is appealing for its positive vision of a health that is more than just physical and it contains different aspects of wellbeing which are key components of health (Quennerstedt et al., 2010; Brolin et al., 2018). Wellbeing is offered as the ultimate goal of human life (Aristotle cited in Irwin, 1975) and this is a 'dynamic process of living (being) well in the social world' (Austin, 2016, p.125). In a critique of the WHO definition, calls have been made for an updated definition that takes into consideration this dynamism, viewing health as the ability to adapt and to self-manage (Huber et al., 2011). HWB has a malleable definition linked to different agendas (Weare, 2010; Ereaut and Whiting, 2008) and

is often an umbrella term associated with many other factions of education, such as resilience and citizenship (Spratt, 2014). However, 'if health is a state of wellbeing, it is unclear why the preferred policy term is 'health and wellbeing' as this would appear to be the use of two synonymous terms' (Spratt, 2014, p.26). Highlighting a lack of clarity around this 'ill-defined term', despite the terms being closely related and often measured by 'indicators' (Spratt, 2017, p.35).

Wellbeing is the central political challenge of our time which is linked to quality of life and can be viewed in both subjective and objective terms (Children's Society, n.d.). What constitutes wellbeing and how to 'achieve' wellbeing is a focus for many stakeholders who outline priority areas as a way of defining and proving the 'indicators' of HWB such as

- o Have the conditions to learn and develop
- o Have enough of what matters
- o Have positive relationships with family and friends
- o Have opportunities to take part in positive activities to thrive
- o Have a safe and suitable home environment and local area
- o Have a positive view of themselves and an identity that is respected

(Children's Society, n.d, n.p).

These are proposed conditions that can foster wellbeing in children and share some similarities with indicators associated with HWB in Scotland such as being safe, being supported to achieve, and being respected (Scottish Government, n.d).

Health and Wellbeing in the Scottish Curriculum

HWB as a curricular area has attracted some criticism due the unease at the merging of so many important constructs (Ecclestone and Hayes, 2009) but the term is perceived as useful, inclusive and supportive of actions and policies (Spratt, 2014). In line with the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC), the 'Getting it Right for Every Child' (GIRFEC) policy identifies the right of all children to have access to appropriate health services and to have their physical, social, educational, emotional, spiritual and psychological development

promoted (Scottish Government, 2012), with holistic learning considered to be the key to bringing all of these elements together (Jess et al., 2016). Some areas of HWB are the responsibility of 'all staff in early years centres, schools and their community partners across Scotland' (Education Scotland, 2013, n.p) who have a responsibility to promote and develop HWB as it is 'fundamental to effective learning and a skill for life' (Scottish Government, 2017, p.32). A particular focus is on the development of the whole child and ensuring that children are happy, safe and respected encapsulated in eight indicators in the wellbeing wheel (Appendix 1) (Scottish Government, n.d). Though this may have taken on aspirational slogan status as they are commonly seen in schools, but the meaning associated with the indicators is not always clear despite guidance being produced (e.g. experience and outcomes) to support the implementation in school (Priestley and Humes, 2010).

This guidance defines some terms (e.g. mental health and resilience) but the definition of HWB is not explored in depth; instead, it focusses on the practicalities of delivering HWB in school through things like the benchmarks with teachers being afforded significant autonomy to tailor the curriculum to the needs of their pupils. However, whether teachers consider themselves to have this autonomy is yet unknown. It is also worth emphasising that, although the benchmarks are listed as a set of statements, they are to be holistically assessed and cannot be 'ticked off' as having been achieved (Education Scotland, 2017) placing emphasis on the holistic vision of HWB. Interestingly, the HWB benchmarks were not published at the same time as the literacy and numeracy benchmarks. One might wonder if this is an indication of relative importance or simply that the difficulty in defining HWB led to a delay. In either scenario, given the potential autonomy afforded to teachers, it is worthwhile considering whether graduates perceive themselves as being prepared to meet their responsibility for HWB.

HWB is identified as the responsibility of all; this is considered by some to be novel (Spratt, 2014) and curricular shifts like this (seen across the world in response to global interest in health) are not only directed at individuals but also show the capacity of young people to shape society and are seen as the key to a nations success (Quennerstedt et al., 2010). Similarities are seen in other countries, such as Australia, where there is a significant focus on health and, more specifically, on health literacy. The term health literacy shares similarities

with HWB, as health literacy is linked to both salutogenesis and a strengths-based approach, and health is viewed as an asset/resource to be used for the benefit of individuals and communities. From this perspective, health is not considered to be something you either have or do not have; rather, it is about the different degrees of health that are created and sustained (Quennerstedt, 2008). This type of health is something that schools should deliver and something that pupils should adhere to and, as responsible citizens, embrace (Leahy et al., 2015).

Despite the right to appropriate support young people can be impacted by negative experiences in childhood and this is a barrier to learning (especially in disadvantaged youth) as well as a barrier to HWB (Scottish Government, 2018). This is a vicious cycle: wellbeing is considered to be a barrier to pupils' capacity for learning and a diminished capacity to learn is a barrier to wellbeing; while strong HWB can lead to academic flourishing emphasising the interconnected nature of wellbeing and learning (WWCW, 2018). Barriers to HWB are often related to health inequalities which are avoidable as they are often rooted in political or social factors (e.g. income, power, wealth) many of which are beyond an individual's control (NHS Health Scotland, 2015). One of the most significant barriers to HWB is poverty and deprivation, which is linked to poor eating and other factors such as a lack of access to appropriate resources and parental support, which can limit a young person's development in HWB and put young people's health at risk (Scottish Government, 2018). Cutbacks (e.g. to resources or funding) have an impact on HWB and are particularly seen as a barrier when considering mental health (which is a barrier itself) (NHS Health Scotland, 2017). This coupled with obstacles such as teacher workload, confidence and wellbeing jeopardise education's ability to promote HWB (OECD, 2018). It can be argued that, in suggesting an aspirational, holistic view of HWB within its policy framework the Scottish government is attempting to overcome some of these barriers.

CfE is considered ambitious for placing HWB at the forefront, bringing together PSE, HE and PE and for focusing on learning 'in' and 'thru' HWB (Spratt, 2014). Implying that it is more than just teaching 'concrete' subjects, it is also influenced by aspects of teaching and learning (e.g. class management or behaviour strategies). CfE has placed HWB at the forefront of education, and physical activity, PE and sport featuring in the pages of the popular press and

on current events television programmes. However, this was not always the case: for decades PE teachers were equated to sports coaches and portrayed as ineffective teachers, as drill sergeants or bullies who take pleasure in belittling pupils (Tinning, 2009). It would seem that the introduction of CfE, alongside the associated policy shift which brought a renewed focus onto PE and its ability to improve health, indicates that the perspective is changing and thus it is necessary to consider how PE and teachers of the subject have evolved in line with education reform.

Physical Education

For some there is 'no doubt' that PE can make a valuable contribution to wider educational aims, but it is almost impossible to prove that it does (Whitehead, 2021a, p.29). As other subjects also contribute to wider educational aims this could devalue PE as a subject and lead to it not being seen as an essential, unique area of the curriculum (Whitehead, 2021a; Crum, 1993). There are many ongoing debates about the fundamental aim of PE as well as curriculum design and development within the subject (Whitehead, 2021b). Nurturing talent, promoting health and fitness, personal and social development or physical literacy are all considered to be part of the aims of PE (Kinchin et al., 2001). Despite differences most views of PE see it as the planned introduction to 'movement culture', developing the ability for lifelong participation in that culture via education in and thru the physical, though this has also contributed to different interpretations of what this means (Crum, 2013). These ideas originally shared by Crum in 1993 continue to be seen in contemporary views, where PE involves becoming more physically competent (learning to move) and learning through movement, as well as a range of skills and understandings beyond physical activity such as cooperating with others (moving to learn) (Capel et al., 2020). PE is viewed as planned, progressive learning delivered to all pupils during school curriculum timetabled time (Capel et al., 2020) via a broad range of activities including sport and dance (Harris, 2020, p.4).

Quality is often a feature of defining the experiences within PE and commonly includes a focus on inclusion and the development of physical, social and emotions skills (Scottish Executive, 2004). Quality PE in Scotland should be enjoyable, diverse, progressive, focussed on learning as well as planned and delivered by qualified teachers (Education Scotland, n.d),

which is vital to retaining the professional status of PE (Quennerstedt, 2019). Teachers are tasked with taking in to account the curricular design principles (Education Scotland, n.d) to provide suitable learning experiences that set the foundation for a lifelong engagement in physical activity and sport (AfPE, 2015). It is here we start to see connections between quality PE and HWB as 'crucially, pupils are now expected to develop in ways that go beyond simply acquiring physical skills, as notions of 'mental, emotional, social and physical wellbeing' are now considered inextricably linked to students' PE learning experiences' (Thorburn et al., 2011, p.387). Other curricular principles, like challenge and application, are linked to quality PE experiences as they provide opportunities for pupils develop qualities such as creativity and adaptation. Developing these in different contexts through progressive learning that provides learners with greater autonomy and responsibility is essential to quality PE (Education Scotland, n.d.). Indeed, some suggest that application is what makes learning valuable in PE and this is now expected within contemporary Scottish curricular PE to help achieve the aims of CfE e.g. HWB (Thorburn et al., 2011; Quennerstedt, 2019).

There has been an ongoing dialogue about a linear versus a non-linear curriculum in PE (Correia et al., 2019) which has led to calls for a more holistic approach to PE as crucially it is more than simply developing physical skills (Atencio et al., 2014). To do this we must move beyond the traditional and use approaches that place the learner at the heart of it all (Kirk, 2013). This is in line with CfE and highlights that there is the possibility that PE can contribute to a range of education outcomes (Bailey et al., 2009). PE teachers are expected to contribute to extrinsic aims of education (including HWB in Scotland) (Whitehead, 2021a) alongside the intrinsic aims of PE - building physical competences, improving fitness and developing personal / interpersonal skills and attributes (Scottish Government, n.d). These intrinsic aims can be realised through engaging pupils in movement across a wide range of physical activities (Whitehead, 2021a). However, simply engaging pupils in PE does not guarantee that they will make progress in achieving any of the extrinsic aims; it principally depends on how one teaches, not what one teaches (Whitehead, 2021a, p.27). It is therefore important to consider whether PE teachers are prepared to teach in a way that supports the achievement of extrinsic aims such as HWB.

PE in the Context of HWB

The Lisbon agenda highlights that investing in people is key to overcoming social problems and promoting the economy (European Council, 2000). HWB and education's contribution to this have been a noticeable focus worldwide (Ball, Dworkin and Vryondies, 2010) especially with ranking tables being so prevalent and this has placed new demands on the teaching profession (European Commission, 2007). The UK finds itself in the bottom third of these ranking tables, but they are only one indicator of HWB - a multi-dimensional approach is needed given that poverty affects numerous aspects of child wellbeing in many well-documented ways (UNICEF, 2007).

Scotland is healthier now than in the 1970s though the pace of improvement remains slow and the conditions necessary for HWB to flourish are the focus of many policies / strategies (Porciani, 2013). In some ways this portrays a positive outlook despite some highlighting that a lack of activity is literally killing us which has led to wider calls for a physically active life to benefit both quality and length of life (Ratey, 2008). Obesity and inactivity are prevalent in Scotland and costs the economy significant amounts of money (Scottish Parliament, 2015). This may go some way to explaining why health has been the focus of many policy reforms across the developed world and in Scotland, where 'continuing to invest in health has been one of the few areas in political and public life that continues to bring different groups together in a shared goal' (Porciani, 2013, p.471). This increased focus on Scottish young people's HWB, both in the context of curricular learning and more generally in society, has prompted greater interest in the role that teachers have in influencing HWB. This is primarily down to teachers and the quality of teaching being viewed as vital to developing the wellbeing and personal growth of young people as well as to increasing economic growth (European Commission, 2007). However, it is argued that this should not be the primary purpose of education and that education should be a goal in and of itself (Priestley and Humes, 2010). Despite this we can see, at least from the political standpoint, why teachers and their role in developing the young people of today are of particular interest in the contemporary world.

PE has coexisted alongside a wide range of policy goals some of which have had a significant impact on the PE curriculum (Thorburn and Gray, 2009; UNESCO, 2013). Some attribute this to PE being seen as the ideal learning environment for lifelong physical activity (Gray et al., 2015). However, within CfE, the notion of physical wellbeing is just one part of the HWB curriculum, and caution is urged, as the current HWB discourse present in Scottish schools is open to interpretation and negotiation in varied ways in PE, and this has implications for physical educators' practice (McEvilly et al., 2014). This current policy position has led to it being necessary to outline the contribution of PE more explicitly than earlier versions of the curriculum might have required as it is an area of the curriculum which needs to be given greater priority to support HWB (Thorburn and Gray, 2009). This has increased responsibility for PE teachers even though they cannot always articulate how to achieve the aims (Thorburn and Gray, 2009; Gray and Mitchell, 2015) and consideration must be given to whether graduates of ITE consider themselves prepared for this.

School PE and health have often been linked with healthism being produced (Kirk and Colquhoun, 1989). Healthism represents a view that it is in and through the physical that health can be achieved, and this is directed mainly at the maintenance of body shape and size through self-control and focusses on individual responsibility (Alfrey et al., 2017). This culture has been justified by many in terms of offsetting the impact of a sedentary lifestyle (Kirk and Colquhoun, 1989). However, the assumption that individuals are solely responsible for health that is portrayed within healthism is inconsistent with the responsibility of all holistic view that is presented in CfE. Healthism is still a contemporary PE issue with concerns raised that many teachers view as their role as the promotion of fitness and physical wellbeing which produces a narrow form of PE (often equated to 'managed recreation') that neglects the other areas of HWB and might actually not promote health (Gray et al., 2012; Horrell et al., 2012). Comprehensive, holistic models of health promotion can enhance the status and centrality of PE and PE (Lawson, 2018) and physical educators have a responsibility to see and understand their complicity in producing healthism (Tinning, 1985). Therefore, exploring teachers' perspectives and challenging teacher philosophies will be vital, particularly in ITE, to the adoption of curricular or policy initiatives associated with health (Alfray, et al., 2017).

PE and health can coexist and learning in PE can be based in a broad and varied range of experiences in an environment that also promotes health (Gray et al., 2015). The subject of PE even when associated with 'health' has much more to offer than simply educating individuals how to be healthy and physical activity for the sake of physical health (Gray et al., 2015) and this conflation of PE and physical activity is viewed as a core problem (Lawson, 2018). A broader, more varied form of PE could place the learner and their needs at the heart of teaching and learning to enhance social, emotional and mental wellbeing as well as physical wellbeing (Gray et al., 2015). Indeed, providing students with these experiences may be even more important than simply increasing physical activity levels to improve health (Gard, 2011). In this way PE and HWB can coexist in a complementary way, and some recognise that the redesign of PE is already underway, albeit slowly, and school PE teachers have a pivotal role to play in this (Lawson, 2018).

Improvements in mental health have been positively linked to PE with some research indicating a significant reduction in mental health problems because of intervention by PE specialists (Ahn and Fedewa, 2011). This is seen in Scotland where PE can contribute to the development of mental wellbeing in adolescents particularly those living in deprivation (Kirk et al., 2018). This sits alongside a view that PE could not be 'left to chance' (Scottish Executive, 2004) and there being a need for quality PE to focus on the promotion of mental wellbeing (Scottish Government, 2017). This focus on quality PE, alongside the increased teacher workforce for PE, was a clear indication that 'policies were expected to be followed through and that its place in the health and wellbeing narrative ... was both desirable and achievable' (Brewer, 2008, p.54). However, how policy is implemented in practice is rarely uncomplicated (Thorburn and Gray, 2009) particularly when considering quality PE as a solution to a problem and as a proactive step towards improving the health of the next generation. Within this context, there is an underlying assumption that pupils want to take part in, and enjoy taking part in, PE and that pupils will expend enough energy in a PE class to see the outlined health benefits. This trio of assumptions can be suppressed by well-prepared PE teachers with an expert ability to develop not only the skills but also the knowledge through varied experiences to support pupils in engaging in lifelong physical activity (Hill and Peters, 1998). Alongside this, young people's investment in their looks and health is linked to a rise in eating disorders (Tinning, 2009) which indicates the severity of the problem and a possible need for

quality PE that educates pupils on this. Some view that PE teachers are not equipped to do this and that we already 'do' health (Green, 2000) but we must challenge teachers to keep up to date with contemporary practice (Gard and Wright, 2001). Though there are varied views and perhaps some uncertainty as to what PE will look like in the future, it has been noted that 'how the professional needs and requirements of teachers will be met are important considerations for review if PE is to be successful in capitalising on many of the policy opportunities which currently exist' (Thorburn and Gray, 2009, p.1). PE has the potential to make valuable contributions to pupils' health and the ITE of graduates who will deliver PE must come under scrutiny if we are to ensure that these valuable contributions are achieved.

PE and health have overlapping outcomes and PE can contribute to health goals in addition to its own goals (Gray et al., 2015) and as such PE teachers have a responsibility for developing mental, emotional and social wellbeing (Scottish Government, 2009). However, this does not always necessarily lead to change in what is being taught in PE (Green and Lamb, 2000) there is insufficient information on how PE teachers can create learning environments that can support this development in line with curriculum aims (Gray et al., 2015). There appear to be continuing issues between school PE policies and the practical implementation of these policies (UNESCO, 2013) despite schools and teachers being seen as critical to implementing health strategies (Della Torre et al., 2010). Arguably then, PE can make contributions to HWB, but this should be done in meaningful ways that maintain the quality of PE as a subject itself and we must examine the conditions necessary to support ITE graduates of PE in becoming prepared to undertake to contribute to this. Particularly, as there has been 'broad-spread disquiet' about the ability of ITE programmes to provide appropriately qualified PE teachers (UNESCO, 2013, p.11)

Initial Teacher Education

ITE in Scotland is based in eight universities, and the distinctive nature of provision remains a source of pride within Scotland (MacDonald and Rae, 2018) despite fears that teacher educators would lose their professional orientation due to pressure to conduct research in university (Kirk, 2000). This had the potential to impact the ability of teacher educators to effectively prepare teachers (Kirk, 2000) but others, including the government, saw it as ITE

becoming increasingly professionalised (Menter et al., 2010). The commitment to the importance of professionalism is impressive; having the profession be, exclusively, staffed by graduates and having a professional standards framework that drives teacher professionalism are two initiatives which have 'placed Scotland in a strong position to be compared with other countries internationally' (Donaldson, 2011, p.1). Scotland focusses on teacher education rather than teacher 'training' despite some instances where the Scottish government uses the term 'training' (MacDonald and Rae, 2018). The focus on teacher education is due to the complex, unique and uncertain education environment (Schön, 1983) where 'training' might be considered insufficient to prepare prospective teachers for entry into a profession where it is impossible to predict the 'unanticipated twists and turns that take place in a system that assumes that teaching and learning are controllable and predictable' (Brookfield, 2006, p.11). In contrast with counterparts elsewhere in the UK, Scotland's ITE provision can be seen as having a stronger academic base, being more fully professionalised (Menter et al., 2010) and retaining a balance between integration of theory and practice providing a strong foundation for career-long professional learning (Smith, 2013). Credit for this is given to Teacher Education Institutes (TEIs) and the significant role they have played in the development of ITE within Scotland, not least the major input they have had on the suite of professional standards (Christie, 2008). There are still abundant concerns over 'depth of understanding of both what they are teaching and how to employ teaching approaches which meet the needs of their pupils and of the particular subject matter' (Donaldson, 2011, p.8), thus highlighting the need to investigate the ITE experiences of recently-qualified teachers (RQTs).

ITE has been subject to much reform over the last 20 years in Scotland (e.g. Sutherland and Donaldson reports) (Christie, 2008) and is considered to have strengths and distinctive features like the induction scheme which is considered world class by OECD (Menter et al., 2010). This probationary period is viewed as an extension of ITE though TEIs have no statutory involvement, so it is not clear how that is the case (Menter, 2008). Consideration of this concern is outside the scope of this study, but considering the preparedness of early-phase PE practitioners for HWB may shed some insight. Especially as students and RQTs report that ITE does not fully prepare them for the wider responsibilities (e.g. HWB) with many teachers barely surviving the day-to-day demands of teaching (Deloitte and Touche,

2001). Despite this ITE provision in Scotland is viewed as strong though research in this area is described as relatively 'small scale and piecemeal' (Menter et al., 2010, p.3), it has been subject to review via TP21 and a baseline study on Literacy, Numeracy and HWB (Humes, 2013). The baseline study, while it did not take account of the holistic approach adopted by TEIs nor placement (the focus was on number of hours), did highlight that HWB has more prominence in ITE (Scottish Government, 2017).

There has been large interest worldwide in sufficiently qualified teachers (OECD, 2005) which has led to policy reform on entry standards and preparation (Ingersoll, 2007). Advocates of stronger teacher education insist prospective teachers need to know how children learn (Darling-Hammond et al., 2005) and others argue that strong subject knowledge or general academic ability may influence effectiveness as much as teacher education (Podgursky, and Ballou, 2000). Teacher qualification is not necessarily an indication of teacher effectiveness, but ITE can make a remarkable difference in teacher quality (Slater et al., 2012). This is due to the foundations of professionalism being established during this period, which are then built on in the future (Menter et al., 2010). The rhetoric of recent reform has indicated that teacher education does matter and, in particular, the content of ITE matters very much to the preparation of teachers (Moon et al., 2003).

A positive relationship between teacher education and pupils' achievement has been highlighted (European Commission, 2007) with preparedness for teaching key to determining a teacher's ability to support pupil achievement (Darling-Hammond et al., 2005). Teacher education is seen as of great significance to producing effective teachers (Green, 2010) and it also might be a more cost-effective method than smaller class sizes in raising attainment (European Commission, 2007). However, it is critical that it takes account of new demands and national guidelines (Kirk, 2000, p.17). Some have challenged the links as being weak (Podgursky and Ballou, 2000) but this has been countered by reiterating the depth of analysis and labelling the empirical challenges as being political and ideological (Darling-Hammond et al., 2005). Others have highlighted that teacher effectiveness is improved through preparation (Ingersoll, 2007, p.1) though this literature considers the issue in North America, where someone can become a teacher with minimal teacher education, and whilst this is certainly not the case in Scotland, teacher education is of great value to the quality of

teaching in the classrooms of any country. As such high standards of professional competence and commitment are needed leading to calls for better teacher education and recruitment to lay the foundations of a high-quality teaching profession (Donaldson, 2011).

There are very few who would endorse a view that ensuring the highest standards of ITE guarantees quality teachers; no matter how thorough or comprehensive ITE might be, it cannot provide all the skills and understandings that teachers will require throughout their careers (Kirk, 2000, p.51). It is not the aim of this research project to show that ITE is the only teacher education necessary for teachers; the present study fully acknowledges that teachers will be lifelong learners who must adapt to evolving times. ITE is of great importance to the quality of the teaching profession, since it is where the foundations are laid, and a weak programme at that stage 'will have consequences that will be extremely difficult to fix later on' (Moon et al., 2003, p.89). The question of whether ITE in Scotland is perceived as being sufficient to prepare PE graduates to undertake their responsibility for HWB is one to be investigated further through this research project.

Quality in the Delivery of ITE

Ongoing government study has resulted in increased interest in the quality of different ITE routes (MacDonald and Rae, 2018). This is mirrored across Europe where there has been an effort to design ITE programmes that produce a quality teaching profession with extensive subject knowledge, knowledge of pedagogy as well as the skills and competence to be a teacher (European Commission, 2007). It is important to note that it is emphasised that teachers should be lifelong learners, as ITE cannot, and should not, try to provide teachers with the knowledge and skills necessary for their entire career (MacDonald and Rae, 2018). This raises the question of how much is 'enough' and what should ITE do to support preparedness in graduates?

A partnership-based approach is employed within Scottish ITE to support quality, but partnership is problematic and is highlighted consistently as an area of concern in ITE (Christie, 2008). Some view the difficulties as being a result of struggling to find placements or not having effective relationships with schools (Menter, 2008) where others highlight that

schools need to be 'convinced of their value in initial teacher education' (Kirk, 2000, p.45), and there is a popular discourse that ITE content is not relevant and does not effectively prepare student teachers for the practice of teaching (MacDonald and Rae, 2018). Additional concerns over integrating theory into practice were attributed to the lack of recent classroom experience of teacher educators (Tryggvason, 2009) despite evidence of frequent use of 'teaching fellows' a practice that was commended for providing recent classroom experience in ITE (Christie, 2008, p.832). It is unlikely that this concern can be dismissed by one example of good practice but with ITE trying to deliver a programme that will 'produce a research informed, intellectually curious, adaptive profession prepared to adopt a critical enquiring approach' (MacDonald and Rae, 2018, p.845), it is possible that a struggle to achieve balance in the content of ITE programmes still exists.

Across the world there are generally two main types of teacher education - concurrent and consecutive (Eurydice, 2000). The landscape of Scottish ITE is now more flexible because of the Donaldson report but unlike counterparts across the UK has resisted school-based routes with continued calls that standards of ITE should not be compromised and that universities are crucial to this (MacDonald and Rae, 2018). The more recent trend has been towards consecutive degrees with the introduction of the Professional Graduate Diploma in Education (PGDE) and some attribute this to the PGDE receiving little criticism in the Donaldson report (MacDonald and Rae, 2018). Both routes are supposed to achieve the same challenging outcomes of knowledge and skills (Christie, 2008) but have been challenged on their ability to prepare teachers due to their short nature (Deloitte and Touche, 2001) and the Donaldson review highlighted some concerns over preparation (Scottish Government, 2011). There are common features seen across ITE irrespective of the route (e.g. assessment, pedagogy) and investigation into preparation of graduates might shed some light on the reason for these concerns. Although investigating this across all ITE providers is outside the scope of the present study, it can consider the effectiveness of the PGDE route and there is an opportunity for this research to lay the groundwork for future studies in this area across all ITE providers.

Feedback from teachers indicates that ITE and school are disconnected (Livingston, 2008) this is despite refinement of ITE, student teachers being viewed as well prepared and much

evidence of good experiences (Deloitte and Touche, 2001). Some indicated that ITE had not taken advantage of the opportunities presented by CfE to design innovative programmes although ITE provision is viewed as being a 'securely established successful part of the Scottish education system' (Smith, 2013, p.915). Quality in ITE is influenced by admissions procedure and GTCS accreditation (Scottish Government, 2011) as well as internal quality assurance procedures (such as the NIF) with a focus on teacher professionalism (Scottish Government, 2017). By some measures, ITE in Scotland is generally considered to be of a high standard; in the recent Complete University Guide (2018), Scottish universities filled five of the top eight places (n=77) for education across the whole of the UK. Yet, one prevailing view is that ITE does not contain enough focus on the key areas of priority, such as literacy, numeracy and HWB (Donaldson, 2011, p.11). The focus of ITE for much of the 21st century has been responding to the controlled numbers stipulated by the government and attempting to secure placements for the number of student teachers on the programme, whilst stakeholders have been urged to consider how ITE undertakes the preparation of prospective teachers (Smith, 2013). ITE is being encouraged to employ new and innovative ways to support 'student teachers to develop the capacity to become transformative teachers who make a positive impact on the outcomes for learners and have the capacity to become future leaders of the profession' (Scottish Government, 2017, p.10). It is hoped that this research into the current practice within ITE can shed light on other innovative approaches which could be employed across ITE programmes to support the delivery of HWB.

ITE of PE Teachers

Alongside this shifting educational landscape in Scotland, the need for change within PE is highlighted frequently in contemporary literature (Jess and Collins, 2003). However, inadequate attention has been paid to the question of what constitutes quality in PE and PETE programmes which must be able to meet the challenges associated with changing societal trends and government priorities (AIESEP, 2014). Internationally, ITE for PE teachers takes several forms and has evolved alongside growing international interest in physical activity, PE and sport. A bachelor's degree, diploma or equivalent is a prerequisite for teaching PE at primary and secondary schools (UNESCO, 2013). The teacher education of

physical educators was, initially, hosted in dedicated PE colleges, which then evolved into university departments; Bedford College of PE is one such example, becoming, first, De Montfort University and, now, Bedfordshire University. Similarly, in Scotland, the development of the four-year Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.) degree in the 1960s replaced the three-year diploma as the main qualification for teaching PE. The new course drew heavily on exercise physiology, biomechanics and motor learning for its educational content (Kirk, 2002) and continued into the new millennium, where it evolved into an MA degree and was joined by PGDE courses. Those remain today as two of the main qualification routes for prospective teachers of PE. Much of the evolution came into being as a response to changing government priorities but it cannot be assumed that current teacher knowledge is sufficiently robust in adjusting to societal trends (Brewer, 2013). As such, PE teacher educators are challenged to ensure that they are open to revising their programmes so that graduates from those programmes hold skills that are relevant to contemporary society and develop sufficient resilience to be change agents in their future professional practice (AIESEP, 2014).

Having existed since 2004, the PGDE route is relatively new compared to other forms of ITE, which have existed in various forms for over 50 years. The entry requirements for both routes have similarities e.g. each route requires appropriate English and Mathematics qualifications, candidates must demonstrate practical competence as well as the skills, attributes and dispositions that are desirable in a teacher as part of the interview process (GTCS, 2019). These are summarised as being committed, reflective and innovative; being self-directed and resilient with high levels of self-efficacy; and having an awareness of the role of a teacher as well as an understanding of educational provision across Scotland (GTCS, 2019). Where the routes differ in their entry requirements are with the academic qualifications required for entry. The undergraduate route has a requirement of four or five higher grade qualifications depending on the grades achieved, with no stipulation of subjects studied other than Higher English while entry requirements for the PGDE route stipulate that candidates must have an undergraduate degree related to the subject they wish to teach (GTCS, 2019). The PGDE also has subject-specific entry requirements which outline that the degree must contain subjects related to, or involving analysis of, the aspects of PE, and should include a great deal of practical performance (GTCS, 2019). The final similarity is that

due to the competitive nature of both programmes, the minimum entry requirements are not necessarily sufficient to guarantee that a candidate will be selected for interview.

Given the nature of the present study, the focus of this section of the literature review will be on the PGDE route into PE teaching. Due to the subject-specific entry requirements outlined above, the introduction of the PGDE route has resulted in an increased range of sports degrees that claim to serve as a relevant qualification for entry into ITE at the postgraduate level. In the Memorandum on Entry Requirements (GTCS, 2019) there is an attempt to identify relevant subjects that could be studied as part of an undergraduate degree, such as sport, dance or outdoor pursuits, and module topics such as movement analysis, sports coaching or exercise physiology. Whilst these may give indications of suitable degrees, the GTCS stops short of identifying degree routes that are suitable for entry to the PGDE with the responsibility for ensuring the acceptability of qualifications lying with universities (GTCS, 2019). However, relatively little is known about the content of these degree programmes and less is done in conjunction with TEIs to ensure that these do indeed meet the minimum entry requirements for the course, let alone whether the programmes serve as a good basis of knowledge and skills for a prospective PE teacher. This has led to calls for teacher educators to work more closely with colleagues responsible for the delivery of sports-related undergraduate degree courses to support the development of subject knowledge for those who wish to continue to the graduate route (Gower and Capel, 2004).

Within the PGDE course in this study, as is common in similar routes, student teachers spend 50% of the course on placement. Thus, the success of the programme and that of the graduates from it are highly reliant on partnerships with schools, though this is also true of any ITE programme, irrespective of length. Thorburn and Gray (2009, p.52) argued that the four-year undergraduate route offers 'the best opportunity' for teacher educators to develop new physical educators who have a broad view of PE that is in line with the aspirations of the curriculum. Concerns have been expressed about levels of practical activities within the 36 weeks of study, and reviews of the types of opportunities and experiences which might be considered useful in ITE are pertinent to explore given the new centrality of PE and the associated policy expectations (Thorburn and Gray, 2009). This, combined with the relative

lack of understanding of content at the undergraduate degree level, further highlights the need to investigate the preparation of student teachers engaged in the PGDE.

Socialisation of PE Teachers

In any arena socialisation is the process through which individuals learn the norms, cultures and ideologies deemed important in a particular social setting by interacting with one another and social institutions. Socialisation of teachers can be linked back to workplace socialisation which focusses on the ways in which individuals become effective members of a particular profession (Bauer and Erdogan, 2011) and has sought to understand the motives for entering teaching, the impact of ITE and the challenges of navigating the social politics of school settings (Richards and Gaudreault, 2016). ITE is one of the three stages of socialisation that teachers go through - acculturation (before teacher education), professional socialisation (teacher education) and organisational socialisation (career long in school) (Lawson, 1986; Templin et al., 2017).

Organisational socialisation which is a process of constant forming and reforming of views based on interactions with students, colleagues, context, policy (Lawson, 1986) is more impactful than professional socialisation. It may be that any impact from professional socialisation is reduced or even eradicated by organisational socialisation, this is particularly possible if perspectives on the purpose of PE are left unchanged by teacher education (Templin et al., 2017). Thus, the socialisation of teachers can be linked to the success of schools and the pupils within them (Templin et al., 2017; Lawson, 2018). Schools operate in an ever-evolving environment where the social, economic and political environment has changed significantly, subsequently so have the conditions in which teachers operate - today's reality is full of education reform and increased teacher accountability (Templin et al., 2017). It is noted that most teachers are not prepared for this reality during teacher education (Templin et al., 2017). It is therefore important to consider the impact of teacher education on preparedness for delivering a recent education reform - Health and Wellbeing.

The socialisation of PE teachers has a significant impact on teaching and learning practices (O'Leary, 2019) and Templin and Schempp's (1989) seminal work highlights the impact of

teacher socialisation on teachers' beliefs, pedagogical practices, and career trajectories. Socialisation also influences role identities, value commitments, professional practices and work behaviours of teachers (Lawson, 2018). Of particular importance to ITE and student teachers is the understanding of themselves / others in relation to health and physical activity that they bring to ITE (Wrench, 2017). This is primarily influenced by experiences in school-based PE, sport and other movement cultures and these understandings have been developed through an 'apprenticeship of observation' (Lortie, 1975). This provides an important base for understanding why some student teachers teach in accordance with the practice experienced in childhood as opposed to that which they were exposed to in ITE and why some favour teaching through more innovative pedagogies over the traditionalism present in schools (Richards and Gaudreault, 2016). Given this and the direct impact on children experiences and outcomes (Lawson, 2018) it is important to consider how teacher education contributes to this area.

There has been a range of policies which have influenced the shape of school PE, with ITE provision worldwide having been impacted in a similar way with both governmental and non-governmental indicators or guidelines that dictate or suggest the components of a quality programme (UNESCO, 2013). In Scotland, these are a combination of the SPR, the memorandum on entry requirements and validation; all of which are the responsibility of the GTCS. Alongside this governmental push to ensure the quality of programmes, teacher educators have been researching, reforming and developing teacher education for PE for over 50 years (Collier, 2006). This is a result of cultural influences on the nature and scope of school-based PE and, it could be argued, responses to continual criticism of the quality of such programmes, which is equated to inadequacies in the teacher education of PE graduates (O'Sullivan 2014). When looking at what quality might be within ITE, graduates are expected to be lifelong learners who have a deep knowledge of the subject area alongside a set of skills and professional dispositions to be a reflective practitioner (AIESEP, 2014). Perhaps where we might see a difference in these expectations for PE graduates, is that they are, not only, expected to advocate for pupils, but to advocate for quality PE throughout the teaching profession and education system (AIESEP, 2014). Students enter ITE with views about what teachers, specifically PE teachers do as well as what PE is (Capel and Blair, 2007) and different students will make sense of their ITE experiences in different ways (Tinning,

2002). This is particularly important with continuous changes and the evolving nature and scope of PE, it has been observed that teachers are reluctant to give up control of the learning process as they believe it is what they know (Casey and MacPhail, 2018). Being a PE teacher is complex and requires time spent during ITE thinking about PE and what it means to shape teaching philosophy and consequently practice (Capel et al., 2020). Thus, any programme must consider how their students make sense of their experiences and what impact their professional socialisation has on their preparedness to teach.

Preparation: what do teachers need to know and be able to do?

Government guidelines state that the overall aims for ITE are to 'prepare student teachers to become competent, thoughtful, reflective and innovative professionals who are committed to providing high-quality teaching and learning for pupils' (Scottish Government, 2017, p.10). However, exactly what teachers know and need to be able to do has been subject to much debate (Mayer, 2014). In the past, would-be teachers attempted to become an authority in their chosen subject area, now most teachers aim to be 'facilitators of learning' (Cotton, 1995, p.59). The knowledge or professional knowing of teachers is complex and contested (Shulman and Shulman, 2009) and the content of teacher education reflects that (Boyd, 2014). It is therefore important to look at what the literature tells us about preparedness in teachers and other terms that could have been the focus of this study.

Preparedness is one of several words that are often associated with consideration of teaching; readiness, confidence and competence being a few other frequently used (sometimes interchangeably) terms when considering teacher effectiveness. Studies that consider readiness often look at characteristics and readiness-for-the-job - 'readiness is typically a list of skills and dispositions across development dimensions that are seen to be important for school success' (Graue, 2006, p.44). Others link readiness to competence frameworks and identified teacher educators as having a central role in shaping the professional competence of student teachers (Mohamed et al., 2017). This idea of readiness was more aligned to the idea of teacher training as opposed to teacher education which advocates being prepared to be a teacher requires more than just a list of skills and dispositions. Focusing on teachers' perceptions of their own levels of preparedness is

significant as it provides a unique insight into the views of the students themselves which is a valuable lens through which to view practice (Brookfield, 1995). Looking at perceptions of preparedness through a student teacher's eyes has been linked to teacher efficacy and effective practice in the learning environment and is viewed as a powerful connection in the development of teachers (Darling-Hammond, Chung and Frelow, 2002). This is attributed to student teaching experiences and their impact on the sense of teaching efficacy and feelings of preparedness of PSTs (Brown et al., 2013). Perceptions of preparedness are related to increased efficacy and can predict desirable student and teacher outcomes and there is some evidence that student teaching may improve teachers' perceptions of instructional preparedness (Ronfeldt and Reininger, 2012). As a result, focusing on preparedness rather than readiness in this way was chosen for this study.

Other studies have looked at the perception of preparedness from ITE with a focus on things like perceived preparation for inclusion considering the views on both perceived preparedness and confidence as they moved into the early phase of their careers (Coates, 2012). Other studies have looked at perceived confidence in primary PE (Randall, 2020) though the focus on generalist primary teachers teaching PE here is a well-known area of research in confidence to teach Primary PE, it is not as well established in secondary education. Other studies focus broadly on perceived preparedness to teach PE (Langdon et al., 2014). A mixture of methods is used to investigate things such as perceived preparedness for utilising technology (Davis, 2017) and for differentiated instruction (Wan, 2017). Despite these examples research on teacher preparation is an emerging, complex, and multifaceted field, influenced by competing ideas about the purposes of research and the goals of education (Cochran-Smith et al., 2015). It is recommended that future research address questions that link teacher learning with student learning and teacher candidates' views (Cochran-Smith and Villegas, 2015). Whilst studies have considered the perceived preparedness of teachers to meet a myriad of agendas little is known about PE teachers' perceptions of their preparedness to meet their responsibility for HWB. This along with the examples of studies above led to the eventual selection of perceived preparedness within ITE as the focus for this study.

Earlier sections detailed the changes to ITE courses in Scotland; however, the core structure of the courses has remained 'remarkably constant' (Menter et al., 2010, p.10). This view is echoed by Christie (2008, p.826) who states:

though the detailed curriculum of initial teacher education courses in Scotland varies considerably, not least to reflect durations ranging from 36 weeks to 4 years, their overall structure basically comprises three common components.

These three components are curricular studies, professional studies and school experience (Menter et al., 2010) and these are seen in the ITE programme focussed on within this study. Donaldson (2011) confirms that the challenge for the architects of ITE programmes is to find a balance between developing core teaching abilities and consideration of wider professional responsibilities. Some university-based provision has been criticised for being highly theorised (Feiman-Nemser, 2001) and concern has been expressed over a lack of reflection on, or questioning of, the purpose or justification of the mandated curriculum in schools (Kelly, 2009). Alongside this, the change in curriculum in Scotland's schools has resulted in scrutiny of the content of the curriculum of ITE.

Teacher preparation is seen as one of the significant variables in the difference in the performance of new teachers and, in Scotland, there has been an expressed need to research and support improvement in teacher education (Scottish Government, 2017). There is considerable concern about the treatment of subject knowledge within ITE, with the need for all teachers to be confident in their subject knowledge deemed 'more important than ever' considering the new curriculum (Menter, 2008, p.824). Advocates for the place of educational theory and pedagogy claim that having a deep understanding of your subject area is not sufficient to be a teacher, you must also have in-depth knowledge of how to teach (MacLellan and Sodden, 2008; Kelly, 2009). To be considered prepared, teachers must gain knowledge (and strive to become experts) in both their subject and teaching as knowledge of how to teach is as important as knowledge of what to teach (Shulman and Shulman, 2009). Whether an effective balance has been struck that prepares PSTs for entry into the profession is a matter for investigation within this study.

Most ITE programmes indicate that teaching for social justice is an important aspect of their programme (Cochran-Smith, 2010). In considering what teachers must know and understand it is noted that this 'includes a requirement that PE teachers possess an informed understanding of social justice agendas, the nature of learning and the wider responsibilities of being a teacher in general' (Thorburn and Gray, 2009, p.49), these wider responsibilities would include responsibility for HWB. This focus on teaching for social justice started with the work of Freire (1970) and continued through other academics like Giroux (2003; 2012), who reiterated the plea of Freire for a socially just education system. This is seen in Scotland where recommendations call for teachers who are confident in their ability to address social disadvantage; work with young people with additional support needs; and teach literacy and numeracy (Donaldson, 2011). This imperative is seen clearly in the GTCS Standards (2012; 2021), where social justice is one of the central professional values. Social justice and health are often linked, as having good health supports individuals in accessing a range of human rights; if the citizens of a country do not have good health, it is very difficult to ensure a prosperous economy, political participation or collective security (WHO, 2010). This may suggest that ITE should, not only, educate on how to meet the responsibility for HWB, but also foster the HWB of the student teachers in their programme. There is value in investigating the development of the HWB of prospective teachers given that teachers will be role models for their pupils, although this is out of the scope of this study. This study focuses on the perceived preparedness of graduates to meet their responsibility for HWB, although it may shed light on any impact their own HWB has on their perceptions of preparedness.

An OECD (2005) survey, provocatively entitled 'Teachers Matter', highlights a potential lack of competence in teachers to deal with new developments in education. In the NFER education briefing (2019), which reported on PISA results, headteachers in England and Wales more often reported a problem with inadequate or poorly qualified teachers than in Scotland and Northern Ireland. More headteachers in Wales reported teachers not being well prepared for classes as a barrier to pupils learning than in England, Northern Ireland and Scotland. This highlights the need for sufficient education and scholarship for teachers to support effective preparation Dewey (1938). Whilst this study does not look at competence or confidence, the perceptions of preparedness of the participants may shed some light on the ability to deal

with one new development in Scotland: the introduction of HWB. Advocates of the importance of well-prepared teachers also show support for new teachers undertaking induction activities (OECD, 2005); here, Scotland has a well-established programme (European Commission, 2007). As a result, this study will also consider the feelings of preparedness following the period of induction.

Striking a balance can be considered challenging for those educators charged with preparing teachers but when considering many countries there is a remarkable similarity in what is expected for teachers to be considered prepared. These can be summarised as:

- Demonstrating competence in the practical setting
- Curricular Knowledge ‘the what’
- Teaching Skills ‘the how’

(Noell-Parks and Wagner, 2015).

Having some form of certification or licensure is a very common theme for professionals and teaching is no different. When the framework of standards was introduced, it was met with ‘stern criticism in both academic and professional circles’ (Christie, 2008, p.845). It is argued that the use of standards in this way is flawed, as it assumes that it is possible to come to a general agreement on the expectations of something as complex as teaching (Cochran-Smith, 2001). Others argue that it demeans and diminishes the status of the profession (Menter et al., 2010). There was also an apparent ‘inherent logical inconsistency here: how can it be ‘expected’ but only be ‘illustrative’ (Christie, 2008, p.848). The use of the term ‘expected’ implies that student teachers are aiming to demonstrate that they have met the standards. Whilst the term ‘illustrative’ implies that these are examples of things we might see student teachers do, it leaves room for the potential that some may do only some, or indeed none, of these things. Thus, the implication is that student teachers might demonstrate that they have met the standard in other ways. It could be that this is a consequence of the standards being for all student teachers, irrespective of level or subject they are studying to be qualified in, thus justifying the need for these to be sufficiently generic to be applied to different routes e.g. primary or secondary, PE or mathematics. While the framework for these standards is

significant for ITE in Scotland, it is not possible to interrogate the quality of the standards within the scope of this research project.

Within Scotland, preparedness in our graduates is measured by achieving the standards for provisional and full registration and they provide a framework around which ITE programmes can be developed (Christie, 2008). However, with the criticisms levelled at the standards, the question of whether the programmes shaped by this framework can prepare PSTs for entry into the profession must be considered. Through GTCS governance, ITE programmes must ensure that student teachers are supported to meet the standards (Scottish Government, 2017). This can be achieved through ITE programmes that are designed to support students to develop:

subject-specific knowledge and understanding, skills, abilities and dispositions but also to have a wider view of education that keeps the child at the centre and understands that ongoing professional learning is vital to enable teachers to support improvement and improve the life chances of all of our children and young people

(Scottish Government, 2017, p.10).

The standards are divided into three areas:

- values and personal commitment
- knowledge and understanding
- skills and abilities

(GTCS, 2012).

Within each of these, there are expected features that must be demonstrated to be deemed to have met the standards for entry to the profession. In outlining standards in this way, Cotton (1995, p.22) argues that we sometimes see 'a deliberate attempt to shape individuals into a model of behaviour'. Yet, the focus on the current standards is more than just 'a model of behaviour'; values and professional commitment are placed at the forefront. When comparing the standards set in Scotland to other countries, this is a novel and important

contribution to the view of what teachers need to be and do and have been called 'an inspiring set of professional standards' which are 'bold and supportive' (OECD, 2015).

Conclusion

This literature review has outlined the nature and scope of PE within the context of HWB. It has also detailed ITE within Scotland and the international context alongside the importance of well-prepared teachers to achieving reforms such as HWB associated with CfE. It considered perceived preparedness and what that looks like in graduating teachers linking this to the importance of ITE in laying the foundations for the quality of teachers.

Methodology & Methods

Introduction

This chapter will outline the methodology and consider positionality and its impact on the research. This chapter explains the appropriateness of the selected methods for answering the research questions of the study and will give an account of the design, data collection and analysis for each method. This chapter will explain the sequence of procedures used as well as pertinent ethical considerations linking these to the components of 'trustworthiness' which are important to qualitative studies such as this one (Duncan and Watson, 2010).

IPA as a Methodology

IPA was selected to support understanding, interpreting meanings, and participants experiences (Smith et al., 2009). While it was also a method of analysis as a qualitative methodology it has its routes in psychology. Within IPA, the researcher reflects on their preconceptions and tries to suspend them to focus on making sense of the research participants' meanings. It is a form of interpretivism which draws upon the fundamentals of phenomenology, hermeneutics and idiography. There is a considerable body of work using IPA to explore issues of personal experience of health and a growing number of studies looking at life transitions (Smith et al., 2009) which added to the consideration that IPA would be suitable for this research project given its focus on HWB and the transition of young educators from student teacher to probationary teacher to NQT. IPA draws on phenomenology as it focuses on exploring participants experiences in their 'own terms' (Smith et al., 2009, p.32). Phenomenology is a 'complex system of ideas associated with the works of Husserl, Heidegger, Sartre, Merleau-Ponty and Alfred Schutz' (Denzin and Lincoln, 1994, p.15) but is considered the study of the nature and meaning of experiences and is a form of interpretivism (Saldana, 2013). While it is not possible to outline all the ideas associated with these works, it is important to draw out the key links between these phenomenological works and IPA.

Husserl introduced a central focus on reflection, lived experience and the need to 'bracket' and these are significant to IPA (Smith et al., 2009, p.16). Husserl's work is quite abstract and focusses on the 'essence of experience' (Husserl, 1927, para 2) which led Heidegger to shift away from the abstract and focus on the importance of meaning and the 'practical activities and relationships' while also positing that knowledge outside of an interpretive stance is not possible (Smith et al., 2009, p.17). Where Husserl's work differs from that of IPA is that he 'was concerned to find the essence of experience' where IPA has a focus on trying to capture experiences for groups of people in a particular situation (Smith et al., 2009, p.16). Attributed to introducing two concepts 'worldliness' and 'Daesin', Heidegger (1962/1927) focused on what is possible and what is meaningful within a view of a person being in context and the intersubjective nature of our engagement in the world. This relatedness to the world is fundamental and underpins our ability to 'communicate with and make sense of each other' (Smith et al., 2009, p.17). These are key to IPA as it highlights that our 'being-in-the-world always in relation to something' and that interpretation of the meaning attached to those experiences is central to phenomenological inquiry (Smith et al., 2009, p.18).

Merleau-Ponty (1962) also viewed our knowledge of the world as both situated and interpretative (Smith et al., 2009) and this emphasises the embodied nature of the relationship which is critical for IPA as the practical activities and relationships are significant (Anderson, 2003). This was extended by Sartre (1956) by stressing that we are always becoming ourselves and that our experiences are interpreted in the presence or absence of relationships therefore very important to making meaning from lived experiences. This reiterates the worldliness of experience that Heidegger highlighted and was developed further to show that our experiences are contingent upon the presence or absence of our relationships with other people which is key to IPA and its focus on understanding live experience (Smith et al., 2009, p.20). These leading figures have contributed to some of the main developments in phenomenology and thus have relevance to IPA as a methodology, particularly the move towards a more interpretative stance and they help us to understand the complex nature of understanding and making meaning from lived experience (Smith et al., 2009). In line with phenomenology, IPA aims to understand meaning and explore experiences by providing participants opportunities to share their 'own frames of meaning' (Pintrich and Hoffer, 1997, p.94) - telling their own story in their own words to support the

creation of an interpretive account of what it means for the participants who had these experiences (Smith et al., 2009). Miranda and Freire (2012) advocate that more attention should be devoted to studies that draw on phenomenology where the investigation is focused on not only the beliefs and perspectives of the participants but also on their actions in the 'real' environment. Thereby, we can see that this study has in part a phenomenological focus due to its focus on participants' perceived preparedness during their experiences in ITE.

Many of the ideas in interpretivist approaches stem from the German intellectual tradition of hermeneutics and the *Verstehen* tradition in sociology and from critiques of positivism in the social sciences. IPA is an interpretive endeavour focused on understanding and thus is informed by hermeneutics, the theory of interpretation (Smith et al., 2009). This is seen in this study by interpreting the social interactions and the meaning attached to them by the participants (King and Horrocks, 2012) as well as an acknowledgement that different people construe the world in different ways (Mertens, 2005) and thus multiple knowledges can exist (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). This therefore imposes on researchers an interactive relationship with their research participants and a rejection of the ways of the natural scientist (Punch, 2009). Often associated with qualitative methods such as interviews, interaction of this kind is often criticised as being subjective and having significant room for bias to influence the research process (Cohen et al., 2009). Therefore, issues of power are important to recognise but interactive, cooperative, and participative relationships can be valuable as it can support the goal of gaining valid, in-depth, and participant-led data, which allows the researcher to gain an empathetic understanding of why participants act in the way that they do. This is particularly relevant in the case of education because, as while education contexts share similarities, they are complex and unique (Brookfield, 2006; Schön, 1987).

If then, the study is positioned within a context where knowledge or 'truth' is socially constructed, making sense of actions, behaviour or experiences may be more like 'interpreting a text in an unfamiliar language than finding its external laws of motion' (Green et al., 2006, p.15). This is closely linked to hermeneutics as it relies on interpretation through textual meaning and the individuality expressed by the speaker to understand experiences (Schleiermacher, 1998). This is important for IPA as it allows us to see how analysis might offer meaningful insights beyond individual participants (Smith et al., 2009). This could come

from visible meanings but also might be from hidden meanings and thus part of the interpretation is concerned with examining the thing itself as it emerges (Heidegger, 1962). Thus, it is important that researchers acknowledge the prior experiences, assumptions and preconceptions and priority should be given to the new view during interpretation rather 'fore-conception' (Heidegger, 1962) highlighting the importance of bracketing in IPA research.

Gadamer showed that interpretation is a dynamic, multifaceted process where the interpreted and the interpreter have a complex relationship (Smith et al., 2009). This relationship has been captured in the 'hermeneutic circle' - a cyclical idea that helps to think about 'method' in IPA research and the iterative process of moving back and forth between the data (parts and whole) and ways to think about the interpretations (Smith et al., 2009, p.28). IPA researchers are engaged in a 'double hermeneutic' as they are trying to make sense of the participant making sense of their experiences (Smith et al., 2009, p.3). The researcher facilitates the sharing of experiences and tries to make sense of them, thus the researcher will invariably influence the process (Heidegger, 1962). Interpretations are therefore reliant on the participant's ability to articulate their experiences, and the researcher's ability to analyse them (Smith et al., 2009). It must be acknowledged that IPA cannot fully access the complete world of the participant or their cognitive processes but through a careful and explicit interpretative methodology, insight into the meaning the participants attach to experiences can be gained (Smith et al., 2009). This is achieved through the two complementary commitments of IPA - 'giving voice' and 'making sense', researchers seek to reach an 'insider perspective' of individual lived experiences (Smith et al., 2009). Consequently, within the context of this study, this led to a belief that the participants of the study who had recently engaged with ITE were well placed to provide insight into perceived preparedness for HWB, using one of the four critically reflective lenses outlined by Brookfield (1995) - our students' eyes.

IPA is also considered idiographic as it focusses on individual experience and their meanings (Smith et al., 2009). Therefore, any claims made from a study that uses IPA are inherently linked to the individuals studied and are not normally generalisable, rather it is a different way of establishing those generalisations (Smith et al., 2009). This potentially limits the ability

to generalise from the research but as education policy and practice are constantly evolving and the contemporary context may not be applicable to future educators, some of the value of being able to generalise is diminished. Instead, the wish was to understand the fundamental meanings attached to this context. This is supported by delving deeper into the particular which can take us closer to the universal and cross case analysis can be used to focus on more general themes (Smith et al., 2009).

Positionality

Positionality focusses on the researcher, their position and world views in relation to the context of the study, the participants, the field, and its impacts every phase of the research (Coghlan and Brydon-Miller, 2014). This section will consider my positionality as an ITE tutor for PE, the programme leader for the PGDE (S) course, the researcher and how these 'positions' relate to one another, the research, and the research participants. It will also consider how my positionality impacts my worldview which arise from what Lin (2015) details as a practical interest in understanding how humans make meaning and centred around the interpretivist research paradigm and sociocultural understanding. In this study my professional identity was most pertinent to my positionality as this had the potential to affect things such as access to participants and how willing and to what depth the participants shared their experiences and views, and this could have an impact upon the data gathered in the study (Moser, 2008). It is therefore important to consider aspects of positionality that may have affected the way in which the research was undertaken, conducted, and engaged with.

Absolute neutrality used to be the goal in research (Moser, 2008) but because of work such as Rabinow (1977) there is growing recognition that there are nuanced potentially significant power dynamics at play in the process of research. Therefore, no research is completely unbiased or neutral (Haraway, 1988) and in this scenario knowledge is situated and findings influenced by the researcher (Moser, 2008). Many have argued that having personal connections to research has the potential to lead to more insightful analysis (Cloke et al., 2000) and many encourage researchers to investigate topics as an 'insider' due to the advantages it can provide (Tembo, 2003). The research process is underpinned by democratic principles, giving equal status to participants, and welcoming a diversity of perspectives. The

researcher has an impact on the research setting and is affected by an insider/outsider position. My personal interest in the topic being studied and an established relationship to the participants had the potential to influence the research and the next part of this section will consider the insider / outsider role within this study.

Insider / Outsider

Insider researchers have commonalities with participants which impacts notions of power and intentions and the closer the research is to the participants the more likely there are to be common expectations, intentions, and power equity the closer the researcher is to the participants (Coghlan and Brydon-Miller, 2014). Though it does not equate to 'sameness' (e.g., we are both PE graduates but from different routes) so while I can appreciate some experiences of the participants only in speaking to them can I even try to fully understand the meaning they attach to their experiences. Being an insider researcher enhances the depth and breadth of understanding of a population that may not be accessible otherwise, it also raises questions about objectivity, reflexivity, and authenticity of a research project because perhaps one knows too much or is too close to the project and may be too similar to those being studied (Kanuha, 2000, p.444). As such it is important to consider the costs and benefits of such a status within this research study.

An insider position is beneficial as it can provide easier access, acceptance and a common ground being established quicker leading to trust, openness, and increased willingness to share from participants (Dwyer and Buckle, 2009). All of this may lead to greater depth of data and a fuller picture being gathered (St Louis and Calabrese Barton, 2002) but it is not without its challenges. These include role confusion, assumed knowledge, difficulty separating own experiences from that of participants all of which could influence the study (Dwyer and Buckle, 2009). This is something I was particularly concerned with as my passion for and connection to the subject may prevent participants from considering certain aspects of their experience and this led to specific actions being taken during the study such as the use of an independent focus group facilitator.

Despite the challenges, an insider position does not have to be a negative influence on research as disciplined bracketing can reduce potential concerns (Dwyer and Buckle, 2009). Alongside this being open, authentic, honest, showing a keen interest in the participants experiences and being committed to accurately and adequately representing their experience can benefit the research (Dwyer and Buckle, 2009). Although my membership status in relation to the participants did not seem to affect the research negatively it was important to continually develop my awareness of my potential influence as 'there is no neutrality. There is only greater or less awareness of one's biases' (Rose, 1985, p.77). To assist with this, I employed various methods of 'self-supervision' throughout the research project: including prolonged engagement in reflection; member checking; a peer support network; a research journal; and an audit trail (Berger, 2015). After each interview I examined my reactions and reflected on whether there were questions that were consciously or subconsciously emphasised which helped me to become aware of potential influence on the research and reduce potential bias in future interviews (Berger, 2015).

My position had the potential to impact the data collection and analysis as I approached both of those tasks with some knowledge about the topic under investigation. The participants and I already had a shared experience and I had additional knowledge, such as module evaluations, which could influence aspects of the study. Therefore, assumed knowledge was a real possibility in this study and to offset this I adopted a non-patronising stance, maximised the opportunity for participants to impact the research and developed a continuous awareness of my position (through reflection and discussion) which have the potential to offset controlling influences (Berger, 2015). An insider position may result in participants voice not being fully heard (Cloeke et al., 2000) thus disassociating my own experiences alongside reflection was vital to help ensure that I had not overlooked any content. I also considered how I might have filtered the information through my own experience, trying to refrain from insinuation (Padgett, 2008). In doing so, the intention was to use my own experience to enhance the understating of the topic but not impose my own experience onto the research participants. As part of the analysis process, I often challenged myself by reflecting 'well you would think that' and asking, 'what would an outsider think'. This points to the importance of bracketing assumptions and reflection, a key part of IPA as a method of analysis (Smith et al., 2009).

I am an interpretivist, and this brings with it a set of beliefs and values that led to the selection of this topic, but also other decisions made within the research study e.g., it is people centred, involves integration in the research environment and explores meaning from the participants perspective. The evidence collected by interpretivists will often be qualitative in nature, offering a rich and deep description of the research environment as a unique context (Cohen et al., 2018). Within this world view reality is socially constructed and there are multiple realities. Reality is a construct; it is multi-dimensional, ever-changing, and dependent on different frames of reference. My ontological position is that there are multiple world views and that led to the choice of interviews and focus groups to support the goal of the research - understanding the experiences of those intimately involved in ITE. Consequently, the construction of knowledge is a democratic process, involving both researcher and research participants and is constructed from multiple perspectives. The element of subjectivity and bias is acknowledged and declared – the ‘belief’ system underpinning the viewpoint of the research. The goal of the research was not to try to predict but instead driven by an interest in understanding a particular phenomenon, a specific set of experiences within a particular context. Subsequently, the knowledge generated focused on meanings and is relative to this particular time and context – in this study that was the meaning that PE graduates attribute to their ITE experiences and their perceived preparedness for HWB.

Personal Reflections

Though professional identity was most pertinent to my positionality within this study aspects of personality are also important (Moser, 2008). Some of these are what Moser (2008) describes as quite impersonal others are more intertwined with my personal choices and interactions within the research process. I consider myself to be an advocate of women’s rights and the Black Lives Matter movement had a profound impact on me due to my experiences teaching in an African American high school in the early stages of my career. This was the most difficult and rewarding thing I have ever done in my career - starting a school with the lofty goal of improving the number of African Americans who went on to university. Wellbeing was never far from our mind, sometimes through the content of our lessons but more commonly due to losing members of our community to gun-violence and this was in

part reinforced by features of the school such as metal detectors, on-campus police officers and active shooter drills. This was the first time in my career where I remember wellbeing being a significant focus of what I did as an educator and on many occasions, it superseded our goals for PE. Even the department title, Physical Education and Wellness, gave a nod to the more holistic focus of the philosophy adopted within the school. It challenged me to think differently about how I taught PE, and I could see why it mattered so much to these pupils, in that context, but I wasn't sure if this was what I wanted my philosophy to be - indeed when I started teaching at the school it was not my philosophy. This was in part due to the different context compared to my upbringing in Scotland, where my schooling had focused on a version of PE that emphasised skill development and understanding factors that might support skill development. Since then, the move to PE being situated within HWB has potentially shifted the value and place of PE in the curriculum and as a teacher educator, I am challenged to think about how I model that and to give some consideration to whether HWB has given PE more value and whether our PE graduates perceive themselves to be prepared for that.

I consider that I must not only teach quality PE but must also advocate for the high-quality provision across the subject and for the position/value of the subject in the curriculum; a view that is often shared across the PE profession (Kirk, 2000). This was reaffirmed by my time in America where although sport had a very high-profile status, PE had a mixed/inconsistent status. The best example of this was student-athletes being exempt from PE; the belief being that they had received enough activity through their participation in their sports team. For me, this was heart-breaking as it reduced PE to a simple act of just being active. Even students that I coached and believed I had a strong relationship with were found to be lacking motivation for, or interest in PE as they already trained for volleyball daily, played games regularly and were happy to take the exemption. Though colleagues in the PEW department also valued the education and learning that PE could provide, the educational value of PE was not widely recognised in actions around the school environment e.g., we taught in an emptied-out classroom or outside for the first six months of the school year until we secured access to local leisure facilities. Twelve years after the school started, and 8 years after I left, the school building had a games hall and other facilities added - primarily down to support for the school basketball team but the PE department were lucky

to benefit from this during the school day. Overall, this showed a poor understanding of PE as a curricular subject and the links it makes to overall HWB, despite the efforts of the department. Ultimately this combined with the lack of advanced studies in PE led to a professional dissatisfaction with how PE was viewed and undertaken; it was one of the main reasons that led to me returning home to Scotland where I believed it to be different - that PE had a higher value and was viewed in a way that more aligned with my views of PE. Reflecting on this, it encouraged me to consider the need to consider this within ITE – are our graduates prepared to deliver their responsibility for HWB?

Research Design

Qualitative research can enable the researcher to get close to their participants and potentially gain a deeper understanding (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). The adoption of multiple methods offers advantages as it can 'increase the scope, depth and power of our research' (Punch, 2009, p.294) implying that using only one approach may not support a full investigation of the topic at hand. However, this can come at an expensive cost due to extensive data collection, time-intensive analysis and a greater skillset needed from the researcher (Creswell, 2009). Despite this, the potential of the different methods to complement each other and increase confidence in the results makes the costs more than worthwhile (Cohen et al., 2007). IPA is well suited to methods that allow participants to share detailed accounts of their experiences (Smith et al., 2009). Interviews are considered optimal for this though focus groups can also achieve this goal (Phillips, et al., 2016) and this led to the choice of focus groups and interviews as the methods for the main study.

Focus Groups

Focus groups, while an emerging method in IPA, are extensively used in other areas (e.g., market research) and have recently become more prevalent in education due to the strengths they offer (Litosseliti, 2003). These include a dynamic environment that can provide rich and profound insights (O'Toole and Beckett, 2010) though the contrived nature of a focus group is considered both a strength and weakness (Cohen et al., 2009). Focus groups are valuable for the exploration of themes and gaining a greater understanding of the

participants' views of the themes (Johnson and Christensen, 2008). Of particular interest within this research project was the ability of a focus group to gather data on 'attitudes, values, and opinions' (Cohen et al., 2009, p.376). Other strengths include the ability to gather in-depth information, to collect a large amount of data in a relatively short period (Mertens, 2005), and empowering participants to speak out in their own words (Silverman, 2013) so participants' rather than the researcher's agenda can predominate (Cohen et al., 2009).

Focus groups have been described as 'deceptively simple' (Wilkinson et al., 2011, p.168) but issues can arise when organising focus groups; namely accessing people and trying not to lead the discussion (Silverman, 2013). The size / number of focus groups are important to the richness of the data produced with a single focus group not considered to be sufficient and the number of people can result in either insufficient or too much interaction within the focus group (Cohen et al., 2009). There are other disadvantages of focus groups: they tend not to yield data that is generalizable; data analysis can be challenging; and group dynamics can influence levels of participation (Krueger and Casey, 2015). The goal of this qualitative study was not to generalise, and the moderator can go a long way to in overcoming participation issues (Krueger and Casey, 2015). The selection of the moderator is discussed later in this chapter.

Question Design

The questions for the focus group were designed by brainstorming then sequencing, phrasing, and timing were considered. Feedback was then sought and used to revise questions before piloting them (Krueger and Casey, 2015). This meant that the first step of question design, brainstorming, focussed on information provided by the participants in an initial survey (Morgan, 2014). For efficiency, to devise better questions and in the knowledge that the initial survey would provide information, the researcher completed brainstorming individually to devise key questions (Krueger and Casey, 2015). Following that questions were organised with general questions first to stimulate discussion and then became narrower and more focussed (Krueger and Casey, 2015). Other principles that were utilised in designing the order of the questions included placing positive questions before negative questions (Krueger and Casey, 2015) to allow participants to offer insight into both sides of the topic under

discussion, which can be particularly important for students in education settings where they may 'launch into criticism of those who have control and power' (Krueger and Casey, 2015, p.62).

Probes / prompts, open ended phrasing and a sweeping final question were used to try to ensure topic was explored fully (Krueger and Casey, 2015). Participants were encouraged to speak to their feelings about their experiences (Cohen et al., 2009) and follow up questions were used to reduce the chance that in analysis it is concluded that what is mentioned most often is equated to being the most important (Krueger and Casey, 2015). Given the focus of the study 'think back' questions were used cautiously ensuring that they asked about recent events / experiences so that participants can recall the experience effectively and 'why' questions were avoided to help participants feel free to express their views (Krueger and Casey, 2015). Short, simple, clear questions that sounded conversational were planned to try to ensure participants knew what was being asked of them (Krueger and Casey, 2015). Examples were only used in probes to gain further insight so as not to restrict the initial thinking of participants (Krueger and Casey, 2015). Questions were reviewed considering complexity, category, and type of question to identify how long they might take in the focus group. Less time was estimated for introductory questions than for key questions with flexibility built in for late arrivals and to summarise at the end (Krueger and Casey, 2015). Following this, questions were piloted (discussed in a later section) and an example of a focus group schedule used in this study can be seen in Appendix 5.

Interviews

In the teaching profession when you want to get information the natural thing to do is talk and discuss (Drever, 2003) and interviews have the potential to provide insights into perspectives (Morgan and Mannay, 2014). Because of this, interviews are commonly used in IPA research (Smith et al., 2009) and were selected for this project to allow individual stories to emerge in the final stage of data collection.

Semi-structured interviews (SSIs) are commonly associated with IPA and education (Biggerstaff and Thompson, 2008). This is because they can yield rich data, aid gaining

clarification, provide flexibility to follow participants views, support observation / recording of tone / facial experiences and can generally be organised easily (Menter et al., 2011; Bell, 2010). They are highly time consuming and subjective which can introduce bias; analysis can also be challenging and at times it can be hard to coordinate schedules (Menter et al., 2011; Cohen et al., 2009). Despite their potential disadvantages time spent on SSIs are worthwhile for the 'rich' data (Gilham, 2008) which combined with previous experience in SSIs led to their selection as a data collection method in this study. Steps were taken to try to overcome some of the potential disadvantages such using a timeline for the project alongside the initial and follow-up communications to organise the proposed interviews (Appendix 7 & 4 respectively).

It was also necessary to consider question design for the interviews which, if done effectively, can mean that the benefits are achieved and the costs minimised (Mertens, 2005). Thus, careful consideration of the topics to be covered is needed in designing the questions and interview schedule (Johnson and Christensen, 2008). However, the questions on the interview schedule are often used as a 'guide' and straying from the guide is often encouraged particularly as it allows the question and answers to be a topic for discussion (Silverman, 2013, p.204). There is no 'recipe' for successfully conducting interviews but there are things that can increase the chance of success (Silverman, 2013, p.204). These include piloting your interview schedule and asking questions that support you to get information that might answer your research questions without asking these questions directly (Silverman, 2013). As a result, attention was paid to wording in designing the questions to try to capture participants' views on the topic. It was projected that the interview would take 30 to 45 minutes to complete. A copy of the interview schedule can be seen in Appendix 6.

Ethics, Access, and Informed Consent

Ethical considerations arise in any type of research, but in qualitative research they are 'sometimes more acute' as they 'often involved the collection of the most sensitive, intimate, and innermost matters in people's lives' (Punch, 2009, p.50). Consideration of ethical issues is inevitable in research involving people and typically involves dilemmas or conflicts and negotiated trade-offs are often needed rather than the application of rules (Miles et al.,

2014). All researchers wrangle with the issue of ethics, mostly as they have the responsibility to protect the participants within the research project (O'Toole and Beckett, 2010). These issues include consent, avoiding harm, beneficial results, and competence (Punch, 2009). The participant information sheet and consent form for this project were the two main ways utilised to protect participants (Appendix 2 & 3). The university ethics application was completed which required demonstration that the project would be undertaken ethically and approval for the study was given by the ethics board (Appendix 15).

A multifaceted consent form was used in the research project to recognise that consent is an ongoing process (Punch, 2009) and participants were allowed to choose their level of participation. The form made it clear that the university was assessing the project and should the question of publication arise later the permission of those involved will be sought. As is recommended, the supporting documentation made clear that official approval had been given along with an outline of confidentiality / anonymity and how the data would be treated (Bell, 2010). Confidentiality is a complex ethical issue in focus groups (Litosseliti, 2003), though it must also be considered in interviews (Mertens, 2005). Confidentiality is when only the researcher knows the identity of the study participant (Johnson and Christensen, 2008). When transcribing, pseudonyms were used to keep the data confidential, and quotations were assigned to their pseudonyms when presenting findings. Participants in the focus group are also responsible for keeping what they hear confidential (Litosseliti, 2003), and participants were encouraged to do so as well as use generic/neutral terms such as placement school or school-based mentor to avoid identifying specific places or people.

There is also a responsibility to the wider research community that the researcher presents themselves to the participants as being competent, supportive, and trustworthy (Cohen et al., 2009). This was achieved through planning and preparation for the data collection as well as the participant information sheet which outlined the purpose of the research and how the information will be handled. Portraying competence and trustworthiness must also be demonstrated when reporting the research and careful attention was paid so as not to falsify, suppress, or invent research findings and not anticipating the impact of the research findings (Creswell, 2009). The 'integrity and conscience' of the researcher will determine the response to any ethical issues that arise (Cohen et al., 2009, p.73) and, with guidance and 'professional

judgment', this was done with consideration for the participants at the forefront (SERA, 2005). The established working relationship between the participants and the researcher is based on trust and mutual respect but in this evolving relationship dynamic it is important that trusting relationship continues as it is shown as being important to participant motivation (Dillman et al., 2008). In this study, ensuring confidentiality and security of the participants' information was one of the ways that trust was earned. The study had been given ethical approval by the university which offers a type of sponsorship by a recognised authority. However, given that this 'recognised authority' is also the institution from which the participants graduated there are potential power issues that could come into play here (discussed later).

Initial invitation was done in person with participants given time to review the information and to ask any questions before deciding whether to participate. To support recall, this was done at the end of the PGDE so that the participants could reflect on their experiences that had just finished. Participants were given two weeks to respond, and a personalised reminder email was sent after one week (Dillman et al., 2008). A similar process was used for coordinating the interviews later in the data collection cycle but with the initial invite being via email rather than in person. An overview of the timeline of the data collection can be seen in Appendix 7.

Sample

As is recommend for IPA studies, a non-probability, purposive sample was used (Smith et al., 2009) with the entire cohort of PE graduates from the PGDE invited to participate. This means it should be possible to uncover participant accounts both for shared themes and for distinctive voices and variations of these themes (Smith et al., 2009) which are of great interest to this study. The researcher acknowledges that it is then difficult to make generalisations from the study but of greater interest in this study is how things come to be for a very specific group of individuals. Quality (not quantity) is important in an IPA study and the choice of sample size depends on organisational constraints, the degree of commitment to case level analysis and the richness of the individual cases (Smith et al., 2009). At this level, it is advocated that three related studies of around 10 cases are attempted (Smith et al.,

2009) and this led to the selection of three data collection cycles throughout this study in the hope that this would lead to the ‘ability to consider the essential features of a particular phenomenon’ (Smith et al., 2009, p.38).

Participants came from a range of backgrounds with undergraduate degrees in Sport and Exercise Science, Physical Activity and Health, Sports Coaching or Sports Studies (this is further broken down in appendix 16). When completing the consent form, most participants indicated an interest in participating at both levels of the research but, inevitably, the logistics or personal circumstances (or both) influenced whether the participants could fulfil their initial commitment to future contribution to the research project. This can be seen in the reduction of numbers across the data collection stages shown in figure 1 below.

	Potential Participants	Focus Groups	Interviews
2015	14 (7 Female, 7 Male)	11 (5 female, 6 male)	4 (2 male, 2 female)
% of possible participants	100%	78.57%	28.57%
2016	16 (9 Male, 7 Female)	8 (5 Male, 3 Female)	4 (2 Male, 2 Female)
% of possible participants	100%	50%	25%
2017	12 (6 male, 6 Female)	6 (3 male, 3 Female)	3 (2 male, 1 Female)
% of possible participants	100%	50%	25%
Overall	42	25	11
% of possible participants	100%	59.52%	26.19%

Figure 1: Sample Overview

The potential implications / limitations of the sample are addressed later in this chapter. The following sections outline specific actions taken within each data collection phase.

Data Collection

Focus Group

Success of focus groups rely on group composition (Krueger and Casey, 2015) and members should be 'chosen so as to be directly relevant to the topic area' (Gilham, 2008, p.35). All PE graduates from the PGDE programme were invited to be part of the focus groups using the PIS and the consent form. Follow-up communication was used to share details of the organisation of the focus group. Participation in the focus group was voluntary and, as a result, it was not guaranteed that the participants within the study reflected the demographic of the overall population.

Focus groups took place following the conclusion of the PGDE programme. Two focus groups were completed in each data cycle except for the 2016 where only one was completed due to participant response. In the case where there were two focus groups, two different locations were offered for the convenience of the participants. The specific timing of each focus group was identified in consultation with the participants so that they were planned at a convenient time for them. The facilities used for the focus groups were set up in a group discussion format) and drinks/snacks were offered to try to make the environment as comfortable as possible (Litosseliti, 2003). The audio from the focus group was recorded to support transcription. Some advocate that a focus group should take two hours, but in the case of a focused study, like this research study, they may successfully be completed in less (Krueger and Casey, 2015). The focus groups that were conducted in the study fell within the expected time frame (45-60 minutes), but they tended to be closer to 60 minutes in duration.

Interviews

Interviews were undertaken towards the end of the participants' probationary year. All participants were invited to contribute at this stage using personalised initial invitations and

follow-up invitations. Interviews were arranged at a time and location that was convenient for the participant. Four interviews were conducted in each data cycle except for the final data collection cycle where three interviews were completed. The length of each of the interviews fell within the predicted time of 30 - 45 minutes apart from one interview in the 2017 which lasted almost an hour. In this case, permission was sought and gained from the participant to continue beyond the initially predicted duration. Interviews were audio recorded with notes taken during interviews to help with transcription / analysis (Bell, 2010). This requires high skill levels from the interviewer, who must ask the questions; listen to the answers; observe the respondents; and write down notes (O'Toole and Beckett, 2010). Through piloting, the researcher had the opportunity to hone the necessary skills (Creswell, 2009). These skills and strategies combined with well-structured interview questions aimed at supporting the rich material to be produced in the interviews.

Data Analysis

IPA frames the whole study but was also employed as a method of analysis to explore the meaning attached to particular experiences and social interactions (Smith, Jarman and Osborn, 1994). In using IPA there is the decision to explore how particular experiences are understood from the perspectives of participants and there is a commitment to exploring, describing, interpreting, and situating how participants make sense of their experiences so analysis 'must be thorough and systematic' (Smith et al., 2009, p.28). This section will outline the steps taken to employ IPA during the analysis of the interview and focus group data.

Focus groups and interviews were audio recorded then transcribed including things such as pauses, mishearing's, apparent mistakes, and speech dynamics where noteworthy (Biggerstaff and Thomson, 2008). The transcription of the focus groups took about 14 hours total and about 33 hours for the interviews. While it was not possible to include all transcripts an example of transcripts can be found in appendix 9 and 11 respectively. The transcripts were reviewed alongside the audio recording and checked for accuracy with descriptive information noted at the top of the transcript. The transcripts were then prepared for analysis with each line of text being numbered to provide an identifier during analysis.

IPA is intended to be flexible, where common processes and principles can be applied to achieve a detailed, nuanced analysis of participants experiences (Smith et al., 2009). The process focuses on moving from the 'descriptive to the interpretive' and the principles have 'a commitment to understanding the participants' point of view': both are intended to uncover how participants make sense of particular life experiences (Smith et al., 2009, p.79). Analysis within IPA is an iterative and inductive cycle (Smith, 2007). The figure below outlines the analysis process:

Actions	Purpose
Close Reading and Re-Reading	Immersing in the original data
Initial Noting	Examining and exploring content and language
Re-Reading	Developing Emerging Themes from transcript and exploratory notes
Mapping	Searching for connections across emergent themes. Creating 'super-ordinate themes'
Repeat	Repeating steps above for transcripts being analysed
Looking for patterns	Looking at themes and superordinate themes across cases to identify patterns

Figure 2: IPA Process

In the initial stages of analysis, the audio recording was used to have 'active engagement' with the data with initial first impressions being noted separately to be immersed in the data (Smith et al., 2009, p.83). This was extended in the next stage where the 'analyst maintains an open mind and notes anything of interest within the transcript' and highlighting ways in which participants understood, talked, and thought about the topic under study (Smith et al., 2009, p.83). This is close to free-textual analysis with the goal of producing a commentary on the transcript and there are no 'rules' on what is commented on (Smith et al., 2009, p.83). This was done by going through each transcript and underlining text which seemed important and then writing notes in the margin why this could potentially be important (Smith et al.,

2009) with deconstruction used to bring into 'detailed focus the participants' words and meanings' (Smith et al., 2009, p.90).

Initial noting aimed to reduce volume of detail in transcripts while mapping connections to support development of themes and understanding why things of interest might be important in capturing the participants' experiences and views (Smith et al., 2009). The next stage involved searching for connections across the themes in a process of 'mapping' (Smith et al., 2009, p.96) where themes were chronologically ordered, printed, and cut up so that the analyst could move around each theme. Two strategies were used: placing 'like with like' and creating a new name for this super-ordinate theme (abstraction); or one of the emergent themes becomes the super-ordinate theme (subsumption) (Smith et al., 2009). These were then collated to support the final phase of the analysis: looking for patterns across cases (Smith et al., 2009). To get to this final phase, the previous phases were repeated for each transcript for each of the focus groups and interviews.

The final phase reviewed the superordinate themes where they were printed and laid out and the analyst visually looked for connections, explanations or themes emerging more strongly (Smith et al., 2009). Themes were then reconfigured or re-labelled where necessary with illustrative excerpts used to capture the most important things said by the participants about their experiences (Smith et al. 2009). Consideration of what is a 'recurrent' theme is important to quality of findings, again no specific rule is advocated but criterion must be established (Smith et al., 2009). In this study, it was decided that for a finding to be classified as a recurrent theme that it must be present in at least half of the participant accounts. This supported identifying patterns across the participants shared experiences to establish key themes for the group (Smith et al., 2009). These were exemplified with illustrative accounts from individuals which were read and re-read while thinking about what they say in their 'totality' (Smith et al. 2009, p.114). Following this, the focus shifted to summarising key points of the shared experiences to get a sense of the whole picture with several extracts selected proportionately to represent and reflect the core of the participants' experiences (Smith et al., 2009). Where present atypical extracts were selected to illustrate the contradiction or complexity of participants' experiences (Smith et al., 2009). Extracts were then linked to the group experience working in the 'hermeneutic circle, constantly and

dynamically moving between part and whole' writing narrative that links themes and relates to the overall analysis (Smith et al., 2009, p.116). An example of an analysed transcript can be seen in appendix 8 and 10.

This close reading and re-reading requires systematic and rigorous efforts as well as critical and conceptual thinking to support the interpretive nature of IPA (Smith et al., 2009). All of which highlights the need to be aware of the influence the researcher and while it is not always possible to be aware of all the preconceptions that might influence analysis, IPA with its 'reflective and cyclical approach to bracketing' can support researchers in acknowledging preconceptions in advance of and during analysis (Smith et al., 2009 p.35). This along with other potential influences are explored further in the next section.

Trustworthiness

In qualitative research, terms such as 'credibility', 'trustworthiness', 'dependability', and 'transferability' (Cohen et al., 2009) are important to the quality of the research (Silverman, 2013) and methods must focus on the accuracy and comprehensiveness of the data captured in a study (Creswell, 2009). Through the close reading and re-reading that is used in IPA analysis, the transcripts are analysed in greater detail to look for other influences on what the participants said as well as how views were expressed (Silverman, 2013). Considering the impact of the researcher / participant relationship is important to trustworthiness (Silverman, 2013). This relationship, although influential in study decisions, was considered a positive in this study.

The methods used in this study can provide different perspectives with interviews being able to triangulate other methods and provide more confidence in research results which can be supported by checking findings with participants (Best and Kahn, 2006). This is one of the key strengths of IPA as it can facilitate critique, feedback, and elaboration of research findings to ensure that the interpretations reflect the meaning of the participants (Smith et al., 2009). In this study, transcripts and a summary of findings were sent to all participants for them to review the accuracy of the interpretations and conclusions. As there was the potential that participants may wish to change / refine the data, participants were asked to provide comments for reference purposes. In addition, during the interviews, participants were

encouraged to compare their individual experiences to the interpretations from the focus groups. It is here we see connections to the focus of IPA on convergence and divergence of the experience of participants within groups of the phenomena under study which requires comparisons between the individual experiences of participants in the study (Hefferon and Gil-Rodriguez, 2011). In addition, seeking the views of multiple participants can provide a more detailed multifaceted account which is another kind of triangulation and contributes to trustworthiness within a study (Smith et al., 2009). This highlights the importance of being aware of any potential influence of the researcher and IPA with its 'reflective and cyclical approach to bracketing' can support researchers in acknowledging preconceptions in advance of and during analysis (Smith et al., 2009, p.35).

Additionally, consideration needed to be given to any exclusions or over representation in the sample as arguably data from these participants could have provided valuable insight (Silverman, 2013). The decision to have a purposive, albeit convenient, sample was a pragmatic one and this then excluded PE graduates from other institutions. However, this study was particularly interested in the experiences of the graduates from one TEI and thus individuals from that population were invited to participate in the study. A gap was noted when reviewing the sample, students who had not completed their ITE did not participate despite being invited to do so. It is possible that these students self-selected to not participate as they did not feel they could take part as they had not yet completed their ITE. While this was only 3 students (7% possible participants), those participants experiences could have led to additional insight on perceived preparedness. It is also plausible that they could have had more negative experiences and influenced the data as a result.

One of the key decisions taken to support trustworthiness, was the timing of the data collection as choosing an appropriate time scale helps to minimise threats to the research (Cohen et al., 2009). The data collection cycle was carefully planned to begin at the end of the participants' ITE programme to reduce pressure to participate as well as giving time and space to reflect on experiences and to support recall (Dillman et al., 2008). This was significant as it potentially reduced the risk that participants might feel that they needed to participate to get into the good favour of the researcher (who is also their lecturer) and that participating in the research may have an influence on their successful completion of the course. On the other side of this, it is possible that already knowing the outcome of their

grades may have had an impact on their feelings of preparedness, for example, if a student had failed it is feasible to think that they would be feeling unprepared. However, it was felt that offsetting the potential influence of the power relationship was more important and that the timing would be aligned to reduce that potential impact.

The established researcher / participant relationship meant considering the potential influence of this was a key consideration. An established relationship might lead to participants being more willing to contribute and can aid with access to the field (Berger, 2015) and because of this, participants were receptive to engaging with the study and cooperative in arranging interviews / focus groups. The relationship also means the researcher has knowledge about the topic under study which has the potential to support them to understand responses in a more nuanced way (Padgett, 2008). However, it might impact the information participants feel comfortable sharing or influence the way the researcher views the data (Berger, 2015) and subsequently might shape the findings and conclusions of the study (Kacem and Chaitin, 2006). For example, as the lead lecturer for PE, I have an integral role in the experiences under investigation in this study and these could consciously or unconsciously impact my views. These effects exist in all types of research (Berger, 2015) and reflexivity was used to monitor the impact of these with the goal of enhancing the study (Bradbury-Jones, 2007).

Though the advantages of this position strengthen the research study, there is still the potential that boundaries are blurred; the values, beliefs and perceptions of the researcher can be intrusive, and biases may be projected (Drake, 2010). This was particularly true at the final stage of data collection where I conducted the interviews. After each interview, I reflected on the interview overall to examine whether questions were consciously or subconsciously emphasised. Alongside this, in the reflection post-interview, I considered my reactions to participants throughout the interview. Doing this helped me to become aware of their potential influence on the research (Berger, 2015) and in turn reduce any potential bias in future interviews. Additionally, I employed various methods of 'self-supervision' (Berger, 2015, p.222) throughout the research project: including prolonged engagement in reflection; member checking; a peer support network; a research journal; and an audit trail. While these

were utilised throughout the research project, they also played a significant role in the piloting that was undertaken during the study.

Piloting

Piloting supports checking for ambiguity or imprecision and is important during the design stage (Menter et al., 2011). For this project, a two-stage process for piloting was employed, initially with colleagues and then with the first data collection cycle. During the final stage of developing the focus group and interview schedules colleagues reviewed and gave feedback on whether the draft questions were appropriate to get the information needed; were understandable; flowed from one to the other; included any redundant questions; and whether any questions had been omitted with revisions being made where needed (Krueger and Casey, 2015). Piloting in this way helps to formulate schedules (Silverman, 2013) so these piloting strategies were continued whenever a new schedule was being devised.

Piloting in this way though does not support the trialling of some other key elements like recruitment strategies, the workability or realities of the process which might indicate the feasibility of the study, nor does it support the practice of things like interview techniques and because of this, piloting was also undertaken during the first cycle of data collection. Piloting in this way supported the testing, building up and refining of data collection and analysis strategies. This was particularly important for some elements of the IPA like bracketing which supports the researcher to focus on the interpretation of meanings (Smith et al., 2009). In addition, piloting in this way supported a process of refining the content to make the process as meaningful as possible to the participants which is linked to potentially gaining valuable data (Cohen et al., 2018). Thus, being able to practice and refine this while going through data collection cycle was considered important to the study.

Piloting Review and Implications

During the first round of data collection participants reflected on their experiences and the language used in questions to try to uncover any potential ambiguity or unclear language (Cohen et al., 2009). Participants were asked about the clarity of instructions, questions and

were allowed to identify any topics that had been missed or omitted and provide any additional comments. The form used for review can be seen in appendix 12 and a completed example of the form is included in appendix 13. Alongside the participant, the researcher engaged in a review both of which led to some implications for later data collection cycles.

One of the most profound realisations was that the timing of the interviews could be more effective. This was highlighted in the review of the focus groups with participants stating, and the researcher reflecting, that participants would be in a stronger position to contribute to the discussion on levels of preparedness as early-phase practitioners after their probationary year had been completed. This could facilitate an interesting opportunity for participants to reflect on whether they were as prepared as they thought they were, which will be key to understanding the impact of their preparedness. Thus, the decision was taken to move the interviews from their original planned time to one year later at the end of the participants' probationary year and this happened in all data collection cycles.

A few points arose from the review of the focus groups – participants highlighted that being able to ask for clarification/repetition of the questions helped with clarity where needed. This was discussed with the moderator as a planned part of the focus group schedule and given the importance placed on this by participants, this practice was continued throughout later data collection cycles. Reflections indicated that the presence of the researcher had the potential to impact the conversation within the focus group. So, while taking notes and observing non-verbal behaviours are valuable to analysis, it was felt that to reduce any potential influence the researcher would not be present for the focus group.

The review of the interviews (one year later than planned) reaffirmed the decision to move the timing of the data collection. Researcher reflections and observations highlighted that, within the interviews, participants were offered a valuable chance to recall experiences and reflect on their current levels of preparedness compared with their views upon graduation. The participants reviewed elements such as question wording and instructions and indicated that questions were generally unambiguous. The participants noted that the opportunity to seek clarification supported them in understanding what was being asked of them. Participants shared that the environment was one where participants felt they could share

openly and honestly about their levels of preparedness. The researcher reflected that, as many of the participants still had a vested interest in the quality of the ITE course (many were mentors to current students), this appeared to encourage deeper reflection and more thoughtful responses from participants.

The decision to include the data collected while piloting was the final implication of this as it can produce preliminary data that can be useful to contribute to the study overall (Cohen, et al., 2018). During the analysis it became clear that the participants had some insight that would be useful for answering the research questions and that the inclusion of the piloting data might provide a fuller picture. This raises potential concerns around contamination which can occur if there are significant changes in the tools because of piloting (Van Teijlingen and Hundley, 2001). It is acknowledged that there were small differences between the tools used in the pilot study such as changes to fix typographical errors and some small amendments to wording but the more significant changes (such as the timing of the interviews) happened before the data was collected and thus followed a similar pattern to that of the main study, so contamination was not likely to occur. Contamination is less of a concern in qualitative studies and researchers often use some or all their piloting data as part of the main study (Van Teijlingen and Hundley, 2001). Considering this and the researcher reflecting that they had an ethical responsibility to include the data collected, the piloting data was included alongside the main study data.

Overall, piloting served its planned purpose of testing data collection tools and methods of analysis, and this was significant as this has the potential to increase the quality of the research as results and inform later parts of the study (Malmqvist et al., 2019). It also supplied an opportunity for the researcher and moderator to practice the skills needed for data collection and analysis and as such is linked to the concept of 'trustworthiness' and increasing this within the study (Cohen et al., 2009). Finally, it supplied some interesting and valuable insights into the experiences of one graduating student that led to the inclusion of this data, and this will be presented later in the findings and discussion.

Reflexivity

No research is free from influences such as personality biases and assumptions and, when we are closely involved in the topic under investigation, it is difficult to separate those (Sword, 1999). Through reflexivity, we must recognise them, acknowledge them, and seek to offset any influence which requires openness and an acceptance that the researcher is part of the research (Finlay, 1998). Many of the factors that influence this were considered in the preceding sections e.g., piloting as well as the thorough planning and preparation for the data collection. This section will consider three key areas - the possibility of social desirability bias, the importance of construct validity and power issues.

Social desirability bias is a tendency to present reality to align with what is perceived to be socially acceptable and while it may be difficult to remove from qualitative research it can be minimized (Bergen and Labonte, 2020). Construct validity 'must demonstrate that the categories which the researchers are using reflect how the participants actually experience and construe the situations in the research' (Cohen et al., 2018, p.257). Power relations are 'immanent in all research settings' (Brooks et al., 2014, p.106) with the research often being viewed as having more power than the participants necessitating the need to take steps to address the issues that might arise (Cohen et al., 2018). In the study, these were a central consideration in many of the decisions made during the design that were then implemented during data collection and analysis. Strategies to reduce bias included clear methods for introducing the study, utilizing the established rapport, and asking questions alongside pre-fieldwork training with data collectors and regular debriefing sessions (Bergen and Labonte, 2020). This section will highlight some of those key considerations and decisions for each of the data collection tools and make connections to the concept of trustworthiness (Lincoln and Guba, 2000).

Focus Group

The impact of this established researcher-participant relationship and the potential for power to influence the data was a strong consideration in the design of the focus group. It was decided an independent moderator was needed as this can potentially minimise bias by

reducing any conflict of interest, thereby encouraging participants to express themselves freely (Berger, 2015). It was hoped that this could eliminate any conscious or unconscious efforts by the researcher to shape the conversation. It could be argued that, as the researcher designed the focus group schedule, some influence still existed. As one of the aims of the focus group was to consider agreement (or not) with the presented questions and topics, it was hoped that participants would be able to 'member check' the themes identified in the survey to minimise any potential bias that might exist (Cohen et al., 2009). Despite the presence of an independent moderator, there could still be elements of implied content within the focus group (Berger, 2015), this is where knowledge of the topic supported the researcher to better understand this during analysis and be potentially more aware of certain aspects of the data that might have gone unnoticed otherwise. The moderator selected for this study was one who had previous experience facilitating focus groups, who had some knowledge of the higher education setting in which the research study was situated but who was not connected to the delivery of the ITE course.

The purpose of a focus group is to focus on discussion of a particular issue - structured or unstructured - and gain multiple views and attitudes in relation to the issue (Litosseliti, 2003). In this scenario, the moderator becomes important as the intention is that the participants will interact with each other and potentially reach a consensus on the issues discussed. However, it could be in the discussion, not the consensus, that the most valuable insights are uncovered (Mertens, 2005). There is immense value in asking about opposite views, but care must be taken to ensure that one viewpoint (either positive or negative) does not dominate: it is the moderator's role to encourage the group to have a full discussion of both sides (Krueger and Casey, 2015). The success of a focus group hinges on 'well-developed questions asked of the right respondents, but another ingredient is essential: a skillful moderator' (Krueger and Casey, 2015, p.103). Often the moderator is automatically assumed to be the lead researcher with not much thought given to what makes an effective moderator. The researcher had previous experience with conducting focus groups during master's level study and was considered for leading the groups. However, given the already established close relationship between the researcher and the participants, care it was decided that a moderator who was not directly associated with the participants' course of study could ease the potential pressure that participants may feel (Cohen et al., 2018).

In addition to this attention was given to the skills needed to be effective in this role as it requires great skill and is indeed a complex and challenging role (Mertens, 2005). Often there is a danger that some participants' voices will be silenced during the focus group, but this can be brought out by skilled moderation which creates an open, friendly, and non-threatening environment and encourages participants to be forthcoming (Litosseliti, 2003). Ensuring that everyone has their say is one of the key parts of managing a focus group (Johnson and Christensen, 2008). With the use of external stimulus and skilled questioning, the moderator can work to ensure that all participants' opinions and views are heard (Gilham, 2008). The moderator can also use periodic checks to discover whether all group members agree with the statement being made or, if they do not then their views can be heard. This is useful in counteracting 'group think' where the group unconsciously takes on a set of views or opinions that might not accurately reflect their personal views (O'Toole and Beckett, 2010). It is possible that, as a group of students who have studied together, the participants already have an element of this 'group think'. However, there is also the potential that they are more able to participate effectively in a focus group because they know each other and have been in this discussion setting before (O'Toole and Beckett, 2010).

The open approach of a focus group is of great benefit for uncovering rich data, but it is necessary to proceed with an outlined plan of the areas to be covered - otherwise chaos is a real risk (Gilham, 2008). Alongside this, the moderator needs to know enough about the topic to steer or focus the discussion (Peterson, 2000) which although the selected moderator was not connected to the PGDE they had experience in Higher education and some understanding of teacher education. Gilham (2008) offers a potential solution to some of these challenges: have two researchers in focus groups - one to facilitate, and one to record key or novel elements that are thrown up by the rapid movement of the debate this raises additional challenges in terms of logistics as well potential additional concerns about bias, so only one facilitator was used in this project. Even with an independent moderator, there is the potential that they may bring bias to a study. However, if one moderator is used and they are careful of language and try not to show their stance, efforts can be made to minimise any potential bias (Litosseliti, 2003). Focus groups are intentionally planned to prompt more of the participants' points of view than would be gained in more researcher-dominated interviews (Mertens, 2005) and the moderator plays a key role in this. However, transcription

of focus groups is challenging, as participants may be talking over each other. Some suggest filming so that speakers can be more readily identified in such cases (Litosseliti, 2003). However, this was not used due to concerns about the students being easily identifiable and limiting their answers to what they thought the researcher wanted to hear. A neutral location was also chosen for the focus groups to try to avoid negative or positive associations with places or people. The convenience of the location was also considered to increase the chance that participants could contribute to the focus group and support the gathering of as many views as possible.

The choice of the moderator alongside moderator/researcher interactions also played a significant part in reducing bias. As a result, the researcher and the moderator spent additional time preparing for the focus group and the moderator was asked where possible to record any relevant non-verbal communications from the participants and debriefing between the researcher and the focus group facilitator was significant to the analysis of the data (Kreuger and Casey, 2015). As a result, after each focus group the moderator and the researcher spent time discussing the focus group and the notes that the moderator had taken. These supported researcher reflections on the focus group process though did not result in any changes to the focus groups.

Interviews

Unlike in the case of the focus groups, the researcher was the interviewer, and this choice was due to the change in the relationship and the desire to take advantage of the potential positive influences of the insider knowledge e.g., knowing when to probe in interviews (Berger, 2015). This offered positives as the participants were familiar with the researcher, they were potentially more at ease and keen to help add to the data (Bell, 2010). However, again there are potential power issues given the established researcher-participant relationship (Berger, 2015). The decision is highly significant, as it may either validate or seriously corrupt your data (Creswell and Plano-Clark, 2011). The interviews were conducted at a point when the participants had been away from ITE for a year and the relationship had evolved from a student-teacher relationship to one more akin to colleagues. This shift is evidenced in two key examples: the researcher no longer has an input into the evaluation of

the participants' performance as a teacher; participants had contributed to the ITE in ways such as interviewing prospective candidates and mentoring current students. This potentially indicates that the participants had a continued interest in the strength of the ITE programme. Though there is still the potential that the participants may want something from the researcher i.e., a reference for a job, the relationship was a familiar one more akin to being colleagues which could potentially be advantageous in interviews, particularly with recruitment and an understanding of the topic under study (Berger, 2015). This familiarity with the participants' context can elicit more specific answers and allow for the checking of responses (Berger, 2015). However, familiarity can also alter the data participants give you as they might give you the answer, they think you want to hear, might withhold vital information because they think it might upset you, or fear the consequences elsewhere and might also be influenced by the obvious investment that the researcher has in the interview and study (O'Toole and Beckett, 2010). This is where the researcher must work to minimise the risk of any potential corruption or bias that might arise.

The researcher has experience in interviewing in several contexts such as conducting undergraduate and master's research. Alongside this as part of their role undertakes hundreds of admissions interviews every year and frequently sits on interview panels for applicants for teacher educator positions within the school of education – all of which have provided experience and opportunity to develop the ability to maintain neutral expressions and responses working to give no indication of desired response during the interview process. This could be in the form of a verbal or non-verbal response and thus the interviewer can become quite influential in any aims to reduce any potential bias (Anderson-Knott, 2008). Additional practice was undertaken as part of piloting to work on maintaining neutrality in both tones of voice and responses such as 'thank you for your thoughts' as is advocated in the pursuit of interviewer neutrality (Anderson-Knott, 2008) in relation to these specific interview questions.

In this chapter, the methodology (IPA) and methods for data collection and analysis for this research project have been outlined. The ethical considerations, as well as trustworthiness of this project, have also been considered. In the following chapters, the research findings and discussion from the study will be presented.

Findings and Discussion

This chapter of the thesis presents the findings from all data collection cycles and presents practitioners' views of their levels of preparedness alongside the factors which impact this perceived preparedness. It puts forth that early-phase practitioners perceive themselves as being prepared for some, but not all, aspects of their responsibility for HWB. It highlights that feelings of preparedness are equated to readiness as probationary teachers and outlines that factors such as confidence, competence, placement, context, and experience(s) are seen to have an impact on the participants' feelings of preparedness. In doing so, this chapter begins to highlight the potential answers to the research questions of this study.

In line with IPA as a methodology, the themes will be described and exemplified with extracts from participants, accompanied by analytic comments (Pietkiewicz and Smith, 2012). Throughout the chapters, the participants' stories will be used to present a narrative of the findings and the graduating year will be utilised to provide a timeframe for the participants' quotations. When quoting of participants, if words have been excluded, ellipsis will be used to indicate this. When words were implied or missed in the participants' speech, they will be included by using square brackets. As is commonplace in an IPA project, the narrative account is followed by a discussion which relates each of the identified themes to existing literature (Pietkiewicz and Smith, 2012). These are presented to align with the model offered by Menter et al. (2010) which identifies the four categories of teacher: the effective teacher; the reflective teacher; the enquiring teacher; and the transformative teacher.

The Effective Teacher

In line with the international literature presented in Menter et al. (2010) there were several instances where effectiveness or perception of effectiveness was linked to the participants feelings of preparedness. This includes participants understanding of HWB and some instances of how to embed that within their practice effectively. This section considers those instances and other factors that impact the preparedness of participants in the study.

HWB Understanding

Making effective links to HWB within lessons was offered by several participants as the reason they viewed themselves to be prepared for meeting their HWB responsibility. For many participants, this was equated to the understanding that they had developed in HWB. Kevin (2017), shared during the focus group, this was the main reason he attributed to his perceived preparedness, as 'The course gave me a good understanding of HWB elements, and I feel comfortable planning to ensure HWB in all my classes'. Similarly, during his focus group, Russell (2015) declared that his 'placement schools have also been doing a great deal of development work on this' and this helped developed his understanding. This highlights that ITE had supported participants in feeling prepared to meet their HWB responsibility through developing understanding and being able to effectively incorporate HWB in classes, which is an important responsibility for PE teachers (Teraoka and Kirk, 2021).

In linking preparation and effective teaching, we see the mention of the first type of teacher, as described by Menter et al. (2010). It is expected that the participants, who are early-phase teachers, would express views that indicate they are at this stage as they are still trying to figure out what effective teaching is. There are also strong links between preparedness and teacher efficacy, with mastery experiences during ITE and the induction year being viewed as the most crucial factors contributing to teacher efficacy (Protheroe, 2008). This potentially can be achieved by being able to understand HWB and make links within lessons which participants shared as being important to them feeling prepared. However, the inclusion of an experience and outcome in each lesson plan does not necessarily equate to effective delivery of HWB. This indicates that, for the participants to feel prepared, there is the need for a focus on HWB during campus activities, as well as the opportunity for them to apply that to their practice. It is possible that being made aware of their responsibilities is 'enough' and that continued development is needed throughout their career as teacher education is a lifelong journey for which ITE sets the foundations (Biesta, 2017), and this appears to contribute to feelings of preparedness for the participants in the current study.

Subject 'Stuff' Matters

Much attention was paid by the participants to the subject knowledge developed within university PE classes. These subject specific classes were led by the PE tutors, were only for the PE students, and focused on teaching PE. Across all data collection cycles participants felt that 'engaging PE classes and activities from these sessions such as micro-teaching and sharing good practice were important to them feeling prepared. Monica (2016) indicated at the end of her probationary year, that the subject-specific 'stuff' was still very important but that 'there are some things that you can't prepare for'. It has been highlighted that it takes three to five years to become an 'expert' teacher (Berliner, 2004, p.202) so it is not surprising that early-phase teachers have not yet felt fully prepared. The importance attached to these activities could be because 'modelling is important and it has the potential to be the glue by which ITE is made coherent to students' (Boyd, 2014, p.56). However, it could also be because of insufficient content knowledge development in the participants undergraduate degree which has been raised as a concern with students in postgraduate teacher education routes in other areas of the UK such as England (Gower and Capel, 2004). The value placed on the subject-specific classes could question what has been thought to be a strength of the PGDE programme, that candidates had studied their subject first before studying education. Given the routes into the PGDE it is hoped that content knowledge of different activities was developed as part of that but there is no imperative to consider HWB which might have resulted in the subject-specific classes being more significant to feelings of preparedness for HWB. This adds further value to the idea that teacher educators should work more closely with those delivering sports-related undergraduate degree courses to support the development of subject knowledge for those students who wish to progress to the PGDE route (Gower and Capel, 2004).

Though participants in the study shared Monica's view on the importance of subject-specific classes, they also highlighted that their ITE did not cover 'enough' subject knowledge, both of which indicate that subject-specific classes were a vital factor affecting the perceptions of preparedness in graduates during their ITE. Being underprepared for certificated classes was mentioned often by participants and some attributed this to their experiences:

I would have to agree with Keith. When I was in placement I didn't get as much opportunity to take certificated classes as some other people did. So, in that sense, I am probably less prepared than those people and would need help and the other thing is, I was given classes that didn't even run in the school during my previous placement

(Phoebe, 2016).

Here experiences, or a lack of particular experiences, was linked to preparedness; indeed, because the above participant does not feel prepared for taking a certificated PE class, she does not feel fully prepared. However, it is not necessarily the case that graduates from ITE need to feel fully prepared in all areas as it has been highlighted that teachers are shaped by ITE at the beginning and then refined through the teaching career (Keating et al., 2017). Certificated classes were covered in the participants' ITE programme but given the indication that the participants felt more time on these activities would help them to feel more prepared, it would be worth considering how this could be achieved in the relatively short span of the PGDE. Indeed, it might be that the short nature of the PGDE course could be the cause of these feelings or perhaps the participants do not see ITE as the first step on a career-long journey where they indeed will get 'more time' to develop within these areas. A thorough understanding of content is important for teachers to be effective (Berliner, 2004) which could explain why subject knowledge was valued by the participants, especially as 'teachers cannot help children learn things that they themselves do not understand' (Ball, 1991, p.5).

Despite a belief that PE has moved away from the traditional subject knowledge base (Siedentop, 2002) the value placed on this by the participants in the present study could suggest that this is not the case. However, subject knowledge is not necessarily an indicator of pedagogic ability (Slater et al., 2012) and educating teachers on pedagogy that reflects 'state of the art principles' as well as 'incorporating new knowledge' and evolving the teachers' 'knowledge base for teaching' are believed by some to be what ITE should be focusing on (Podgorsky and Ballou, 2000). So, it is possible that of more importance is that graduates of PE teacher education can adapt content to suit the diverse needs of the students in their classes (Ayvazo and Ward, 2011). Either way, it has been shown that

teachers' behaviour is crucial to developing HWB in school (Aira et al., 2014), and thus continued consideration of how teachers are prepared is vital, particularly given that the range and complexity of competencies required for teaching in the 21st century are so great that any one individual is unlikely to have them all (European Commission, 2013).

In evaluating the effectiveness of PSTs, schools often comment on the level of content knowledge that participants have or do not have and, whilst knowledge of the activities taught within PE is viewed as important being able to teach is considered equally important (Capel and Blair, 2007). So, the ability to deliver that content knowledge with appropriate pedagogy and having the skill set to access, understand, and apply content to teaching should be a focus for ITE. Especially as new activities are always popping up in line with trends, e.g., Zumba or parkour, and so PSTs cannot know all the activities, but this seems, for many of the participants, to be very closely linked to perceived preparation, and this warrants further investigation. Equally though, for some participants, the importance of the subject 'stuff' is about the teaching of the content, and so in this way perhaps the focus should be on pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) which refers to a teacher's ability to combine content knowledge with knowledge of pedagogy in a way that fosters and supports pupils' learning (Capel and Whitehead, 2013). In that way, both the content knowledge and the teaching of that content play a vital role in what some describe as one of the most critical components of teaching expertise (Lund et al., 2008). This may go some way in helping understand the weight placed on content knowledge by the participants within this study. However, it is noted that progress towards expertise in PCK requires extensive teaching experience over many years (Ward and Sullivan, 1998), and so it might never be possible to achieve this and subsequently improve feelings of preparedness in ITE.

Ready to Teach or Just Ready to Move on?

Throughout all data collection cycles, many participants frequently utilised the terms 'prepared' and 'ready' interchangeably. It was not always possible to distinguish whether participants viewed these terms as having identical meanings. However, looking at the context in which they used them, it is possible to discern that, for some participants, 'prepared' or 'ready' meant ready to move on to the next stage, their probationary year:

I was prepared when I left uni. I felt ready, I was happy with my teaching style and ability but I didn't know my school or my pupils, so looking back, I wasn't ready, fully ready, for what my school did. I guess I would never really be ready until I was in it doing it.

(Calvin, 2015).

In this response, the participant utilised 'prepared' once and then 'ready' four times when asked to think back and reflect on their feelings of preparedness. This participant admitted to feeling prepared after having completed the ITE, and because of being 'happy' with their effectiveness as a teacher, they felt ready. This aligns with work that equates such a concept to readiness for the job as well as with other work which has stated that readiness is related to competence (Winterton et al., 2006) though caution is advised as there can be a difference between perceived and attained readiness (Mohamad et al., 2016).

The choice of the word 'prepared' in the study is important, as it implies more than just being 'ready'; indeed, had the word 'ready' been used, there would be the potential for it to have multiple meanings. For some, it could just have been that they were ready to leave university and get on with the 'real' teaching. However, ITE is 'preparing' them for their career, and is linked to terms such as instruct, teach, and educate. This alludes that you can never be fully prepared for practice, even a veteran teacher may experience new things daily that they had not been prepared for, but they are ready for practice (Darling-Hammond, 2012). However, despite the deliberate choice of word for the study for some participants, preparedness is equated to being ready to move on to the next stage of their development within their career. However, this does not necessarily mean that the participants were not prepared, just that, for them, it was noted that they had an overwhelming feeling of being ready to move on. It is possible, however, that part of being ready meant they were prepared in the sense of being equipped and confident in their abilities. This suggests that only by moving to the next stage, namely their probationary year, could they become more prepared.

During the focus group, Helen (2017) indicated that

I definitely feel prepared, but I still have the kind of nerves because there is stuff that is unknown. This is the next stage in your career and you have never been there before and you don't know what's expected of you but again it's exciting and I feel I'm ready.

Despite the unknown element the participant expressed a readiness to move on to the next stage of their career as an indication of preparedness which contrasts with other work, which highlighted that many student teachers reported feeling underprepared for the real-world classroom (Stahl et al., 2016). Feelings of preparedness were impacted by uncertainties, and this was echoed by other participants:

I have not yet done the job therefore I don't completely know what's ahead of me however, I agree that this course has prepared me the best it can without being in the role full time.

(Kevin, 2016).

So, their feelings of preparedness are impacted by elements which participants viewed as being 'unknown' and that exist when they graduate or progress into the early phase of their career. They may know where they are going for their probationary year or they may not; either way, they do not know their pupils or what they will be teaching. This is where knowing the context in which you are going to be teaching becomes important as effective teaching depends on 'knowing your children well and having relationships with them' (Berliner, 2004, p.202). It could be, then, that TEIs and local authorities should work, in as timely a manner as possible, to provide information on the school context to support teachers in feeling prepared.

However, these 'unknowns' are out with the control of TEIs and does not necessarily mean that ITE has not prepared the students to undertake their probationary year. As views of preparedness were unpicked during the focus group the participants were able to reflect that they did have some feelings of preparedness to undertake their probationary year, but these

were overpowered by the fear of the unknown. Perhaps, then, for teacher educators, one of the goals should be to build resilience in students and skills that can support them to cope with the professed impact of the unknowns during the early stages of their journey as a teacher. This was discussed during the focus groups as Monica (2016):

I think I'm feeling prepared about starting probation. Quite possibly because of the network I've built as well so I'm like no matter what I go into, I can get in touch with anybody on the course that has specialities or get in touch with the years above because of the mentoring programme and things like that, so even the schools that I've been in on placements (...) I know I can get in touch with these departments and they will be more than happy to help so networking has definitely been something that has helped me be prepared from probation.

A variable that was not explored in this study should also be acknowledged, namely the extent to which each participant is optimistic or confident about life and themselves normally. It is possible that this might influence how participants perceive their levels of preparedness throughout ITE and beyond. There is also the opportunity to explore connections with academic optimism – an individual teacher's beliefs that they can teach effectively, their students can learn, and that they will be supported by parents (Beard et al., 2010). Potentially, though even with additional consideration participants might still be hesitant to say that they are prepared as education is complex, unique, and full of unknown elements (Schön, 1983). Consideration should be given as to whether competence and the ability to reflect, impacted the participants' ability to explain their feelings of preparedness. The ability to say that they are ready does not necessarily mean that the participants are prepared. It may be that participants were using the term 'ready' as they were not fully able to reflect and articulate their understanding of preparedness. However, since all the participants successfully passed the course, they were of satisfactory competence. Despite that, it is possible that competence then impacted the ability of participants to answer questions.

Being prepared appears to be hinged on things that the participants do not yet know, which can sometimes be difficult, although the experiences gained during a probationary year have the potential to help with that. Helen (2017) recognised during her reflective interview:

that's always a challenge, of knowing. Like, how to act out certain things in lessons. But it has gotten easier, I think. Having a good relationship with Guidance, and being involved in, like, PSE, like, you learn a lot on probation, so it gets easier.

The previous accounts provided by the participants may highlight the possibility that they were never going to feel fully prepared due to certain things which are out of their control, and this meant they were reluctant to say they were fully prepared. However, we see that, despite this, they were ready for the next stage of development, and whilst challenging, some steps could be taken to make things easier. It could be that ITE does not need to produce participants who feel fully prepared to undertake their probationary year, it is enough for them to have sufficient preparedness to feel ready to move on to the next step in their lifelong learning journey.

Placement – Where Students believe the ‘Real’ Learning Happens

For almost all participants, time spent on placement appeared to influence their feelings of preparation a great deal; for some it was the most significant factor that contributed to their feelings of preparation.

Derrick's (2017) account captures the views that were often shared by participants throughout the study – ‘Teaching practice I have experienced on placement and at university equals being prepared’. Derrick's account offers some insight into why that might be the case; for him it was about the opportunity to practise teaching both on placement and on campus, which helped him to feel prepared. This was also shared by Conrad (2015), who indicated that ‘teaching activities, where we were brought in to teach our peers’ impacted his preparedness. Thus, there appears to be a close link between the ability to practise teaching, either on campus or on placement, and perceived preparedness. This gives an indication of

the significance of placement in supporting participants to feel prepared which is common for PSTs to place such value on opportunities to be positioned in the teacher role (Ní Chróinín et al., 2018).

During a focus group discussion regarding why the placement was a standout experience, Steve (2015) shared that it was 'just the relationships that you build with the pupils and staff that was the reason why placement played a significant role in increasing his feelings of preparedness. Murray (2015) offered a slightly different reason - '[to] actually go out and try and put that theory into practice. It's a whole other ball game. It's so fast and furious when you go into classes'. Whilst they offered different insights, both suggest that university learning on its own would not be sufficient for them to feel prepared to teach; they had to be able to put the theory into practice for themselves. It is in these comments that we begin to uncover the particular significance of placement experiences for some of the participants in the study; the ability to apply campus-based learning – 'the theory' – to their school-based practice. This supports the work of Brookfield (1995), who declared that 'theory' can help us develop our practice by providing perspective and highlighting influences on the situations we experience in the classroom. Brookfield (1995) also stated that the 'Theory-practice dichotomy is nonsense' (p.185) and that, as teachers, 'we are all theorists, and we are all practitioners' (p.185). This suggests that university-based learning, in part, is seen as significant if it can be applied to practice on placement. This is particularly important for PE teachers who are negotiating their understanding of PE and its relationship to HWB which are often developed through an 'apprenticeship of observation' (Lortie, 1975).

A significant view was offered by Claire (2017) which indicated why the placement was so important to feelings of preparedness – 'The time on placement is where the real learning occurs' and that placements were seen as 'standout experiences' that allowed for the 'real learning' to happen (Murray, 2015). It could be concluded that, without their placement experiences, these participants would not have felt prepared, and this is part of the reason placement experiences feature heavily in most forms of teacher education worldwide, and all teacher education in Scotland. Another focus group presented some interesting views on placement and the experiences that they had which made it significant for them. Phoebe (2016) reflected that:

I think the thing that stood out for me most was just placements, like I think you always knew how hard placements were going to be, but you can't really explain what they are like, until you are actually on placement. I think it's like when you're on placement is such a steep learning curve. If I think back to the first placement and the last placement the difference in the way I was...

This highlights that, whilst influential placement can be difficult and gives some insight into the differences between the beginning of placement experiences and the end, which can have a significant effect on perceptions (Busher et al., 2015, p.399). This is echoed by her peer, Chandler, who also shared that, for him, it was only in undertaking placement that you begin to understand how prepared you actually are:

I think, going to back to what everyone has said, placements are huge. It's all fine and dandy someone saying to you, this is how it would look in the classroom, and this is how it should go, this is how you should deal with this but until you're actually out there and can actually deal with it, then you're not really as prepared as you could be. Until something actually happens you don't actually know how you're going to react and how the class is going to react to a behaviour issue or the way you're delivering something. So, I think being on placement is probably one of the reasons why I'm so ready; if you look at the first day on placement compared to the last day on placement, every single one of us has improved massively, because of being on placement and learning stuff like that...

Chandler's account also highlights the importance of gaining experience in the practicalities of teaching in school, which is one of the key elements of any placement experience and, as such, beliefs and practices can be shaped and developed during teacher education (Busher et al., 2015). These accounts gave some insight into the differences between the beginning of placement experiences and the end, which can have a significant effect on perceptions (Busher et al., 2015, p.399). These accounts show some consistencies with Dewey's (1998) theory of experience and the work of Schmidt (2010), as the participants undertook, and reflected on, their teaching experiences; they formulated their own meanings and made

connections to their learning. This is influenced by the participants being able to reflect on, and recognise, the progress they had made across placements and realise that this, in part, helped them to feel prepared for what might come. It could be that participants who are not able to reflect in this way might not be able to recognise the progress they have made, and subsequently this might lead to a lower perception of their preparedness.

Participants described their preparedness as being positive and self-assured in their ability to effectively undertake their responsibilities as teachers. However, frequent mentions of 'more time on placement' or 'more time in schools' were seen when participants were asked about how their feelings of preparedness could have been increased. However, there was no suggestion from participants that extra time on placement could replace any of the activities during their ITE though the participant views do align with work which indicates that the majority of beginning teachers value the school-based elements of their education over the traditionally taught course (Hobson et al., 2006). Most of the participants believed that additional time on placement would support them in feeling more prepared, which could lead to a recommendation that more time on placement within ITE is necessary. However, caution must be exercised when thinking about proposing that exposure to education theory should be reduced within ITE in favour of more practical experience in schools; indeed, this is misleading and perhaps misguided, as theory is explicitly linked to how teachers explain developments and resolve issues in their practice (Brookfield, 1995). Indeed, suggesting that you do not need theory to become a teacher could be considered a theory itself. Making connections and establishing a balance between university learning and placement learning is viewed as one of the key challenges for ITE (Boyd, 2014) as often a 'gap' is observed (Busher et al., 2015). As such, this study recommends that ITE programmes and teacher educators consider how to make these links explicit and support the implicit use of theory to inform practice and vice versa.

Other participants spoke of the short nature of placement and how that meant one could perhaps never be fully prepared:

I feel that you couldn't ever be fully prepared; (...) because it is such a short time, as Chandler said, certain things will creep up. There's probably teachers who have been

teaching for five or ten years who are still learning, and they are being better prepared for situations, so (...) I just felt that we have been really, really well prepared in the time that we have had. Of course, we could be more prepared; you can always be more prepared but in the time that we have had (...) it is a really good effort

(Carlos, 2016).

This reflection highlights that teaching is a lifelong learning journey, and even situations that you may have faced previously might still not go as planned. It could also be that placement experiences are more important to PGDE students due to the short nature of the course and the rapid development across the course. So while there is no expectation that ITE would prepare graduates for everything they might face in their careers; perhaps increased preparation can be found in developing a set of skills that will support graduates to adapt, reflect and learn from their experiences (Schmidt, 2010).

The Reflective Teacher

The idea of reflective practice is prevalent within the teaching profession and across teacher education (Gilles, 2016), and this is also the case for participants in this study. As the participants developed throughout their probationary period, they began to understand more of what was expected of them regarding HWB, thus leading to them reflecting on the experiences they had in ITE and how different experiences in ITE could prepare them more fully.

As I Understand More, I Feel Less Prepared

In the interviews, the participants were provided with information from the analysis of the focus groups, which indicated that they felt they were prepared to meet some of their responsibility for HWB. A year further along their journey as a young educator, they stated that they knew more, and reflected that perhaps more could have been done during ITE to prepare them:

I mean, [I'm] realising the skills of it all... like, I imagine it to be talking

about the mental side and the emotional side of being healthy. Not just the physical side of looking healthy. More could have been done in uni. (Jamie, 2016).

Interestingly, the participants did not specifically discuss the definition of HWB in terms of an academic definition; they often spoke of the impact that HWB had on their practice. In his interview Derrick (2017) was not able to fully articulate his understanding of HWB, but was able to provide relevant examples from his own practice and the work of the school that promoted and developed HWB:

I mean, I am not really sure, but we do breakfast clubs and health week; is that health and wellbeing?

It is here we begin to see that as participants were more aware of what they did not know, and they were more hesitant to say they were prepared. Thus, in that sense, for the participants aligned with the view that HWB was malleable and context specific (Weare, 2010). Perhaps it could also be claimed that some of the understanding that the participants need to fulfil their HWB responsibility could (and potentially should) only be developed in the school context during their probationary experiences, as HWB within the CfE is intended to be moulded to suit the community, school, and pupils (Education Scotland, 2015). This is particularly important given that HWB is much wider than a health-based PE curriculum (Brolin et al., 2018). Though PE contributes to this both explicitly and implicitly (Chong et al., 2018) participants across data collection cycles focussed on the explicit ways that they taught HWB, few participants were able to articulate implicit aspects of their practice such as having a good relationship or a good ethos in the classroom or building confidence in their pupils as part of developing all aspects of health (Teraoka and Kirk, 2021). It is perhaps that participants are not always aware of, or able to reflect on, the implicit ways in which they are contributing to HWB.

For others, the enactment of reflective practice was in the words they used in their responses: 'in terms of health and wellbeing, it's definitely an area I want to explore more and find ways to make more links' (Monica, 2016). This desire to continue to reflect and

remain open to the potential of enhanced performance as part of a professional commitment to the continual development of practice has been noted as one of the distinctive features of teaching as a profession (Kirk, 2000). Thus, it could be argued that, for the participants, the enactment of their reflective practice (and the factors they linked to their reflection) was implemented so that they could continue their development as practitioners. Others were able to reflect on their feelings of preparedness both generally 'more could have been done on the ITE course to help with feelings of preparedness' (Brendon, 2017) and specifically in relation to things that would have increased preparedness:

... we would have benefitted from a vote of confidence from our tutors prior to assignments and crits [tutor visits].

(Conrad, 2015).

This suggests that passing elements of the course had an impact on participants feeling confident and prepared. Assisting student teachers in becoming confident has been one of the key challenges facing teacher educators (Stahl et al., 2016). It is then credible to link confidence to feelings of preparedness with the potential for this to have a positive or negative impact on the participants' feelings of confidence and subsequently preparedness. Though the definition of what the participants meant by confidence was not discussed, the participant accounts could suggest that confidence is linked to preparedness and that considering yourself to be confident means that you are prepared. Indeed, preparedness is of key importance for an effective teacher, leading to confidence or teacher efficacy in their ability to promote student learning (Hoy, 2000). However, this may be misplaced by the participants, as confidence does not necessarily mean that one is competent or prepared. The opposite could also be true, that a participant who feels prepared may not be confident or competent. As such, it is not surprising that participants referred to confidence when discussing their feelings of preparedness, as they require a certain degree of confidence to be able to adapt their practice (Stahl et al., 2016). So, whilst the participants may not have used the term 'teacher efficacy', they expressed views about confidence and self-belief because of ITE when asked about their feelings of preparedness. It could be, then, that self-belief and confidence in their competence can positively influence participants' feelings of preparedness.

All of this highlights an intriguing concept that began to emerge during the interviews that as the participants began to understand more about HWB, they consequently began to feel less prepared. This included looking back at how prepared they felt they were when they graduated and indicated that perhaps they had not been as prepared as they thought they were. It should be noted that no participants stated that they felt unprepared – just that they were not as prepared as they had thought they were. In Figure 6, a representation of this relationship is shown.

Figure 3: View of HWB/Feelings Preparation

As can be seen, the more the participants' view of HWB developed, and the broader it became, the less prepared the respondents felt about it all. The timescale in which this happened seemed to differ for participants, and so the relationship stopped short of being an identifiable trend in the views of the participants. Nonetheless, there appears to be a relationship between the participants' understanding of HWB and their feelings of preparedness.

Value and Relevance

Preparedness, for some of the participants, also seemed to be linked to the value attached to particular activities within the course. As we have seen earlier in this chapter, high value was attached to subject-specific activities, and this positively increased the participants' feelings

of preparedness. Where it was viewed that there was no relevance, or a lack of relevance, to activities, this was linked to having little value to their preparedness. Often this was combined with ways in which activities could be modified to support an increase in the participants' feelings of preparedness.

The most noteworthy activities that invoked negative responses in the discussion regarding the impact of the ITE course on perceived preparedness were encompassed in what the participants described as 'the Thursday classes' – a term which refers to the School and Professional Studies module in the PGDE programme content (Appendix 17). Some participants expressed dissatisfaction with aspects that were studied within this module and indicated that they had the least impact on their feelings of preparedness. For Conrad (2015), this was because 'Some lectures were very boring and the delivery of them did not match the delivery we would be expected to do in schools'. This highlights that preparedness is not only related to the value which the participants place on topics, but also to the perceived quality of the delivery which is important as students learn to teach both through what is taught and how it is taught (Philpot and Smith, 2018). This suggests that consideration needs to be given to the delivery of the content, particularly as teacher educators are 'teaching teaching' and what student teachers learn during their ITE is influenced as much by who is responsible for teaching them as it is by the content (Murray and Kosnick, 2011). Rowan et al. (2015) highlighted that close consideration should be given to teacher educators and the work they do, with a particular focus on ensuring that they are in touch with the education practices in contemporary schools.

It could be that, as is common with early-phase teachers, the participants became confused about what is important and, as a result, they found that much of their initial learning was not directly useful when on teaching placement (Ure, 2010). Alternatively, it could be that these views of the participants are a manifestation of a common issue associated with ITE – that one of the weaknesses within teacher education is that if teacher educators continue to advocate innovative practices that they do not model or illustrate, then improvements in teacher education and the preparedness of the graduates will continue to not materialise (Tryggvason, 2009). Equally though, it could also be that the perception of lack of relevance is due to the participants not reflecting on the content and applying it to their practice. There is

the possibility, then, that taking the time to encourage students to apply any 'generic' content to their practice could offset this and reduce any potential confusion. Darling-Hammond and Bransford (2005) suggested that negative attitudes about the university could be avoided if teacher educators prioritise what it is that the PSTs need to know. However, there is the possibility that what teacher educators view as being 'need to know' might not align with the views of the participants in terms of what they feel might have increased their preparedness for their career. So, whilst the findings of this study indicate that ITE has a perceived impact on the level of preparedness within graduates, those responsible for the design of such programmes may benefit from reviewing content. The current research study also contends that the role and position of TEIs, in developing levels of preparedness, has not been sufficiently examined within the wider research field.

It is equally possible that it requires consideration of how the value and relevance of inputs are communicated to students participating in these inputs as part of their ITE as Phoebe (2016) reflected that:

I think another thing I was thinking of about the Thursday class is I think it's partly because it was with primary as well, so a lot of the time when they were answering a way you could use it, like controversial issues, topics in the class were primary examples, obviously the secondary students couldn't really use it, so I think the Thursday class maybe worked better for the primary.

This participant accounts highlight the potential need to communicate examples or activities that encourage and support PSTs to apply their learning and see the relevance of the topics being discussed within the class. Part of being a student teacher is applying learning from university classes to practice and this may support better understanding of the relevance of learning activities. Teacher educators and those responsible for the planning of content within ITE should consider whether this might be useful for their specific context. It is also entirely possible that this content did have some impact, just not as much as others, because different students will make different sense of their experiences and thus could be viewed as more or less impactful (Tinning, 2002). This, of course, is just the view of one group of

participants who engaged with the module; other secondary and primary students also experienced it. Gaining a broader view from other students who experienced this module may shed light on whether these views were specific to PE students or were also felt by other students who participated in the module.

It is possible that participants did not see the value at the time of the class, but it had future value, and this is typified in the experience of Jamie (2015) who reflected that

I think the biggest difference for me was to do something with my class.

I think, looking back, all the inputs we had are highly beneficial because it allows me to do it in my class.

This view expressed in the interviews at the end of the participants' probationary year highlights that, although classes may not have had immediate relevance learning from ITE became relevant during the probationary year. Consideration ought to be given to whether all content in ITE should have immediate relevance or whether additional support might be needed for students to see the potential relevance, even if this is not for their immediate practice. There is the possibility, however, that some of these topics that were viewed as being irrelevant by participants should be reviewed to ascertain whether they are still appropriate for inclusion within ITE or perhaps may be better placed in the career-long learning journey of teachers.

It is possible that the content referred to as 'irrelevant' by participants is actually an indication of another key concern expressed by students when discussing their perceived preparedness, namely the perceived disparity between university and school-based practice. It is vital that teacher education is 'in alignment with the new demands that are placed on schools' (Kirk, 2000, p.17) and reviewing the value of topics and classes covered in any ITE programme could be useful in increasing the value or relevance to the students within the programme. Trying to do this is complex work and demands a great deal from teacher educators, particularly that they have a well-developed understanding of the practice associated with teaching (Loughran and Russell, 2007). It is therefore possible that, in having this understanding, teacher educators can make decisions about the content of ITE

programmes that will prepare PSTs for entering the profession and that, as PSTs, the participants do not necessarily have the same level of understanding and so may not always see the value of all the classes. This could also require reflection on whether these parts of the ITE course are indeed valuable to the development of the graduates' preparation.

Context and Feelings of Preparedness

For some of the participants across all data collection cycles, context played a significant role in their feelings of preparedness. For participants, entering their probationary year with limited knowledge of the context in which they were going to be working meant that they did not feel fully prepared. Similarly, for participants at the end of their probationary year and moving into the early phase of their career, not knowing the context in which they would be teaching meant they perceived themselves as, in some way, lacking preparation. The influence of context on perceived preparedness appears to be related to some of the 'unknowns' discussed earlier, in that not knowing the context in which they are going to teach means they do not feel fully prepared and 'skilful', teaching must be contextually informed (Brookfield, 2006).

It is in this view that an indication arises that the experiences provide within a context can also influence perceived preparation in perhaps an adverse way. Pheobe (2016) reflected

When I was on placement I didn't get as much opportunity to take certificated classes as some other people did. So, in that sense, I am probably less prepared than those people and would need help and the other thing is, I was given classes that didn't even run in the school during the previous placement.

This indicate that a perceived lack of knowledge around certificated classes had a negative impact on their feelings of preparedness. Given the significant focus on mental, emotional, social, and physical factors throughout these courses (SQA, n.d) this could indicate that in that context students were not fully prepared to meet their responsibility for HWB. At the time that Phoebe made her observation she was aware of her school and what she would be expected to teach in her probationary year; she reflected that she had been asked to teach a

class that she did not have experience of, as her placement school had not offered this class. Her peer Jonas added:

I'm also the same as Phoebe and I'm taking sport and rec class that I've never been prepared for; I'm taking some other classes that I have not been prepared for either, so certificated classes are something that I maybe wish there was more emphasis on.

Jonas is referring to Sport and Recreation, which is an SQA-accredited course that falls into The Skills for Work course category. Sport and Recreation covers the main practical activities involved in carrying out a support role in a sports and recreation environment, as well as health and safety legislation (SQA, n.d). It is not a required part of the curriculum, and so schools can choose whether they offer this course, which means that some of the participants may have experienced this on placement whilst others may not have. The ITE content does include some classes on alternative curricular courses such as this, but it does not delve into each potential course; it looks broadly at several examples of alternatives that exist across Scotland. This reinforces that, whilst experiences have a positive impact on perceived preparedness, not having particular experiences due to the context also appears to contribute to some participants feeling less prepared and, in some cases, less prepared than their peers, because they had different experiences. It is almost impossible for TEIs to ensure the same experiences for student teachers or to prepare them for all the courses that schools might offer. TEIs could explore ways in which student teachers could be supported in understanding the reasons why different experiences might happen and increase the number of ways in which experiences are shared amongst peers.

Participants see context as vital, perhaps because knowledge is situated and 'made powerful by the contexts in which it is acquired and used' (Shulman, 1988, p.37). This is an area where enhanced partnership that involves the sharing and interrogating of observed good practice might improve perceived preparedness. It is therefore important that ITE make teaching a site for enquiry to support student teachers in obtaining insight into their practice in such a way as to gain a genuine appreciation for the skills, knowledge and abilities that shape practice (Loughran and Russell, 2007). Consideration should also be given to the different

contexts that teachers might find themselves teaching in as ITE should prepare graduates to teach in any school across the country. Equally though, attention should be given to how we can prepare graduates of ITE for specific situations that have been identified as having a particular impact on perceived preparedness. In a postgraduate course, such as the one in this study, the balance between what gets covered and in how much depth is recognised as a struggle for all universities (Grossman et al., 2009). It is also possible that the necessary experience comes from the probationary year and beyond. Nonetheless, the question is still raised as to whether the time spent on certificated classes or alternative courses offered as part of PE should indeed be increased in ITE. Given that this was mentioned in several questions and appeared frequently across the data collection cycles, it could be recommended that this ITE course ought to spend more time on this to support feelings of preparedness in the participants. However, it could also be possible that the context in which the teachers are teaching dictates whether this experience is necessary and indeed that experience could be gained at other points in their career-long learning journey.

Experience(s) Shapes Perceived Preparation

Earlier it was highlighted additional time on particular activities might have supported the participants to feel more prepared even though they had considered themselves to be prepared to enter their probationary year. Despite expressing this view, some of the participants felt unprepared to deal with the practical realities of teaching and some interesting insight was shown when they noted that it might be impossible for them to have been prepared, via their ITE course, for everything that they could encounter in their probationary year.

In the reflective interviews, participants declared that teaching experience in their probationary year had supported their feelings of preparedness. Participants indicated that their probationary year was a significant learning period for them, stating that they were 'prepared enough when I left uni but that is not to say I learned more in the first few weeks of the year than in 36 weeks of ITE' (Jamie, 2015). This in part aligns with the view that ITE is seen as least influential in teacher's professional socialisation and that organisational socialisation within a particular school setting is more impactful (Lawson, 1986). Since the

participant indicated that he learned more in the first few weeks of his probationary year than he did on his ITE course this could be considered a concerning viewpoint as this might question the impact of ITE (McCulloch, 2012). It is also possible that experience changes participants' perception of preparedness which is seen in Jessica's (2015) reflection:

I felt 100% ready for my probationary year but having been through the year I'd say it was more like 40%, now at the end I'm 60%; I'm not sure I'll ever get to 100% but I definitely took my uni stuff and built on it during the year.

Jessica's account shows that as she began to know more, she was able to articulate that she had not been as prepared as she had thought earlier in the data collection cycle. In one study, almost half of the probationary teachers surveyed did not feel prepared to start their probationary year (McCulloch, 2012). However, this study was undertaken with probationary teachers from the primary sector and across all secondary subjects, which makes it difficult to make a direct comparison here. However, some participants in this study, did express that they never felt unprepared but that it was difficult to know in advance how prepared they were:

You never really know until you start and obviously, Day one Lesson one is always a bit mental ... you can just constantly put things and adapt things for your own teaching, so you didn't know how prepared you were, but I didn't feel unprepared at any point, and I think that you guys got us into really good habits in terms of how a really, really good lesson should look. Obviously, the reality in a massive school is that not every single lesson will look like that; I'm not going to lie, but you knew what it should look like, so you knew in the back of your mind, this should be happening, and I need to try to get this done; we need to try to get to this destination. We might have to cut a wee bit out here and there in order to get there, but you knew how you should be doing it.

(Ross, 2016).

For Ross, his experiences shaped his understanding of what a 'good' lesson was, and he reflected against that as part of his practice and how prepared he was because of these experiences. This is particularly important as simply having experience does not necessarily mean that learning will happen, and so student teachers may need support to help them develop the ability to critically analyse experience (Brookfield, 1995). In this way, everything may be just an experience until you reflect on it; only then does it become learning (Kolb, 1984). Making sense of experiences in this way indicates that 'learning is the process whereby knowledge is created through the transformation of experience' (Kolb, 1984, p.38). Similarly, developing knowledge about practice by learning from one's own experiences of practice has been highlighted as particularly important to young educators (Loughran and Russell, 2007). As such, given the value placed on experiences by the participants, teacher educators should work to support students in making sense of these experiences and learn from them.

As a result, it could be concluded that both experience and specific experiences influence the feelings of preparedness for participants in this study. Learning within the teaching profession is a recursive and non-linear process (Keay et al., 2018), and thus it is perhaps because of this process that participants value their experiences so highly, since it is part of the process of learning and developing their practice. Teachers therefore should be supported in developing their knowledge, skills, and relationships through a range of experiences that both challenge and support their development (Keay et al., 2018). For the only 'significant method, is the method of the mind as it reaches out and assimilates' (Dewey, 1938, p.9). Alongside this, it has been posited that ITE has the potential to produce graduates who enter the profession as engaged 'policy actors', and this, in turn, has the potential to invoke educational change (Keay et al., 2018). Thus, whilst participants are shaped by their experiences as part of the ITE, participants may also need to be supported and encouraged to create new experiences themselves. This brings us back to the theme earlier, that participants are prepared but not prepared for everything. This aligns with the view that the provision of teacher education in Scotland is strong but that there is no indication of complete satisfaction with the system (Humes, 2013), indicating that even when provision is strong or rated highly by participants and there is evidence of reflective practice within the participants there is always room for improvement. Indeed, the reality of being a teacher; the

constant reflection and evaluation to strive to improve practice may mean that one might never feel fully prepared. This could in turn suggest, however, that there is a need to help student teachers deal with the uncertainty that comes with contemporary education (Dunne, 2008) and that ITE exposes student teachers to a wide range of relevant practices to support greater reflection and improved practice (Gillies, 2016).

Alternative Viewpoints

So far in this chapter participants accounts have presented a picture of effective and reflective early-phase practitioners. Though these stages that young professionals travel through in their career development may not be as categorical as set out in the literature review by Menter et al. (2010). Indeed, this study highlights that participants' perception of preparedness shifts, sometimes back and forth, through a series of perspectives that depend on a variety of factors, like experience. Overall, in alignment with the work of Menter et al. (2010) there are indications of effective and reflective teaching within the views of the participants. However, the study also contends that teachers do not neatly fit into a category and that their feelings of preparedness are messier and more nuanced than that. Indeed, this study asserts that, as the participants developed, their perspectives not only shifted but overlapped in some cases. The analysis presented other perceptions that were held by participants of this study:

- The Narrow Viewpoint – 'PE and HWB, it's just what we do'.
- The Hesitant Viewpoint – 'I'm ready but I'm not sure I'll ever be fully prepared'.

These have important potential implications which will be discussed in the concluding chapter but first each of the viewpoints will be discussed.

The Narrow Viewpoint

As was presented earlier, participants agreed that they were prepared for their probationary year overall. However, variation was observed in levels of perceived preparedness to meet their responsibility for HWB when reflecting on their experiences. Given this, it could be

concluded that graduates are prepared for some aspects of HWB, but not all. The defining characteristic of this self-perception is a narrow, perhaps naive, and straightforward view of HWB in contemporary Scottish PE.

Initially, during analysis, this viewpoint seemed to be more aligned with a naive viewpoint – one where the participants, perhaps due to their inexperience or lack of understanding, viewed HWB as being covered just because the participants considered themselves to be effective PE teachers that focussed on the ‘physical’. However, on further analysis of the feelings of preparedness expressed by participants and in discussion with a critical friend, it became apparent that their viewpoints were more to do with ‘innocence’ and perhaps their career stage. Their expressed viewpoint aligns in part with the healthism view of PE, which is a ‘discourse relating primarily to fitness and physical wellbeing is influencing the way the PE curriculum is both interpreted and delivered’ (Gray et al., 2015, p.165), and is often held by early-stage practitioners. That is, PE teachers developing physical health through fitness is part of their job and thus being prepared to be a PE teacher means being prepared to promote HWB. However, PE within the context of HWB can contribute considerably more than ‘physical activity for the sake of physical health’ (Gray et al., 2015, p.168), so it would be relevant to consider if participants developed a more holistic view of PE within HWB as they become more experienced, this is presented in other viewpoints later.

When asked about their feelings of preparedness to deliver HWB, the participants who identified with this self-perception frequently shared views akin to that offered by Stuart (2015):

I think we, as PE professionals, do this without thinking.

Stuart, who was a Sport and Physical Activity undergraduate, shared this as he was graduating from his PGDE. It puts forward the notion that HWB and PE are viewed as being synonymous for some participants. This viewpoint was the dominant one amongst the participants at graduation and did not seem to be influenced by the undergraduate route that participants had taken with participants from other routes such as Sports Coaching and Sport and Exercise Science sharing the view of Stuart - that HWB is inherently part of what

they do and that as PE teachers they are meeting their responsibility for HWB almost without trying. This viewpoint was common across the data collection cycles, with participants in other graduating classes articulating similar views. This viewpoint has some commonalities with a healthism view of PE and is often seen in early-career teachers of PE (Green, 2004) so it is not unusual to see this given the participants' career stage. It has also been shared that understanding and acknowledging teachers' perspectives have become increasingly important (Alfrey and Gard, 2014), with reference to developing health discourse in the teaching of PE. Thus, listening to the viewpoints of the participants, who are recent PE graduates, may shed some light on how HWB within the context of PE can be developed. However, it is important to note that, for some of the participants, this viewpoint was not just about what they do, but also about what they were expected to do as a PE teacher:

As with PE being mainly responsible for delivering HWB within schools, I feel that what I learned in university and during school experience ensured that I am able to do this.

(Kerry, 2017).

Kerry like many of her peers was a Sports Coaching undergraduate who would not have spent significant time in her undergraduate course considering HWB. Kerry is clear that she believes PE teachers are mainly responsible for delivering HWB in schools which aligns with the work of (Gray and Mitchell, 2015) and indicates that her feelings about being able to do this have been influenced by her university and school experiences. This brings into consideration whether this view had been affected by socialisation as is often the case where viewpoints are observed in practice on placement (Mays-Woods et al., 2017). Given the high value attached to placement by the participants, understandably participants would want to adopt practices observed on placement. However, it has also been noted that, for PE teachers, ITE is a 'milestone' in developing their identity as a teacher, but it is difficult to fully understand the quality and impact of ITE programmes (Keating et al., 2017, p.166). If socialisation has occurred in school and result in this viewpoint, this could potentially bring into question the enactment of the responsibility of all policy in practice. It does serve to highlight that in this viewpoint participants saw themselves as being responsible for the leadership of HWB and that it was is part and parcel of being a PE teacher (Gray and Mitchell, 2015). On the one

hand, this viewpoint PE offers a positive perspective that embraces HWB as part of the post-CfE role of a PE teacher. On the other hand, there is the assumption by participants that because they feel they are prepared to be a PE teacher, they are unequivocally prepared to deliver their responsibility for HWB, which is not necessarily the case. To some extent, this viewpoint reinforced the theory expressed by Spratt (2017) that with reference to HWB, participants actively interpreted policy as coinciding with their own views. In this case, physical educators who professed this narrow viewpoint believed that HWB would be addressed inherently by them effectively teaching PE.

As noted earlier, this was the dominant viewpoint at the point of graduation from the PGDE, as the participants were entering their probationary year. There is some evidence emerging from this study that if participants have a narrower view of HWB, as in the case of this viewpoint, the participants perceive themselves as being prepared, because 'it is just what we do' in PE. The opposite of this is also highlighted within the study, in that the more the participants know about their responsibilities for HWB, the less prepared they feel, and this will be considered in the section on the hesitant viewpoint later in this chapter. Therefore, continued study is needed to explore the participants' understanding of practice, their responsibility within HWB, and its impact on their feelings of preparedness. It is particularly important to consider the impact that this might have on current and future practice for teachers and teacher educators working within ITE. Consideration should also be given to the role that ITE could or should play when it comes to supporting graduates in obtaining a broader view of their responsibility for HWB.

The Hesitant Viewpoint

As presented earlier participants' feelings of preparedness shape and shift as they are moulded by context and experience. One year later (after completing their probationary year), the predominant view was one where participants were able to acknowledge that there was more to their responsibility for HWB and showed an appreciation of the skills and knowledge it takes to try to meet this responsibility. In line with the categories presented by Menter et al. (2010), participants showed more evidence of being effective and reflective teachers, who were more aware of their responsibilities and as such their feelings of

preparedness had changed. Participants in this viewpoint had shifted their perspective away from the 'narrow' viewpoint to one where they were 'hesitant' to say they were prepared given what they now knew about their responsibility for HWB. So, in this sense, in developing a wider understanding of HWB they began to realise how much they did not know and which skills they had not yet developed. Indeed, this influences their ability to say they were prepared and changes their view on how prepared they thought they when they completed their ITE.

Originally, during analysis, this presented as perhaps a possible other viewpoint where participants were stating that they were 'reluctant' to progress into their probationary year; often this was related to a view that they had been told they had met the GTCS standards but that they did not perceive themselves as being prepared. However, additional analysis and discussions with a critical friend highlighted that whilst the participants shared this reluctance at the end of their ITE, there were close similarities in the feelings expressed by the participants at the end of their probationary year. Thus, despite being shared at different points in the study the common feeling shared was one of being hesitant to say that they were fully prepared. As a result, a single viewpoint was identified that was shared by many participants predominantly at the end of their probationary but also by a minority of participants at the end of their ITE.

Participants who were in this viewpoint expressed feelings of preparedness and were able to show understanding of what this meant for them moving forward; they had skills and abilities which meant they considered themselves to be effective teachers and, thus, looking back they were ready to undertake the teaching of their own classes and continue their development. However, they were also able to reflect on the views they had shared at the end of their ITE and articulate that there was no way they were ever going to be fully prepared after a short intense course such as the PGDE. This begins to show indications of the careerlong journey that educators are on and candidates were able to reflect that they did not know everything that they needed to know to be a fully developed teacher. So, they were hesitant to say that they were prepared, as they did not fully understand everything that was required or think that they had all the necessary experience or skills to feel prepared. Part of this, for many of the participants, was the knowledge required to meet

their responsibility to deliver HWB and their experiences during their probationary year had shifted their perspective.

Many of those participants who had expressed a 'narrow' viewpoint at graduation, now showed a broader understanding of HWB and this had shifted their perspective on preparedness – highlighting again that understanding of HWB influences feelings of preparedness. This shift in the participants' viewpoint was accompanied by participants reflecting that perhaps more could have been done during their ITE to support their feelings of preparedness for HWB given what the participants now understood about their role, and that of PE, in promoting HWB. This suggests that there is a need to support early-phase PE teachers in developing their understanding of HWB:

We spent next to no time exploring the outcomes' meanings
(Garry, 2015).

There is still a predominant view that HWB is the PE departments responsibility and this is linked to physical aspects of health, which is only one part of HWB and perpetuates a limited conceptualisation of health (Teraoka and Kirk, 2021). Thus 'thinking outside the physical' and exploring outcomes meanings could be significant in supporting the participants to feel prepared and help with developing the participants' understanding of HWB and consequently have the potential to offset some of the concerns shared by Gray et al. (2012) that teachers might misinterpret the role of PE within HWB. However, as noted earlier the participants' viewpoints are shaped by the context within which they are working and the experiences that they have had. As the ITE course is only one context and one experience (or collection of experiences) other school-based contexts and experiences may lead to this misinterpretation. This may potentially be the case despite any additional time spent developing an understanding of HWB in graduates during their ITE.

This hesitant viewpoint offered by the participants also shared some similarities with the first 'narrow' self-perception, in that because they felt they were prepared to undertake their role as a probationary PE teacher that they were indeed ready to meet some of their responsibility for HWB. However, given the definition of HWB, which sees it as more than just

physical (Spratt, 2014), it could be that a narrower view of HWB may lead to greater levels of perceived preparedness. This might, in part, be due to a lack of understanding when it comes to what HWB requires within the context of PE. However, crucially in this category, participants were now, at the end of their probationary year, able to distinguish that this was not enough – that HWB was so much more than ‘just what we do’ in PE:

And it wasn't just ... looking to develop skills... in terms of physical skills.
It was more about this holistic thing...

(Melanie, 2015).

Here we see an example where the school-based experiences have developed the participants’ understanding of their responsibility for HWB, along with a shift to a viewpoint that embraces a more holistic understanding of the purpose of PE within that. So, in combination with increased work on developing an understanding of HWB during ITE, this has the potential to impact perceptions of preparedness within physical educators. Whilst this hesitant viewpoint became more prevalent during the interviews at the end of the participants’ probationary year, elements of the viewpoint were also present in some participants at graduation.

A few participants within this viewpoint opined that their preparedness was impacted by classes ‘always [being] relevant to the GTCS standards and the CfE’ (Garry, 2015), which highlights that teacher educators’ work should be underpinned by the criteria of the standards as well as the curriculum. However, there was not always explicit reference to the GTCS standards, and so the participants could have been referring to those standards or to the expectations set by the course and conveyed by the teacher educators within it that made them reluctant to say they were prepared. Of course, we must acknowledge that teacher educators are supporting students in achieving the GTCS standards and that the SPR provides a framework from which ITE course programmes can be developed (Christie, 2008) thus their expectations as teacher educators should be greatly influenced by these standards.

The focus group allowed for greater exploration of what the participants meant when they referred to ‘standards’. For some, like Kelly (2017), it was the GTCS standards and ‘the

standards are probably something that I think I will refer back to', and this appears to have been connected to feelings of preparedness particularly when explicit links were made between classes and the Standards. However, it seems that, within this study the experiences of the participants during their ITE programme did not necessarily equate to feelings of perceived preparedness. The question of whether the programmes shaped by this framework can prepare PSTs for entry into the profession should be investigated further and considered on a larger scale across multiple programmes. Additionally, given that, for certain participants in this viewpoint, some value was placed on the engagement with standards in helping them feel prepared, it would be appropriate for teacher educators to continue to reflect on the ways in which they make relevant and meaningful links between on-campus work and the standards that the students are trying to achieve. This could include links and support to guide student teachers in evaluating their progress towards the standards. There may also be some benefit to supporters of probationary teachers reflecting on the inclusion of this in their practice, or at least reflecting on how they support teachers in reaching the standards.

Conclusion

The data presented no evidence of the final two categories by Menter et al. (2010) – enquiring or transformative teacher. The findings discussed in this chapter highlighted instances of effective and reflective teacher but also that other viewpoints were presented in the participants accounts of their preparedness. These highlighted that early-phase practitioners perceived themselves as being prepared for some, but not all, aspects of their responsibility for HWB. This chapter also highlighted that preparedness in some instances was equated to readiness and that factors such as placement, context, and experience(s) are seen to have an impact on the participants' feelings of preparedness. In doing so, this chapter begins to highlight the potential answers to the research questions of this study which are considered in the next chapter.

Conclusions, Implications and Contribution

Introduction

This concluding chapter explores implications by outlining the ways in which the study has contributed new knowledge and adds to the existing literature. Importantly, this chapter will make recommendations for those who have a stake in the promotion of the HWB agenda across education and in the preparation of teachers who will enact this agenda. The chapter will propose areas for future investigation that may expand the knowledge in this area. The chapter will end with a reflection on the research process.

This study aimed to utilise qualitative methods to examine the perceived preparedness of PE graduates following their ITE programme. In doing so, it aimed to identify factors that shape this perception in the early-phase practitioners in PE. Using the work of Menter et al. (2010) and Brookfield (1995), the study investigated how early-phase PE teachers felt about their preparedness as they enter a career-long journey and examined how these feelings of preparedness were constructed. The findings should be interpreted cautiously as they are based on a small-scale study of three cohorts of PSTs within a single education setting. However, this study highlights how one group of physical educators, from one teacher education setting, in one country, felt about meeting their responsibility to deliver, promote and develop the HWB of the young people in their care. The findings of the study may be applicable to other early-phase practitioners, student teachers and TEIs in Scotland. There are potential implications for other stakeholders who are involved in HWB. Beyond this, the findings may have a wider reach, as other countries follow the shift to curricular inclusion of HWB (e.g., Wales). Finally, given the global focus on health and the 'ongoing struggles' regarding the role that PE can play in promoting it (Brolin et al., 2018, p.1), this study suggests some insights that could be relevant for PE and ITE worldwide. First, this chapter will begin by outlining the contribution of the study by considering the answers to the research questions of the study, which were:

- How do practitioners view their levels of preparedness to meet their responsibility for Health and Wellbeing as:

- o a probationary teacher and;
 - o an early-phase practitioner?
- What are the reported factors that contribute to perceived levels of preparedness within physical education graduates of ITE?

Contribution

As presented in the findings and discussion, this study has uncovered new knowledge and built on the existing literature surrounding the preparation of PE teachers, with a particular focus on perceived preparation for meeting their responsibility for HWB. Whilst this study focused on one context, with a modest ambition of answering a specific question in a particular organisation, it has, nonetheless, developed new knowledge. The study has shed light on how recent graduates view and understand HWB within their role as a PE teacher. As a result of this study, more is known about the factors that appear to have an impact on perceived preparedness as well as how prepared beginning PE teachers feel to deliver HWB.

Perceived preparedness

Building on the work of Gray and Mitchell (2015), the study has shown that participants see PE and HWB as being synonymous and that this has increased and changed the responsibilities within their role as a physical educator. This impacted the perceived preparedness as participants viewed themselves as being prepared to meet their responsibility for HWB by being an effective teacher of PE. Participants also presented a narrow view of PE and its role within HWB which led to increased feelings of preparedness. Alongside this, the study has shown that a teacher's personal understanding of HWB can mould their perception of their own preparedness. It is acknowledged that HWB is a difficult term to define (Spratt, 2017), and the participants in the study concur with that view. However, it is highlighted in this study that an underdeveloped view of HWB could be linked to higher levels of perceived preparedness. This can lead to narrow aims for PE, where there is an assumption that being able to deliver lessons that develop skills will also promote physical activity, improve, and promote physical health, and meet curricular responsibilities for HWB (Gray et al., 2015). This assumption was prevalent for the PE graduates in this context but, as the understanding of HWB grows, develops, and expands, because of

experiences during their probationary year then perceived preparedness changed. This shows that, for early-phase practitioners, perceived preparedness is impacted by understanding of HWB and how it is implemented in practice.

There was an acknowledgement by many participants that, for a PE teacher setting out on what could be a career-long journey of learning, it may be some time before they feel prepared; indeed, they may never feel fully prepared. The concept of a continuum (lifelong learning) can be linked back to the argument presented by Dewey (1998), that each learning encounter must be designed to build capacity for the next. From this viewpoint, it can be argued that each stage of teacher education – or learning – should have, as one of its main purposes, to build future learning capacity. More recently, Hodkinson et al. (2008) presented learning as a holistic process of ‘becoming’ within a transitional process of boundary crossing, arguing that learning is both social and embodied. These theorists remind us that learners do not ‘come’ to a fixed endpoint and ‘learning is more fruitfully viewed as an ongoing process rather than a series of acquisition events’ (Hager and Hodkinson, 2009, p.620).

Thus, teacher education must indeed be viewed as a continuum. As some of the participants in this study indicated that meeting the standards did not necessarily result in them feeling prepared, it may be worth considering whether more explicit links might be made between the learning during ITE and into the probationary year and beyond. Being a lifelong learner and having the ability to adapt, evolve and change is a positive notion in a dynamic profession such as teaching. Conversely, this may lead to teachers striving for a ‘perfection’ which is unattainable, given that teaching is a ‘gloriously messy pursuit in which shock, contradiction and risk are endemic’ (Brookfield, 2006, p.1), thus skewing their perception of preparedness. Given the short, intense nature of the PGDE, it is therefore important to consider how the participants in this study, as well as early-phase PE teachers, can be supported in making their ‘best attempts to muddle through the complex contents and configurations that our classrooms represent’ (Brookfield, 2006, p.1) and what impact that might have on perceived preparedness.

The present study has established that the stages that young professionals travel through in their career development may be more intricate than those set out in the literature by

Menter et al. (2010) if they are to reach the desired status of 'transformational' teacher. This study indicates that teachers can perceive themselves to be both effective and reflective at the same time and that other 'narrow' or 'hesitant' viewpoints are present. These perspectives on their preparedness can shift as results of experiences and be shaped by a range of factors, discussed below.

Factors impacting perceived preparedness

The current thesis contributes to the understanding of this body of knowledge by uncovering some of the factors that have a perceived impact on preparedness amongst participants. The study demonstrates that significant factors, such as time spent on placement and experience(s) shape the perceived preparedness of participants. As participants gained 'frontline' experience, they simultaneously felt more prepared about certain aspects of their practice whilst feeling less prepared for other aspects; often this was associated with the wider aspects of HWB and was related to what participants understand HWB to be. However, it would be prudent to be cautious in advocating for 'more experience' (as many of the participants did), as 'simply having experiences does not imply that they are reflected on, understood or analysed critically' (Brookfield, 2016, p.15). Indeed, the assumption that because teachers learn from experiences that more experience is likely to be valuable, should be considered carefully given that experience is not necessarily educative and can sometimes be miseducative (Dewey, 1938). This could potentially lead teachers to reproduce what they have seen without any critical reflection (Ronfeldt and Reininger, 2012). Thus, work must be carried out to support probationary PE teachers and early-phase PE practitioners in making sense of their experiences and applying those lessons to their future practice, with particular attention being paid to those that appear to have the most impact on perceived preparedness.

Additionally, the context within which the participants were situated was a factor that also had a tangible impact on perceptions of preparedness. Mayer (2014) highlighted that employment status and type of contract had an impact on perceptions of preparedness. However, the participants in this study indicated that it was other 'unknown' elements that influenced their feelings of preparedness. Knowledge of their school context (or lack thereof)

was the most common factor that contributed to feelings of preparedness across the study. Other 'unknowns' included perceived lack of knowledge about the school environment within which they would be working and because of this study we know that this impacts perceptions of preparedness in PE teachers to meet their responsibility for HWB. Finally, as context in education is rarely constant due to it being full of 'uncertainty, complexity, uniqueness, and value conflict' (Schön, 1983, p.49), it is possible that context could have implications for perceived preparedness for HWB throughout a PE teacher's career, not just in the beginning stages, as it was for the participants in this study - this might warrant further investigation.

Building on the work of Thorburn and Gray (2009), who stated that how policy impacts practice is rarely as smooth or straightforward as anticipated, the present study shows that, for early-phase practitioners within this context, the understanding of the HWB is varied and its implementation is inconsistent, and this factor had an impact on their perceived preparedness. This reinforces the necessity of PE's ability to coexist or adapt to these policy changes to meet the challenge of promoting HWB (Horrell et al., 2012). The conclusions from this study concur with a later assertion that consideration of how fit for purpose PE is in the 21st century is necessary (Kirk et al., 2018). Indeed, we must raise the question of what the future of PE might look like as the curriculum continues to evolve. The implications for the subject and the teachers of PE are addressed later in this chapter.

Implications and Recommendations for Practice

In engaging in the study, participants were challenged to reflect on their experiences and, in doing so, shed light on how they felt about their own ITE and how prepared they were. By reflecting in this way, participants uncovered implications that may have a wider reach across ITE; these will be discussed later. The implications for others such as TELs and teacher educators as well as other stakeholders (local authorities and schools) are also considered. The next section will focus on the implications for the participants themselves, current and future student PE teachers, and early-phase PE practitioners.

Participants

Livingston (2008) highlighted that teachers should be prepared to both respond and contribute to the process of change. The recommendation from this study is that student teachers and early-phase practitioners in PE, should reflect on their ability to implement the HWB agenda within their practice, but also consider the role that they can play in driving this change. If HWB is the responsibility of all and a substantial portion of this responsibility falls on physical educators, then early-phase practitioners could advocate that this is the *responsibility of all*, not just particular individual. This could involve early-phase practitioners in PE working with colleagues across their school which could be key in developing what *responsibility of all* means in their context. As part of this, the profession must consider what boundaries to set, in terms of content, and what can be achieved in PE regarding HWB. National organisations such as the Scottish Association for Teachers of PE would be well situated to support PE teachers in working collaboratively when considering what schools do and how that matches up to the responsibility of all with regards to PE and its role in HWB. Crucially, it will be important to consider if in practice it is not the *responsibility of all*, then what indeed should it be? What impact does this have on PE as a subject? This discussion should not be confined to early-phase practitioners and a future section will identify ways in which other PE teachers could potentially play a role in that discussion.

This study offers viewpoints that the participants have of themselves and indicates that these perspectives shift based on a range of factors. The aforementioned 'shifting perspectives' could provide a framework to support student teachers and early-phase practitioners in PE to reflect on their practice. Such a model may stimulate reflection on how perspectives have changed over time and how they have evolved. These conversations could be specific to how they perceived their preparedness to deliver HWB in their practice. As the participants did in this study, the model might focus teachers' attention on how and why their perception of preparedness has shifted over a given period, starting with a prediction of preparedness, and ending with a reflection on actual preparedness. This may be particularly important where PE teachers are graduates from a PGDE programme as it has been shown that capacity to engage in reflection differs depending on the programme of study followed (Day et al., 2022). As such, this is perhaps a model that can give beginning physical educators something to

anchor reflections on and, in doing so, stimulate reflection on their perceived preparedness for HWB.

This study used the valuable 'student lens' (Brookfield, 1995) to consider the participants experiences and viewing practice this way offered insights into the impact of ITE on perceived preparedness of PE graduates to meet their responsibility for HWB. So, this study would recommend that student teachers and early-phase practitioners of PE reflect on their HWB practice through the eyes of their pupils, as is advocated by Gray et al. (2018). This could, partly, be promoted by the ITE programmes and could then have implications for both how we talk about and enact HWB, but also for how teacher educators review their practice in this area.

TEIs and Teacher Educators

The study has produced some recommendations TEIs in that it has increased understanding of PE graduates and their perceived preparedness to meet their responsibility for HWB. A recent report highlighted potential concerns as to whether programmes were dedicating enough hours to HWB to provide student teachers with adequate knowledge to support them in effectively teaching within this area (Scottish Government, 2017). This suggests that providers of ITE should consider the impact of the time dedicated to HWB and whether it is sufficient given the stage of development of the student teachers. In considering the concept of *responsibility of all*, the present study would agree with the recommendations of the Scottish Government (2017) that TEIs consider what assistance is in place to support all teachers in developing, promoting, and teaching HWB. In the first instance, such consideration should involve the use of the Self Evaluation Framework for ITE (Education Scotland, 2018). This may also include reflection on the role that TEIs could play in the continuous professional development of teachers beyond the ITE phase. It might also be part of the recent call for in-school PE teachers and teacher educators to collaborate and redesign PE to meet the demands of the 21st century (MacPhail and Lawson, 2020). This could entail the development of Master programmes in HWB, where reflection such as the kind undertaken in this study could be built into the programme to unpick the notion of HWB.

Consequently, this may support the development of a broader understanding of HWB and what it takes to teach, develop, and promote it.

It is well established that placement is significant to the preparation of teachers and, in most cases, is a required element of teacher education programmes (Hobson, 2002). In this study, the critical factor that influenced participants' feelings of preparedness for HWB was the opportunity to 'practice' being a teacher (both in school and on campus). Given this, it would seem relevant to recommend that these practices continue within ITE. Specifically, placement and teaching experience appear to be a key factor in allowing early-phase practitioners to grow their feeling of preparedness. Whilst for some placement was viewed as where their 'real' learning happened, many saw it as an important opportunity to take what they had learnt on campus and apply it to their practice in school. However, for some of the participants, this link was not clear, thus suggesting that ITE programmes should also strive for the forming of more explicit connections between university learning and placement. Of particular interest was the observation that some participants did not always see the relevance of university classes and thus they saw limited value in those. This also highlights that colleagues within these programmes continue to find ways to make the relevance of university learning to school practice a fundamental part of classes but also encourage students to apply the learning to their own context to establish the relevance themselves. With that in mind, it is recommended that TEIs continue to build programmes that draw on the benefits of placement experience and complement this with campus learning and vice versa. These two components should be intertwined to support early-phase practitioners in developing their own practice and, subsequently, their feelings of preparedness.

As was previously indicated, for student teachers and early-phase practitioners in PE, the 'unknowns' had an impact on how prepared they felt for undertaking their role as a physical educator with responsibility for HWB. This indicates the need to continue with measures such as pre-placement visits, which allow students to develop an understanding of the context within which they are working, to support their feelings of preparedness. There is also the potential to advocate for reflection on ITE programmes, with a focus on how they support students in dealing with 'unknown' elements, as education is dynamic and, in many ways, 'unknown'. One 'unknown' was discussed frequently – certificated PE classes – the

participants felt that they did not know the course or have the experience to support them to feel prepared to teach this area. Thus, there is a need to prepare early-phase teachers for the role they might play in teaching certificated PE classes, and this could impact the ITE offered. This could include, as the participants of this study advocated, more time dedicated to certificated course. However, with the time constraints of ITE, particularly in a one-year PGDE programme, this may prove challenging.

HWB is an ill-defined term (Spratt, 2017) and the participants also highlighted that it was challenging for them to fully understand the totality of HWB. Teacher educators addressing HWB, particularly those involved with the teacher education of physical educators, would benefit from reflecting on how they might address the potential perception shift associated with an early-phase physical educator's understanding of HWB. In doing so, teacher educators may be able to support the development of a broader understanding of HWB in all student teachers, not just those within PE. That said, there may be a need to provide support to student teachers of PE given the potential for the extra or different responsibility they have because of the HWB agenda (Gray and Mitchell, 2015). Teacher educators would be well served by reflecting on how they encourage, develop, and promote a deep understanding of HWB, and the role that PE teachers play in delivering this. It is also worth considering how much is 'enough' for early-phase practitioners to be able to be prepared to successfully meet their responsibility for HWB. Part of this discussion could be a review of the Standards for Provisional and Full Registration and whether adapting those could lead to increased feelings of preparedness.

Given the view expressed by the participants, that they wanted to develop more subject knowledge to help them feel more prepared, teacher educators involved might benefit from working with providers of undergraduate degree programmes that are commonly accepted for entry into the PE PGDE. It may also be interesting to consider whether feelings of preparedness are also impacted in this way across other subject specialisms contained within the PGDE. Finally, the results of this research imply that it might be useful for teacher educators to reflect on their practice using the framework utilised in the current study. Listening to students' voices through, for example, module evaluations and national student surveys is widespread practice across ITE. However, examining practice from the perspective

of the student in this way might not only shed light on a more meaningful narrative on practice, but also model desirable practices for student teachers.

Local Authorities and School Leadership

HWB, and PE's position within it, resulted from changes to government policy and the curriculum. As such, this study provides cautious recommendations for policymakers and those that have a responsibility for implementing HWB within schools in Scotland. It will consider the implications for local authorities, school leadership.

In enacting policy and the curriculum, there appears to be a disconnect between the aspirations of CfE and what is understood and experienced by early-phase PE practitioners. Maclean et al. (2015) described how teachers have experienced the 'new' curriculum, finding a discrepancy between the policy constructors' understanding of the vision of PE and teachers' interpretation; this suggests that policymakers would benefit from engagement with policy enactors, such as PE teachers, to consider whether HWB policy is able to capture the many variables that exist in practice. It is possible that the HWB policy is too broad and would benefit from more structured guidance to support teachers understanding of how to implement it in practice. Countries which are following in the footsteps of Scotland (e.g., Wales) and those which have already embraced the health agenda (e.g., New Zealand) might find benefit in engaging in a similar discussion regarding how HWB is, or could be, understood in practice. It is possible that policy enactors in Scotland might benefit from engaging with developments in those (and other) countries as they continue to evolve the HWB policy and practice.

Considering how the achievement of the standards relevant to beginning teachers might contribute to feelings of preparedness in PE graduates would be a useful extension of this exercise. Thus, the reflection on the standards by relevant parties might be focused on the concept of what could be considered 'enough' to underpin the HWB practice of young educators in their probationary year and early phase of their career. This could, potentially, form an important part of the discussion, as this study has only presented a perception of what is happening within this context for PE graduates from the PGDE; it is unknown if this is

shared across the wider education sector. Of interest to this discussion is that *responsibility of all* as the term itself was not referred to or used much by the participants of this study. Whilst one would advocate that it should be more than a ‘buzzword’ that participants use, its relative absence in the conversations of the study suggests there is a need to consider whether the term which is an integral part of HWB policy is fully understood and utilised in practice. It is, therefore, important to also consider the strategies, roles, relationships, and responsibilities that are being established as part of enacting the HWB policy within Scotland.

The impact that ‘unknowns’ have on perceived preparedness has potential implications for local authorities as this may highlight the need to consider how probationary teachers are supported in understanding the context within which they will be working in prior to undertaking their probation year. Many local authorities will host general induction events and school-specific ones, and so reflecting on the impact and the timing of these could lead to a reduction of the feeling of ‘the unknown’ in early-phase practitioners.

School leadership teams have a responsibility for planning and implementing HWB within their context. In the time of the Pupil Equity Fund (Scottish Government, 2015), which has a particular focus on raising attainment, school leadership could benefit from considering how best to use funding to support the promotion of HWB given that it is linked to pupils’ ability to be successful (Porciani, 2013). This could include working with colleagues within schools and across authorities to drive forward the implementation of the HWB agenda. For example, some schools employ HWB curriculum leaders, as a promoted post, to undertake this very task; it would seem, however, that many of these roles are fulfilled by PE teachers. So further support may be needed for PE teachers who might undertake this role alongside a wider use of posts such as HWB curriculum leaders.

HWB is not always a subject to be ‘taught’; rather, it is often promoted or developed through things such as class routines, which are inherent to a teacher’s pedagogy. Therefore, it is advocated that HWB should remain the *responsibility of all*, as pedagogy, disposition and environment can all impact HWB. It is also recommended that if, as advocated by this study, HWB continues to be the *responsibility of all*, then *all* teachers must be challenged and supported to consider the impact of their pedagogical practices; it is important to consider

the role that they play in contributing to the development of HWB, whilst they also have a responsibility to liaise with others to clarify meaning within their context (Education Scotland, 2013). This could then support things like developing an ethos, classroom routines etc which support the promotion / development of HWB. Although this might be driven by individual teachers, school leadership teams and local authorities must also support it. Alongside this, those in leadership roles, such as Education Scotland, as well as those with responsibility for monitoring practice in schools, such as HMiE, could also support, challenge, and monitor the HWB practice in schools. Future research could consider whether developing a pedagogy that is cognizant of the responsibility for HWB has an impact on perceived preparedness.

Future Research Researchers

Having considered the study's contribution to knowledge and implications for practice, it is now appropriate to consider the implications for researchers and the wider research field. Specifically, undertaking research in this way has implications for researchers who are considering utilising IPA. IPA is less commonly used with focus groups, and this study serves to highlight that, as an analysis method, it can strengthen the research data produced in a focus group (Tomkins and Eatough, 2010). Additionally, in using multiple qualitative methods, the study serves to highlight the complementary nature of these. Utilising this may be beneficial for researchers who are also investigating their own practice, particularly those that are viewing their own practice through a student lens (Brookfield, 1995).

This research study contends that the role and position of ITE in developing levels of preparedness have not been sufficiently examined within the wider research field. Further research is needed to fully explore how to increase perceived preparedness to deliver HWB in early-phase PE teachers. Alongside this, given the range and the significance attached to time spent in school further research is required to explore the impact on these practices on perceived preparedness. Most importantly, as this research study was concerned with participants' perceptions of their preparedness, future studies could consider actual levels of preparedness through concepts such as competence. Although not explicitly stated in the findings of this research study, it was observed by the researcher that those students who were viewed as more competent had increased levels of preparedness and were more

reflective when identifying the factors that impacted those feelings. Similarly, research might focus on feelings of confidence within participants and whether a confident person feels more prepared, regardless of their competence.

Given that the sample within the study came from one ITE setting and was relatively small, future studies involving other ITE settings could develop a broader understanding of how preparedness is perceived by PE graduates across Scotland. Moreover, future research could potentially focus on additional secondary subjects, such as Biology and Home Economics, and their preparedness to meet the *responsibility of all*. Future studies could also focus on the *all*: every teacher's preparedness to deliver HWB. Given that there appears to be more success with HWB across the primary ages (Pitchforth et al., 2016), future research could focus on lessons that could be learnt and transferred into the secondary sector. Of particular interest would be whether the perceived preparedness of early-phase primary practitioners for meeting their HWB responsibility is impacted by factors like those mentioned by the participants in this study. The value placed on experience, with significant value attached to teaching experiences on placement and in school during the probationary year, raised an interesting question about whether experience is always useful in developing feelings of preparedness. As indicated earlier, this might not necessarily be the case, and future research could consider the conditions under which these experiences are critically reflected on.

Finally, going forward, research could be focused on the long-term perceived preparedness of PE teachers and as noted earlier, investigate whether factors such as context continue to influence perceived preparedness throughout their career. This could be conducted by revisiting study participants later in their careers, to achieve a greater understanding of how their perceived preparedness has evolved throughout their careers.

Limitations

This section will consider some of the key limitations of the study. It is acknowledged that there are more limitations of the study which are not considered here, as they are not within the control of the researcher, e.g., students all had different settings for 18 weeks of

placement. This means that 50% of the experience of the participants on the PGDE course is in a variable context. Pertinent limitations are considered below.

Within this study, a relatively small sample of participants, from one specific setting, engaged with the research. The justification for the sample was discussed in Chapter 3 and detailed that the selected sample was influenced by aspects of the methodology and what was feasible within the context of the study. As there are other PGDE programmes and undergraduate programmes of ITE within Scotland for PE teachers, it must be acknowledged that this is a potential limitation of the study in that it has not considered the other contexts within which ITE of PE teachers takes place. Although these programmes are different to the one in this study, they are all designed to support the achievement of the GTCS standards and so while there may be differences there will also be similarities with the context of this study. As a result, there are some potentially significant implications that could apply to other teacher education contexts in Scotland engaged in the teacher education of physical educators.

It is also important to acknowledge that there were multiple data cycles within the study and previous data collection cycles may have had an impact on future data cycles. Following each class as the participants graduated meant that ideas uncovered during the data collection and analysis within each cycle could, and did, result in changes within the course the following year. Some examples of this are explored during the reflections later in this chapter. It was inevitable that keeping the course as a 'constant' experience was not going to be possible and it is important to note that each data collection cycle actively had an impact on future practice within the course and, thus, on the following data collection cycle and, potentially, the feelings of preparedness of subsequent graduating classes. As detailed in Chapter 3, it was important then that authentic focus group questions that were related to the experiences of each respective graduating class were designed. This supported a focus on perceived preparedness and the factors that impacted it, which of course could include any changes made to the delivery of the ITE programme.

Studying one's students was a deliberate choice and, indeed, one of the significant motivations for the research project. This could be considered a limitation as the established

relationship may introduce bias. However, the participants displayed a significant investment in the quality of the programme and saw the research as an opportunity to develop and improve the programme, meaning it could be argued that this established relationship was also an inherent strength of the study. The use of the independent moderator for the focus groups which was detailed in Chapter 3 was a significant choice in attempting to reducing potential bias and power issues within the study. However, it must be recognised that this could introduce other potential challenges as they could introduce their own biases or influence the focus group conversations, which could be a challenge in all studies that involve focus groups (Litosseliti, 2003). As a result of recognising this, pre- and post-focus group conversations between the researcher and the moderator took on a critical friend role to consider preconceptions that might be present. These reflexive conversations also focussed on the processes within the focus group as well debriefing between the researcher and the moderator. This helped with considering the different perspectives presented during the focus group and potentially supported the research to see things they might not see. The conversations tried to make unconscious bias conscious and to see different perspectives from the focus group which has the potential to enhance the research study (Cohen et. al., 2018). Being open to the perspective of the independent moderator in this way has the potential to strengthen the research, it is acknowledged that this might have influence aspects of the study such as analysis and this is where bracketing (as is required within IPA) became of particular significance.

While it is acknowledged that there are some possible limitations within the study, the preceding discussion presents some potential ways to overcome these with future research and the steps taken to reduce the impact of these possible limitations with the study. Nonetheless, as with most studies, the current study is subject to limitations and as such the findings must be viewed with caution and the limitations detailed above should be borne in mind.

Reflections

I had read the work of Brookfield (1995, 2006) many times, most recently as part of gaining my fellowship to the Higher Education Academy, but the importance of a student lens in

reflecting on my practice was something I wholeheartedly believed would be the thing that mattered most in developing my practice. Subsequently, this led to the main premise behind the current study, which was to examine my practice with my students. I wanted to embrace what Brookfield (2006) identified as the 'essence' of skilful teaching and research my students' experiences to make decisions about the course and my pedagogy because of these insights.

Initially, I was interested in investigating the impact that ITE had on competence. However, in preparing to write a rationale I realised that competence was a complex concept and that this would require a viewpoint of 'everything depends on the teacher' (Brookfield, 2006, p.10). This viewpoint assumes that if I do a 'good' job my students will become competent teachers and, conversely, that if I am incompetent in any way, the competence of the student teachers will not develop. I found this to be an arrogant viewpoint which ignored the student teacher. Reflecting on what matters to me – my students and their experiences – I could not ignore the participatory role they play in their own teacher education. I knew that without involving and acknowledging my students, I would not be able to gain insight into their feelings about their experiences.

I then considered looking at the participants' confidence to undertake their role as teachers of PE and the responsibility for HWB that comes with that. Confidence, though frequently researched in education, is very complex and difficult to measure with reference to teaching (Tschannen-Moran et al., 1998). As such, it seemed that, perhaps, this was not the route to take for the study. This was further confirmed when reading literature surrounding teacher education, particularly the work of Diane Mayer, who spoke of perceived preparedness. It was in attending the Stow Lecture (Mayer, 2016) that I truly settled on this concept of perceived preparedness. She spoke passionately about the importance of effective teacher education (Mayer, 2016), and this resonated with me, particularly the interesting question regarding how we got to the point in the current policy context that views teacher education as a problem that needs to be fixed (Mayer, 2016). One key factor that struck me during Diane's presentation was that, in her study, teacher education programmes accounted for very little variance in graduate teachers' overall perceptions of preparedness (Mayer, 2016), which prompted me to wonder whether that was the case in Scotland. The concept of investigating

how prepared participants perceived themselves to be and how they came to feel that way seemed to provide a potential way to unpick the participants' feelings about their experiences during ITE. It was particularly comforting that someone had investigated teacher education in this way previously. Thus, my investigation settled on looking at perceptions of preparedness from a student viewpoint.

As a result of my close relationship with the research participants, power dynamics was something that played on my mind constantly throughout the study. Some of this is detailed in Chapter 3 when considering my positionality and when considering the actions taken during the study related to reducing bias and power issues. I wanted to be a 'critically aware teacher' (Brookfield, 2006, p.11) who researched how the programme on which I taught was perceived by my students to understand the meaning and significance students ascribed to their experiences. However, I knew that being so 'close to home' could result in students feeling as though they had to participate or feeling that they wanted to 'help me out': ultimately, it could have changed the power dynamics in our relationship. Researching my own practice in this way could be both a gold mine and a minefield! As such, this thesis must be recognised as only one, potential, way to look at a particular topic of interest that is intimately connected to my own experiences, beliefs, and values and those of the participants, including our joint experiences, beliefs, and values.

People told me that to undertake study at this level, being committed and organised is essential. I was certain that I could be organised but I knew the commitment hinged on my motivation for the subject studied. I used plans of work and timetables (Appendix 14), and would recommend those to any future research student. This included planning for how I would establish a balance given that I was a full-time lecturer and part-time research student; having a social life does not happen by chance and took a great deal of effort. This was one of the most significant things that I learnt during the process, that you must actively plan ways which support you in establishing this balance. Alongside this, I learned that no matter how organised I was, and no matter how many times people reassured me that I was 'on the right track', the independent nature of a study like this always leads to a nagging doubt. Simply put, was I making a meaningful contribution to new knowledge and was I building on the work of others? I came to the realisation that this constant grappling was a key part of engaging in

research and that if I was not doing this, I was not doing it 'right'. I think ahead to potentially supporting others on their journey and wonder how this might manifest itself and how I could contribute to the ongoing intellectual struggle associated with engaging in research. I do not profess to have the answer to that 'struggle', but I would be confident that I could reassure and support students as they negotiated their own work.

In closing, I want to reflect on what it all meant for me as a teacher educator. A dear colleague and friend of mine subscribes to the view that being a researcher does not necessarily equate to you being an effective teacher educator and, to some extent, I would agree with this; I considered myself to be an effective teacher educator before I undertook this work. Am I now a better teacher educator because of this study? I would have to say yes. My study has allowed me to consider a wide range of aspects within my practice by viewing them through my students' eyes, which was both enlightening and terrifying all at the same time. Earlier in the limitations section of this chapter, I alluded to changes to the course that may have an impact on the data collection and, consequently, the study. However, when considering my own practice, this was the factor that had the greatest impact on me and my practice as a teacher educator. For example, in 2015, several students commented that, whilst they enjoyed the micro-teaching activities, focusing these on a particular teaching style, rather than a specific activity, would result in them feeling more prepared. In the following year, in consultation with colleagues, I structured the activities in this way, with each micro-teaching activity focusing on specific teaching styles. In that data collection cycle, micro-teaching activities continued to be a significant positive factor and there was only one mention of using school pupils to make these activities more realistic to improve perceived preparedness. Anecdotally, and through official channels (module evaluations), students highlighted these micro-teaching activities as constituting valuable practice across the course.

As part of programme-wide development, a set of core activities was created for all secondary subject students and, because of my research, micro-teaching opportunities and opportunities to practice skills related to teaching were prioritised on this list. Alongside this, the participants highlighted subject knowledge development as having the potential to increase their preparedness, the content of the PGDE for our PE students was reviewed considering that observation, and some changes were made to the number of activities used

throughout the year. More significantly, I began to collaborate with colleagues on our undergraduate sports-related degrees to design option modules that might support the development of those students who were considering progressing to the PGDE route. It will be interesting to see if it has any influence on the development of subject knowledge in the long term. These are a few examples of how looking at my practice through a student lens and the impact that it had on them challenged me to reflect and, where appropriate, change aspects within my practice.

The other revelation which really stuck with me was how a few of the students perceived the expectations for the group. I have always had (and continue to have) high expectations for my students, as they are the future of the profession. I view this as an enormous responsibility, perhaps that is where my high expectations come from; and consider myself fortunate to be able to, in some way, shape the future of the subject and profession that I love. One class stated that, they would have benefitted from a vote of confidence prior to assessments and that because they perceived expectations to be high, there was always a slight fear that they might not 'make it' and they might not pass. At the time they shared this, they knew the result of their course and they had all 'made it' – some barely passed, and others passed with flying colours. In setting high expectations, I had the goal of encouraging student teachers to think about what kind of teacher they wanted to be and how they could be the best that they could be. On reflection, I do believe that high expectations continue to be a way to achieve this. However, because of this, I have collaborated with colleagues to support the group in building confidence and try to reduce some of the perceived pressure that students may feel whilst under my care.

It seems appropriate to end with one of my favourite quotes from Stephen Brookfield (1995, p.3): 'we teach to change the world'. I know that I and my teaching have changed because of this study, and I hope that, in some way, the participants have benefitted from it too, and that our small piece of the PE world is a better place as a result.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Wellbeing Wheel

Participant Information Sheet

Study Title and Research Details

Health and Wellbeing - Responsibility of All: Are all ready for the responsibility? – A critical examination of the levels of preparedness in Initial Teacher Education graduates in Physical Education.

Researcher

Elaine McCulloch - [REDACTED]

Supervisor

Professor Rowena Murray – [REDACTED]

Invitation Paragraph

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why this research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Please take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

Thank you for taking the time to read this.

What is the purpose of the study?

In the current education climate, Health and Wellbeing have been given prominence in Scotland. Along with Literacy and Numeracy, teachers have been given the responsibility for Health and Wellbeing across the curriculum (Education Scotland, n.d.). Alongside this, Health and Wellbeing teaching has been established as a way of challenging health inequalities in Scotland (Chief Medical Officer, 2011). Given the importance that is placed on Health and Wellbeing it is imperative that the next generation of teachers is prepared to deliver 'Learning through health and wellbeing that promotes confidence, independent thinking and positive attitudes and dispositions' (Building the Curriculum 1, 2006).

The aim of this research is to investigate the impact of Initial Teacher Education (ITE) courses on probationary teachers' levels of preparedness to deliver Health and Wellbeing, focusing on Physical Education graduates. Participants in this study will reflect on their ITE course and in particular assess their levels of preparedness for entering the profession as a result of their participation in the ITE Course at UWS.

Why have I been chosen?

Having either recently completed or in the process of completing your Initial Teacher Education course you fall into the target group for this project and this is why you have been selected. Your experience of your initial teacher education course and opinions on the levels of preparedness in graduates are essential to developing our understanding of both of those areas within this study.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you decide to take part you are still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason.

What will happen to me if I take part?

If you decide to take part in this research project, you will be invited to complete a simple questionnaire, which will be distributed towards the end of April. This questionnaire will be completed online (paper versions are available) and should take about 20 minutes to complete

Following on from the questionnaire you may choose to participate in one of our focus group sessions in order to explore your opinions on the themes emerging from the questionnaire related to the levels of preparedness amongst probationary teachers. The focus groups, will be audio recorded, will be conducted in the first two weeks of June and they should take between 30 and 45 minutes to complete.

Finally, you may choose to participate in an interview following the completion of your probationary year. The interviews normally take place in the June of your probation year and will be arranged at a time / location that is convenient for you. They will be audio recorded and should take between 30 and 45 minutes.

Will my taking part in the study be kept confidential?

All information that is collected about you during the course of the research will be kept strictly confidential and not passed onto any third parties. Any information obtained will be kept in a safe location and computer files will be protected by password access. The data will be destroyed immediately after the publication of the results of the thesis. Paper copies will be shredded and all audio and electronic files will be deleted. Pseudonyms will be used in any publication arising from the research in order to protect the anonymity of those who participate.

What will happen to the results of this research study?

This research is being carried out as part of my PhD Studies and is supported by the School Of Education at UWS. The results of this study will be made available through the School of Education upon request.

Contact for further information

My dissertation supervisor, Professor Rowena Murray, and the Ethics Committee have reviewed this project. For further information regarding this study, please do not hesitate to contact me. If you have any concerns regarding the conduct of this research project, please contact the School of Education Ethics Officer:

Dr Beth Cross –

Consent Form

Title of Project: Health and Wellbeing - Responsibility of All: Are all ready for the responsibility? – A critical examination of the levels of preparedness in Initial Teacher Education graduates in Physical Education.

Name of Researcher: Elaine McCulloch

- 1. I confirm that I have read and understand the Participant Information Sheet for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.
- 2. I give my consent to (please tick as appropriate) **YES** **NO**
 - 0. a. Completing the Questionnaire (approx 20 mins)
 - 1. b. Participating in a focus group (approx 30-45 mins)
 - 2. c. Audio Recording of the focus group
- 3. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason.
- 4. Please indicate whether you wish to participate in this study (please tick as appropriate)

I **agree** to take part in the above study

I **do not agree** to take part in the above study

Name of Participant

Date

Signature

Researcher

Date

Signature

Appendix 4: Participant Communication

Intro Email

Hi xxxxxx,

Hope that you are well and getting a chance to enjoy teaching in this lovely weather. As you will remember from one of our last inputs, I had spoken to you all about participating in my Phd Research. Attached to this email you will find an invitation letter which outlines the project and what will be expected from you. Please email me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. If you could return the consent form via email (an electronic signature is acceptable) in the next 7 days that would be much appreciated.

Thanks in advance for your support in this project.

Elaine

Follow Up Email Example

Hi Everyone,

Firstly massive thanks to all who have signed up and completed the survey. As the survey is anonymous it is impossible for me to tell who has filled it out (hence why this email went to everyone) so if you have filled out the survey thanks and please feel free to ignore the rest of this email. :)

For those of you who have sent through your consent form you can access the survey here: [Initial Teacher Education Survey](#). The survey will remain open for a few more days so if you were able to fill it out that would be extremely helpful as analysis starts soon.

Thanks and hope you have a great bank holiday.

Elaine

Focus Group Email

Hi xxxxxx,

I hope that you are well and are getting some time to relax over the break. I wanted to send you a quick email to thank you for volunteering to be part of my Phd Study. I attach the participant information sheet to this email for your information. A link to the survey will be sent the week beginning the 15th of May. If you could set aside 20 minutes or so to complete the survey before the 26th of May that would be much appreciated.

The Focus group dates are listed below for your information. Closer to the time you will be asked to select a date and location that suits your schedule.

Ayr Focus Group- 13th June 2pm -3.30pm
Glasgow Focus Group - 6th July - 2pm - 3.30pm

Any questions about the research please let me know.

Elaine

Interview Email Example

Hi xxxx,

In my excitement over how good Killie are I forgot to mention about my PhD. As you will probably remember you indicated last year that you would be willing to contribute to the final stage of my PhD research, the interviews. Potential dates are listed below, let me know if any of those dates work for you.

3rd, 5th, 10th, 12th - AM or PM

Interviews can be held in Ayr, Hamilton, Paisley or Glasgow. Alternatively, I could pop over to school if you are able to secure a meeting room that would be quiet. They should last between 30-45 minutes, depending on how talkative you are! :) It will be a semi structured discussion about your experiences during your probationary year. You will be asked to consider how prepared you were to undertake your probationary year and how prepared you feel moving forward into the early stages of your career.

I appreciate your help with this and if none of the above dates work feel free to suggest an alternative and we can hopefully get our schedules to work.

Elaine

Appendix 5: Focus Group Schedule

Focus Group

Introductions and ask participants to pick a pseudonym for the transcript (a fake name that will be used to refer to them throughout the research so that they cannot be identified). Make a note of these here:

Name	Pseudonym
-------------	------------------

You are being asked to recall the experiences of your Initial Teacher Education. The results will be analysed and used for exploration of the themes from the survey and contributed towards PhD research. You were selected because you have direct experience of the Initial teacher education programme.

Guidelines

- _ There are no right or wrong answers, only differing points of view
- _ You don't need to agree with others, but you must listen respectfully as others share their views. The intention is that you will interact with each other, but will be willing to listen to all views.
- _ We're tape recording, one person speaking at a time and please turn off mobile phones so as not to interrupt recording.
- _ My role as moderator will be to guide the discussion as we work through the questions.
- _ All information discussed at this focus group is confidential and should remain that way after the focus group is finished, so no discussing with other people (especially those in the other focus groups).
- _ Specific support / instances is extremely helpful within the discussion we need to ensure confidentiality and thus generic terms should be used to describe people and schools i.e. placement school or school mentor

Go over structure:

Introductory questions (5 minutes)

Discussion / Expansion of themes from questionnaire (25 – 30 mins)

Short Break (5 mins)

Final Questions (5 – 10 minutes)

Introductory Question:

Would you like to say what has stood out for you during your Initial Teacher Education this year?

Probe what will stay with you as you enter your probationary year?

Theme: Preparation

Question:

In the survey participants rated their level of preparation as 4 out of 5 for beginning your probationary year. What factors do you think contribute to this rating of perceived preparedness?

Probe: Can you explain why you feel that way? Can you provide examples to support your view? What are other people's views? Are their experiences the same?

Clarifications: So what you are saying is ... provide a summary

Question:

School Placement experiences and subject studies were both described as 'stand out' experiences by participants in the survey. Would you say that one stood out over the other?

Probe: Can you explain why you feel that way? Can you provide examples to support your view? What are other people's views? Are their experiences the same?

Follow up Question: Did they impact on your feelings of preparedness? In what way?

Clarifications: So what you are saying is ... provide a summary

Question:

Participants in the survey highlighted time spent teaching within teaching tasks and placement experiences as contributing to feelings of preparedness. Do you agree with this?

Probe: Can you explain why you feel that way? Can you provide examples to support your view? What are other people's views? Are their experiences the same?

Follow Up Question: Feedback from tutors / mentors / teachers was highlighted as being integral to feelings of preparedness, was this the case for you? How did it contribute?

Clarifications: So what you are saying is ... provide a summary

Question:

Participants identified three types of content that contributed to their feelings of preparedness. These were PE specific content, pedagogical content and wider curricular content. What is your opinion on that?

Probe: Can you explain why you feel that way? Are there other content areas that contribute to your preparedness? Can you provide examples to support your view? What are other people's views? Are their experiences the same?

Clarifications: So what you are saying is ... provide a summary

Question

Participants equated their level of confidence for teaching to feelings of preparedness, what factors do you feel contribute to your confidence?

Probe: Can you explain why you feel that way? Can you expand on that? Do others agree or disagree?

Follow up Question: Do your feelings of confidence impact your feelings of preparedness?

Clarifications: So what you are saying is ... provide a summary

Question:

Across the curriculum who do you think has responsibility for the delivery of Health and Wellbeing?

Probe: Why do you feel that way? Can you provide examples to support? Can you expand on that? Do others agree or disagree?

Follow up Question: Is Physical Education enough to ensure Health and Wellbeing?

Clarifications: So what you are saying is ... provide a summary

Question:

Overall do you think that you are prepared for the responsibility of delivering health and wellbeing?

Probe: Why do you feel that way? Can you provide examples to support? Can you expand on that? Do others agree or disagree?

Follow up Question: In the survey participants felt more prepared to deliver HWB than they felt for their probationary year overall, what is your experience of this?

Clarifications: So what you are saying is ... provide a summary

Final Question:

The purpose of the focus group was to recall your experiences within your initial teacher education course and your feelings of preparedness, with that in mind Is there anything else you would like to share on the topic?

Probe: Anything that we have omitted? Or that is really important to you?

Thanks for your participation and if you could complete the short form to review the process that would be much appreciated.

Appendix 6: Interview Schedule

Interview Schedule

Welcome and thank you.

Remind participants that they will be recorded and be asked to recall their experience of their probationary year.

Remind participants that all information discussed at this interview is confidential and should remain that way after the interview.

Remind participants that while specific support / instances is extremely helpful we need to ensure confidentiality and thus generic terms should be used to describe people and schools i.e. placement school or school mentor

Remind Participants of their pseudonym for the transcript (a fake name that will be used to refer to them throughout the research so that they cannot be identified.

Go over structure:

Introductory questions 5 minutes

Discussion / Expansion of specific experiences 15 -20 mins

Final Questions (5 – 10 minutes)

Section A

Themselves, their probationary year, their interest / involvement in wellbeing

Opening question:

Can you tell me a little bit about how your probationary year has gone?

Prompts / Probes:

Involvement in HWB activities

Section B

Preparedness for delivering health and wellbeing, reflecting on differences similarities between how you felt this time last year, your experiences this year and how you feel now, understanding of HWB

Question: Is there anything that stands out for you when you think about physical education teachers and their responsibility to deliver health and wellbeing?

Prompts / Probes:

Why do you feel that way?

What factors contributed to your views? Experiences? Probationary year?

Clarifications: So what you are saying is ... provide a summary

Question: Research in this study so far has suggested that at graduation you felt prepared to enter your probationary year, reflecting back on your probationary year, what are your views on your preparedness?

Probe / Prompts: Can you explain why you feel that way? Have your views changed? What factors contribute to your feelings of preparedness? Can you provide examples to support your view?

Clarifications: So what you are saying is ... provide a summary

Question: Research in this study so far has suggested that there was a disconnect between on campus inputs and placements during ITE, what is your opinion on that?

Probe / Prompts: Can you explain why you feel that way? Have your views changed? Can you provide examples to support your view?

Clarifications: So what you are saying is ... provide a summary

Question: Research in this study so far has suggested that placement was one of the main contributing factors to feelings of preparedness, what is your opinion on that?

Probe / Prompts: Can you explain why you feel that way? Have your views changed? Can you provide examples to support your view?

Clarifications: So what you are saying is ... provide a summary

Question: Looking forward to next year, can you tell me how prepared you feel to deliver on your responsibility for health and wellbeing now?

Prompts / Probes:

Why do you feel that way? Have your views changed?

What factors contribute to your feelings preparedness?

Clarifications: So what you are saying is ... provide a summary

Question: What do you think health and wellbeing is?

Prompts / Probes:

What has led to this? Your experiences? Your observations?

Could you provide some examples from your practice to illustrate?

Clarifications: So what you are saying is ... provide a summary

Section C

Catch all questions to allow participants to voice anything that has not been covered

Is there anything else you would like to share that we haven't discussed?

Thank you for your time, your thoughts and views have been interesting and appreciated.

Appendix 7: Timeline

Cycle 1 – Pilot Study (Class of 2015)

Invitations to participate – April 2015
Questionnaire – May 2015
Questionnaire Data Analysis - May / June 2015
Focus Groups – July 2015
Focus Group Transcription – July 2015
Focus Group Data Analysis – July / August 2015
Interviews – June 2016

Cycle 2 – Main Study (Class of 2016)

Invitations to participate – April 2016
Questionnaire – May 2016
Questionnaire Data Analysis - May / June 2016
Focus Groups – July 2016
Focus Group Transcription – July 2016
Focus Group Data Analysis – July / August 2016
Interview – June 2017

Cycle 3 – Main Study (Class of 2017)

Invitations to participate – April 2017
Questionnaire – May 2017
Questionnaire Data Analysis - May / June 2017
Focus Groups – July 2017
Focus Group Transcription – July 2017
Focus Group Data Analysis – July / August 2017
Interviews – June 2018

Appendix 8: Sample Interview Transcript with Analysis

Excerpt of Monica's Transcript with Analysis

Interviewee – Monica Class of 2016

Location – GLA

Interviewer – EM

June 2017

Initial Noting Key

Highlighting = text viewed as interesting during initial noting

Underlining = text viewed as important during further re-reading

Comments (in text boxes) = offer initial thoughts, followed by commentary on potential meaning and interpretations

Colour code of themes =

Influence of Context

Reflections / Reflective Practice

Influence of Experiences

Networking / Support / Relationships

Placement

Preparation

Subject Knowledge

1 **EW:** So, the first question is really quick. A kind of general one
2 just thinking about your probation year and what were the
3 things that you were really interested in and that you found that
4 were really useful for you? Did you have any involvement in
5 health and well-being so given that focus could you tell me a
6 little bit about your probationary year and how it went?
7

8 **M:** Yeah. I think to start off when I was in a department that had
9 **two guidance teachers**, so there was kind of a lot of going on
10 within the department. I didn't have a PT in post, **so it was very**
11 **much that I was left to my own devices, but at the same time I**
12 **wanted to make sure that I was still doing as much as I could**
13 **whole school wise** but not feel like I was treading on people's
14 toes just be like, "Oh I am just going to do this because I don't
15 really have anybody to ask permission to," and things like that.
16 **But then, because of the two guidance teachers, I was really well**
17 **versed on GIRFEC**, like off from them both and it was like... you
18 know as soon as something was even remotely abnormal, or had
19 any concerns, or whatsoever, **I just used my professional**
20 **judgement and just go for it.** So, that was really good. I felt like

Make up of department in the **context** linked to practice and development

Interwoven with **reflections** on opportunities this **context** provided for development

21 after that, I was like, I think like going forward, that's where I
22 want to keep my interest within the guidance and within what
23 agencies are involved in there. So that was really good from that
24 perspective. In terms of like more whole school health and well-
25 being, there's was not a lot going on, so there was a lot of
26 opportunity for me to be like what can I may bring new to the
27 school. But again, something that's going to be sustainable so it's
28 not just, "Oh hey I'm a probationer. Here's this thing," and then
29 go. So, there, we're actually going to be with the school. The
30 pupils health and well-being erm subject, it was going through
31 change and it was turning into a tutor period that we would have
32 once a week, on a Wednesday period 3. So I had a lot of
33 opportunity to kind of play with it with designing that and
34 things. And from personal experience I have had a lot of personal
35 experience with mental health and all the agencies behind that.
36 So I actually helped make up the three week, four week module
37 on mental health, and kind of using like search engines, and
38 using different websites, and having it as a platform, and then
39 building from that. And I had used some of my like personal
40 exercises on how to get kids aware of like what schizophrenia is,
41 and what bipolar is, and I trial runned it with one of my health
42 and wellbeing class and then put it in and we've got some
43 feedback and they really enjoyed it for that particular year
44 group. So, that's really good to know that I had made an impact
45 and that's actually going to be implemented in that school for
46 the next few years.

47
48 **EW:** That's really good.

49
50 **M:** So, that was pretty good. And then, on that staff side of
51 things and there was health and wellbeing committee, and that
52 was more of a focus on social health, shall we say? Is that right?
53 [laughs] And it was like end of term things like nights out and
54 then what to do, that kind of thing. And I also involved doing
55 things throughout the year, like we've done the West Highland
56 way challenge. So, everybody that signed up they had to walk a
57 certain distance in a certain amount of time and all that kind of
58 stuff. and we've done the kids, we've got an email through from
59 Scottish rowing about the rowing challenge we've done, and
60 we've actually done that to made the staff have a goal, as well,
61 and it was kind of quite fun. And then, as part of the Health and
62 Well-being Committee, we were the ones who set up like this
63 the staff versus pupils at the end of the year, and things like
64 that.

Personal Experience linked to developing and having an impact on delivery of HWB

If this opportunity hadn't been provided would the development still have happened in a different context?

Staff health and wellbeing promotion linked to PE activities

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EW: Right.

M: And it was all about making sure that the staffs health and well-being was kept up and going and we set up a Yoga class and hosted a reading group. Just things that were really making people like interlinked because it is a small community it's a massive school, but a small community that it comes from. You had to really like your colleagues. Otherwise, it would impact you kinda life outside of school. So that was really important to make those bonds what it did and I definitely, therefore made friends for life both professionally and just kind of like call you and say hey how you are getting on?

School specific **context** linked to actions and priorities

Networking viewed as important in **context**, perhaps because of the **context**

Implied **connections** are useful professional development and as a personal relationship

EW: Yeah, did Kyle get in touch with you?

M: I got in touch with Kyle so there is now a PT in post, who was one of the guidance teachers and she's been very hard to deal with this year, because of a very head-strong woman. And it's kinda like her way or no way. And in my opinion she wanted to kind of bully me at the start just to see how far she could push me. But being someone who doesn't really like being pushed about, I was like, "Actually, no, I am going to stand up for myself." So she didn't really like that to start with, but then, I think it made a good foundation for us because she knew where, and I knew where her lines were as well. and then by the end we were working really close I told him, "Keep everyone on side." That's the best advice I had been given for that stuff.

Close working relationship as a result of initial challenging interactions

EW: Yeah. I saw him on Friday at graduation but forgot to ask him cause of course there was maybe other things in graduation as there would be. So, the other questions that I have here kind of really just asking you to think back to focus groups. Which I know it was a really long time ago but I will be able to jog your memory with that one. But also just some of the themes that came out of the focus group and think about what are your opinions on the now. Have they changed across the year and stuff so you don't have to remember too much just think about the year as a whole. So the first one's really just thinking about you know at the focus group we talked a lot about how prepared we felt, to deliver health and wellbeing and to do our job. And for the most part people said they were reasonably well prepared you know there was still this fear of the unknown but that they were reasonably prepared. So, I'm just wondering how

109 do you feel now, you know, going forward looking back, were
110 you as prepared as you thought you were? I mean its kind of a
111 big question there, but just the idea of based on your year, were
112 you as prepared as you thought you were, were things different?
113 you obviously understood a lot more better from the because of
114 your involvement but did things change? Your perception
115 changed?

116
117 **M:** Erm, I learned a lot about myself I think in terms of knowing
118 how to adjust to different circumstances when it came to
119 peoples approaching and obviously being a student you're only
120 there for like a few weeks but being there for the year you build
121 up very strong relationships and have good rapport with them.
122 And for some of the classes you weren't just getting pupils like
123 once or twice a week like I was getting as one particular boy,
124 about six periods a week and he was a third year, and just
125 because of the options he chose and I was his teacher all of that.
126 And it was kind of like just like it was like as an example, it was
127 something that ended up being quite a vice for him and it was
128 someone who was constant within his week and he actually had
129 a lot of underlying mental health conditions that hadn't actually
130 been brought up, up until this point. And like I said in the
131 department were like yes just put him in GIRFEC. So I ended up
132 doing a lot for this one particular boy because he was so not like
133 different, unhealthy characteristics, just very strange. I hadn't
134 dealt with anything like that before, when like, this is me,
135 isolated in my class with this person. At least when you're a
136 student, you kinda have the other teacher there. So the other
137 one was like, "Yeah, they are always like that," I'm kinda like, are
138 they always like this, what do I do?" And as a result of that,
139 agencies have managed to come in. There's been a child plan put
140 in place for him and in terms of the guidance side it's really
141 helped having a class for that long. And I don't think you can
142 possibly prepare for that with that student, because you do only
143 have a certain amount of weeks there to work with. However,
144 because of the way that you had obviously designed the program
145 and make it that the two different placement schools you had
146 were different in terms of whether they were affluent or a little
147 bit more deprived and things. Being at one of the schools the
148 second placement where deprivation was very high and their
149 health and wellbeing was almost at the forefront of everything
150 that they done. It was, was able to able to recall a lot of the
151 experience and I was able to get in touch with people from that
152 school but, not that I am having any bother but have you got any

Learning linked to adapting to the **context**

Student **experience** compared to probationary experience

Emphasis on being able to **build relationships** in that time linked to example of supporting HWB

Missing **experience**

Placement time linked to ability to prepare

Indication that there are somethings that can't be prepared for during ITE, linked to timescale

Recalling **experiences** and **networks**

Specific link to support provided by an **experience** where HWB was prominent

153 strategies and restorative practice was something at their school
154 like had their behaviour policy written after. And it wasn't
155 something that my probation school actually had incorporated
156 yet so I was able to pull on a lot of experience and ask them for
157 other of guidance of how to go about it. Obviously there was a
158 lot of managerial change within that department so I was then
159 asking someone who was in a much higher position. Who was
160 actually seeing it from a much more whole school perspective.
161 So that was really good in terms of kind of like course content
162 prepared. Erm, I suppose it's just you have to experience that
163 kind of side of things and like I said delivering the health and
164 wellbeing course it's completely different to what I would have
165 thought it was going to be. But that's just I feel that's just
166 because of where the schools at in terms of if how far ahead it is
167 in terms of understanding health and wellbeing themselves. They
168 were still using very old school like methods and old school dvd's
169 about different aspects of health and it was quite hard to then
170 come and be like I've got some ideas. I was like nope just keep
171 them to yourself for the moment. And then we'll roll with it as it
172 comes up so that, I think that was difficult I think maybe had I
173 into gone into school that was a little bit more a kind of on the
174 ball with health and wellbeing. Then it would have been a lot
175 more kinda educational and I would have learned a lot more but
176 I do feel like going into the school that I was in, it was very much
177 at the same level as what I had come from on postgrad.

Drawing on experience and getting guidance linked to practice

Subject knowledge and preparation

Shifting view of what HWB entails in practice

Influenced by context understanding of HWB

178
179 **EW:** It was interesting what we were talking about there about
180 drawing on your placement experiences because that was one of
181 the things I kinda highlighted that I wanted to talk about so we
182 will maybe just hit on that as we are talking about it. But this
183 idea that most of the students that you graduated and across all
184 my research basically suggested that placement was one of the
185 main contributing factors to them feeling prepared to go into the
186 big bad real world and so do you think that that still holds true
187 now? what is your opinion on that?

188 **M:** Yeah. Absolutely. It was, its having a network to actually go to
189 someone and be like you know I really value, do you know the
190 learning logs that were done with our folder? and obviously
191 there were a lot of different categories with that. And one of
192 them was about like with behaviour management and a massive
193 part of that for me was because there is sort of different
194 policies that the schools had so I was actually able to go back

Value of placement linked to support networks

Activities from placement helped recall experiences

195 into my file and just be like 'So that's what they done' and I was
196 like am not really sure how I would implement that here because
197 that's very school specific. So that's where I then got in touch
198 with said person and I was like am not really sure how to come
199 out of your schools way of like doing that, so how could I? And it
200 was things like him, I ended up doing. I was having a particular
201 bother with these particular girls that were, they were younger,
202 they were first year but there was just no kind of thing I could
203 think of was working and so we came up with a written
204 agreement and that was just through speaking with that person
205 about how does restorative practice work for you and so then
206 coming up with writing agreements with that pupil and that was
207 really quite good.

Utilising **network** to brainstorm ideas

Even though may not have come across situation previously
network support continued throughout probation year

208 **EW:** It was interesting that you were able to make those
209 connections and adapt for the school that you're in and draw on
210 that experience and that quite nicely linked into other things that
211 I've wanted to pick up on was this theme of sometimes there
212 was a, you know, a disconnect between what we did on campus
213 and what happened on placement and there you've obviously
214 made a really nice connection between placement and your
215 probation year. And I'm wondering what is your opinion on that
216 now? Are the things that you have gone back to? you did see a
217 little bit there. Are things that you've gone back to? are there still
218 things that you are like I don't see the connection yet or I don't
219 think that I'll ever see the connection? So do you still feel that
220 there was a wee bit of a disconnect the course and the thinking
221 of reality of teaching I guess?

222 **M:** You've, I've gone back to a lot of the resources I've made and
223 adapted them for all the classes I've been working with and I
224 think that I took all of like the avenues in terms of like software
225 that we could use but that is something that I've constantly
226 gone back to like making resources etc. I think maybe some of, I
227 feel like, the subject, the actual subject specific stuff was
228 valuable in terms of content because there was certain ones that
229 I would come up to me and was like what could I recall on, what
230 kind of springs to mind and then you do go back to the practical
231 lessons where you are actually involved and you remember
232 what you were doing because that's what you want the pupils to
233 actually experience so you draw on your own experience
234 and from you being the teacher in that situation. There was
235 some things that I can't even think of. I remember sitting in the
236 lecture but I don't remember what it was about and therefore I

Subject inputs continue to hold value in supporting **content knowledge** and recall

Experience shapes views of what lessons could / should involve

Recalling **experiences** where they were the teacher to feed into current practice

237 don't remember how to then implement it. There was one
238 where the gentleman came in and he had been dealing with kids
239 that were really kind of badly behaved like there were maybe
240 bad children And he came in and I found that really interesting
241 however it was completely irrelevant to where I was going
242 however it was good to know that if I was to went to go into a
243 school that I could kinda recall on experience from there and its
244 actually only now like I'm coming out of probation here where
245 I'm moving so I am going through a lot of my stuff and I feel like I
246 think, I don't need that anymore I don't remember even, like I
247 hate saying this because it makes me feel really bad but the
248 numeracy and literacy kind of little modules that we had done.
249 I've really not had to draw on any of that at all.

lack of recall linked to not implementing due to views of **relevance** of the topic to their particular context

Reflection that it could be useful at some point - potential relevance

Other areas of responsibility for all not draw on at all in probation year - lack of **relevance** generally or to **context**?

Other areas of responsibility for all not draw on at all in probation year - lack of **relevance** generally or to **context**?

Appendix 9: Full Interview Transcript

Interviewee – Ross Class of 2016
Location – GLA

Interviewer – EM
June 2017

The first section of interview transcript has been removed as the personal and professional history revealed here might compromise anonymity. The final section has also been omitted as the conversation veered off-topic, as the interview reached its close.

Interviewer: So my first question really just is about, em, can you tell me all about how your probationary year went and specifically thinking about what you were most interested in? Any involvement in your health and wellbeing? Just that general kind of overview of how your probationary year was.

Ross: It was good. {school name} is a good school to learn in, massive, sort of big classes, quick turn arounds. Really experienced faculty that I was coming into. And I'm just sort of getting used to working with loads of different personalities and big department as well. It's like eight of us some doing part-time. And lots of different kids, very socially, economically diverse. Kids from SMD 1 and 2, so it's kind of getting used to figuring out what their home lives were like and how that impacted on how they were acting in school. So a good school to learn at. Quite challenging at times but you've got the full range of experiences from the really really challenging to high attaining and everything in between. And it was good and interesting just developing my own actual classroom teaching. And I think the thing that developed the most was probably just building relationships, building rapport with the pupils especially the high tariff ones. Just finding out what kind of what made them tick and building those relationships over time or earning their trust and respect and em So that's probably the thing that developed the most. probably I would have liked to have pushed my teaching on more, but I think in that environment, it is just about what's in front of you.

Interviewer: Uh-hmm.

Ross: So you maybe weren't doing as many all singing or dancing lessons.

Interviewer: Yeah.

Ross: Because the reality in an environment like that. You, you know you can plan whatever you want but if their still not out of the changing rooms 10 minutes in there and then something's happened and you have to deal with that and you're, you're juggling five or six things and that's just reality, I guess.... in a big, modern school like that.

Interviewer: Yeah. I would guess the priorities probably shift a little bit because you know actually getting them in the class changed is probably a really big achievement for some of them. That would be my guess from what I know about the school, I suppose.

Ross: Yes.

Interviewer: And what was your experience of--obviously PE sits within health and well-being--but what was your experience with the wider school in terms of health and well-being you hit on some there about building relationships and supporting young people who's perhaps are socially, economically you know come from that background of deprivation, but what was your experience of any wider health and well-being, stuff that was going on?

Ross: We were a faculty so we were linked with HE and so the ties weren't as good as they could be. I think that PT was just in the job that year. He was starting to kind of make it more cross curricular learning, so him and I started a morning activity club, like a Breakfast Club thing, and that, this year coming, will be linked with the HE department, so they'll be offering like healthy breakfasts at the same time as we're offering morning activities. And so really we started this as an activity club and it would have--if kids had said, "Oh can I get an apple? Can I get a flapjack or something, we would have been able to do it, but it never sort of picked up enough steam and then it just kind of... it was a good idea but I think it'll be sort of run a little bit better this time I think that everyone with the transition, there's just too much going on and it was like the first thing to sort of just like, "Oh, they're coming in playing badminton, and then playing basketball. They seem fine. They're happy. They're getting activity in the morning." [cross-talk]

Interviewer: Was that the PT of PE or...?

Ross: That was well yeah, he's the faculty leader.

Interviewer: Oh right, he's the faculty leader.

Ross: He is a PE teacher.

Interviewer: Right, OK.

Ross: So he did a lot of work developing the HE curriculum em and trying to... yeah... did loads and loads of good stuff, lots of good changes em that'll be running next year.

Interviewer: That's a good thing for you to talk about in your interviews isn't it?

Ross: Yeah. I try to [laughs]

Interviewer: [laughs] fingers crossed.

Ross: em wider school... it's hard. It's such a massive school, and they're so busy in the department and I would have liked to have gotten out a bit more, but again, the reality is, with clubs and observing and meetings and just real life.

Interviewer: Yeah, probably that cross curricular thing is probably about all you can manage, isn't it?

Ross: Mmm-hmm.

Interviewer: You know, you're... that connection's already there and you're probably going to meetings together... that's probably... I imagine can be quite challenging to get beyond that. How many kids were in the school?

Ross: 1350.

Interviewer: So yeah...

Ross: Decent size, yep.

Interviewer: oversubscribed, for that building, I can imagine.

Ross: Yes, yeah I think its about 200 over.... It certainly felt like it a lot of the time. [laughs]

Interviewer: "Is that thirty seven in the class? What's happening here?" [laughs] You may remember Louise, the English tutor from last year and we were talking about class sizes and the day just before she went on leave, and they were trying to convince me to have 45 in one of my classes, and I was just like--I can't have 45.

Ross: It's illegal

Interviewer: I know. I was like, let's not do that. And they were like, "Oh c'mon you can do it." And I'm like, "No, we can't." So that was I mean... got that all figured out, but yeah.

Ross: And the difference between 25 and 31 is--

Interviewer: Huge.

Ross: night and day for a practical subject.

Interviewer: I know. And I still can't get my head around why PE's not considered a practical subject, but...

Ross: I can't either One guy in my department said it was because they wanted to have, like, full-sized games of football, rugby and hockey, which I think is not a good enough reason... to reduce the teaching and learning quality

Interviewer: 22 or 24? Like that's okay

Ross: 24 is perfect. 33 is not perfect.

Interviewer: I know the... one of the local schools, are merging and I was talking to the PT about their design and stuff like that. And it's just--I can't get my head around how you justified sizes. It's like--

Ross: I was in the department there when [ross and Jennifer] were going to the meetings and they were saying, they were all just kind of fighting for space. Oh no they're giving us one games hall, but they're counting it as three teaching spaces, and then we've got a primary school in there and then we'll have an assisted support needs school in there and it's going to be like 1800 kids. I go to the gym with [ross] in Irvine

Interviewer: I think he's getting married on Friday isn't he?

Ross: Is he?

Interviewer: I think--

Ross: He got the job at [St. Matthews].

Interviewer: No way.

Ross: He went for that, yeah.

Interviewer: Wow.

Ross: So he's moving on. I know Laura's—it think Laura got that job.

Interviewer: Yeah.

Ross: So Laura's [inaudible]

Interviewer: I haven't seen Laura way after---they had one of her students this year and I haven't seen her in a while but no...

Ross: That's gonna be nuts.

Interviewer: Yeah. The reason I was thinking that Ross got married was 'cause of one our students from this year is good friends with Ross, I'm sure she said she was going to his wedding on Friday, 'cause it was graduation and then she was going to his wedding, but anyway, we digress. I want to maybe get back on to this idea of reflecting on your experiences and how they may have helped you or not, as the case may be, in your probationary, and more to this research that we've done so far from the focus group and the kinda survey and stuff suggested that most of our students felt prepared, when they left us, they were ready to go on and to take on their probationary year. And I'm just wondering, I should reflect back on that year, what are your views on your preparedness, are you feeling more ready, less ready, about the same, or you've got a different perspective on what readiness actually is, I guess, as you go through the year

Ross: I think that the post grad prepared us really, really well. You never really know until you start and obviously, Day 1 Lesson one is always a bit mental but, I think... yeah, especially the... I was talking to Joey about this, the team-teaching stuff that we did, the actual practical workshops, like getting your hands-on em kind of out of our comfort zones

with having to lead all range of activities. Also, like the mini workshops and CPDs that you had that you and [tutor] and other people come in and run for us. Like, I still use that stuff now. I think. And then, speaking with other people on other post-grads, I think we're kind of the gold standard for that, just cause that.. sitting in lecture, you're not really--that's not going to help you when you've got 33 kids in front of you. But having that experience of leading even your peers or being led by a netball specialist or you personally like that's the stuff that you practically remember as a PE teacher as you learn by doing, not by sitting and listening. So, having done a badminton warm-up and a little mini tig game and that leads on into something and sort of seeing how those really really good lessons work and run, you can just constantly put things and adapt things for your own teaching, so you didn't know how prepared you are, but I didn't feel unprepared at any point, and I think that you guys got us into really good habits in terms of how a really, really good lesson should look. Obviously, the reality in a big massive school, not every single lesson will look like that, I'm not going to lie, but you knew what it should look like, so you knew in the back of your mind, this should be happening and I need to try and get this done, we need to try and get to this destination, we might have to cut a wee but out here and there in order to get there, but you knew how you should be doing it. And I think that I did that as much as I could possibly could. I remember, letting my standards drop...

Interviewer: I think that's really interesting to think about... there's been a lot of time this year. Obviously, in my first year as programme leader, spending more time with other subjects and talking about what their doing and how they get to that point of that you know, the gold standard and what we're aiming for and it's... and interesting to hear you say that you're pulling that information from the practical workshops and still taking some of it and adapting it and using it, one of the things that kind of stood out and semi-connected to this is there seemed to be some sort of missing link between some of theoretical stuff you mentioned lectures there and some of the students in this study--and I'm not sure if you have this particular view--but suggesting that perhaps some of the lectures or the more theoretical things seem to be disconnected to what was going on in school. And I'm wondering if that still seems to be the case for you, or if it was never the case for you, or if you're not really sure of it... just this idea of theory maybe not matching up to what the reality of school is.

Ross: I think that is accurate but you kinda see that everywhere in education, that what's coming out from the SQA or the Scottish government, there seems to be a real disconnect between what they want teachers to be doing on a day to day basis, and what's actually happening in schools. So, with CfE or SALS or the new benchmarks, seems like there's something new coming out every two years. So you're seeing experienced teachers and you're coming in fresh-faced and "All right, guys! What are we doing for SALS." And they're like, it's just another acronym... we've seen this it's gonna come and go. I remember a teacher saying, like, "My lesson six basketball lesson is the same as it was 10 years ago, it's going to be the same 10 years from now." And it's a niggle and its quite bad but you can also see why they say that, because they've seen things come and go and they're probably bored of it with someone saying... someone in Edinburgh sitting round a table, saying "Right. This is what we want you to do." And you know in two years time, they're going to say, "Oh, that's not working. Here's a new thing." So I suppose... at uni it was kind of the same thing and I'm quite pragmatic but you guys are the lecturers, they need to be telling you about

policy and all the stuff coming down from the government and telling you about that stuff 'cause they'd be doing you a disservice if they didn't. And they can't sort of say like, "Oh, guys... the reality is totally different to this. So don't worry about this. You guys are going to see what's actually like in the school." Like, they have to be telling what they expect and what the expectations are. So I think there's always going to be that disconnect until the people writing the policy are as closely connected to people who are actually teaching as possible.

Interviewer: Yeah, because I can imagine that--you were talking about that story there about basketball lessons staying the same. Basketball hasn't really changed. But what has changed since I guess the lense through which were delivering it so it's like. We used to just teach basketball because we wanted to teach our kids to play basketball. And then it became about they need to learn about teamwork and communication and then it became, well, actually, we need them to understand sport education and the cooperation and now it's like, well, how do we teach numeracy through basketball? And you're just... I think the lens changes a lot, but I think your colleague is right in saying that actually basketball hasn't changed. We still deliver it in the same way but...

Ross: it comes down to teaching philosophy, we had a lot of discussions / arguments [laughs] look into the SALs and profiles and stuff and some teachers, they got into PE teaching because they like sport and coaching and their in there to get the kids better at doing a handstand, whereas someone like me's coming in and has been told skills are as important as a social factor as developing them mentally, as developing them emotionally. Argue, em like my favourite thing was yeah they've all failed higher but they are really nice people like ... that's it. You're developing the whole person. It doesn't actually matter if someone's really really good at basketball. It matters if they're able to work in the team and cooperate and they're mentally well-adjusted, and deal with success and failure really really well and they know how to build up skills and progress themselves. Being good at basketball's not that important in life

Interviewer: Yeah, unless you're going to go be a basketball player which most of us are not.

Ross: Yeah, that's right... it's very narrow, so.... but yeah, I can absolutely understand why an experienced PE Teacher would be like, "Well, I'm not worried about how they deal mentally, emotionally. We'll talk about that when they get Nat 5 and Higher. I want to them to be able to actually play the game." So you can see both sides of it.

Interviewer: I know, it's a bit of tough one... with your placement experience different--well obviously, the different schools that you went, but kind of keeping that idea of. was that the experience of the staff that you worked with on the placement, in terms of did they have similar views or different views.

Ross: It's a mixture. All departments are different and Loudoun (Tommy) it was all... all of those guys were really sort of up-to-the-minute on what was happening and that tommy worked really closely, he does a lot of curriculum development and always has super high standards... so it was great working there, because he was singing from the same handbook as you were and everyone at Uni was, so it was like, "OK, this is how it should look" and

lesson plans, everything, was really, really prepared. And then, auchinleck, just the reality, it was different. It was about being adaptable, and that's really tricky at first, going from somewhere where I always got to deliver the lesson I planned, everything was really really good, structured, and then you are two members of staff down and it was just about right, "Let's get them in. Let's get them moving. Lets you know... just do something because you're not going to be able to teach that gymnastic lesson. We're all going to go into the hall, you're going to go outside with a group and do football, and then they're going to stay inside to play dodge ball. "And it's like, "Oh, but I have this planned." It doesn't matter what you got planned. You've got 70 kids here and two teachers, so...

Interviewer: And you're like, "This would have been awesome."

Ross: Yeah. [laughs]

Interviewer: Do you think those can two.. I guess, there were probably quite opposite experiences, do you think that--or how do you think they contributed to your preparedness and just survive your year at Greenwood?

Ross: Yeah, they worked really really well together weirdly it wasn't em neither were very easy experiences because at Loudoun, it was always, "I'd never had a good lesson. Even when I had a good lesson." It was hyper-critical because they were trying to make you the absolute best, so even when something was all singing all dancing, they would still find seven things and say, "You need to do this, you need to do that." And it's like, "Oh, I thought I was really good." But it never was so that was really good because it just dragged me up as high as it possibly could in that time. And then... auchinleck, it was just a reality. It was you have a really really good plan A, but you also have to have plan B, and then also plan C. If it's raining and two members of staff down and this kicks off and that's happened and so and so doesn't have his kit and you know they decide to do a class play on that day and you have to just be able to think on your feet. So I got very very good at that, just having lessons in my head, doesn't matter what I had in a nice little folder. It was right, what's going to work for this group. And again that is the pupil relationships. It was finding out right... we tried Danish longball with this lot and they absolutely hated it, or they love football but if you do football two lessons in a row, then they'd just get bored after, and then just start knocking around and kicking each other up in the air. So [laughs] it's true... so it's just learning reality, so it prepared me really really well, because greenwood is a mix and when it was my classes, my BGE I was able to pretty much consistently deliver what I wanted and it was really nice to kind of having that control, of being able to building those routines and seeing my ideas work mostly in the long-term, but then also when it came to like dropped down into core and formative development, you had to be really adaptable and what... there's tons of choice and personalization agreements, too much actually. They've taken a lot of it out, because it caused a lot of problems with every second block, or actually, two or three blocks, in third and fourth year, they were just there to choose, "Here's the activities and see here what your choices are..." Gymnastics. Fitness. Football, etc. and then people just kind of go to that area, they get re-registered and that causes a lot of wasted time and then people get bored after two weeks and they want to go with their pal there or something like that or they don't like the teacher. So, you just have to be really really adaptable. You just have to work together and communicate.

Interviewer: I suppose it's maybe about redefining what choices and personalization is because I had a really a long conversation with some primary teachers about how they can do something like that, because obviously they've only got their one primary class and maybe a stage partner they could offer some choices I suppose. We ended up talking about whether allowing which benchmark they focused on that day was that enough for personalization and choice? And they were like 'oh I don't know' so they're going through those struggles right now. "How do we get that personalization and choice" But its nice to hear that I guess, secondary school has gone through that they're working on something that's practical and actually allows... to get what the teachers want, what the students want and hopefully, what the government wants, but no one really knows about that. But no, it's quite interesting but I think in primary they are feeling a big push to offer personalisation and choice in PE and it's tough. When you've got one space, it's also the dinner hall and it's also the stage...

Ross: Again, it's just the reality of it. So it was good. And then my experience at greenwood as well was kind of a mixture, so that made me... I know what a lesson should look like but I'm also pragmatic enough to know that in certain classes, certain pupils on... with certain weather conditions... that's not just gonna be practical. So you have to have contingencies and just being able to think on your feet and throw something together at last-minute so you're not... I've had lessons where it was so fragmented because something happened and you know if you've got ten minutes of indoor football at the end, it was success because of four or five things all happening and just someone would call in sick first thing in the morning and then you adapt to the reality. So you've got to be good at just thinking on your feet and never just let it get to you.

Interviewer: I've only got two more questions and kind of trying to now look forward to, 'cause obviously you're going forward to the early phase of your career and what I'm interested in is really this idea of health and well-being. We know that PE sits within health and well-being but also that we have the responsibility of all concept there and how prepared do you feel to contribute to health and well-being, either through PE or through the wider school or both?

Ross: Em Through clubs and initiatives, very prepared. I would like there to be more focus on Nutrition and that's something with the Diet Fitness class at greenwood with. Unfortunately, the diet was all handled in HE so there was never really that connection. Like that course had a lot of potential but the fitness side of it was just kind of fitness testing, developing a program and kind of going for it like that quite linearly... and I think if you had much more connection you'd be able to talk about energy systems, talk about... you know teaching about proper nutrition and how that's linked to... that's gonna impact your performance--and it's something, I'm surprised, isn't a bigger part of PE ... just seeing the way kids prepare for their one-off performance. And they're having a chip roll before their one-off and it's like, "How do you not realize that that's a bad thing to do?" But it's not actually in our remit. That's all to say, you know, "You shouldn't be having sugary drinks and all that" type of thing.

Interviewer: I wonder... well where that remit sits then ? Because I agree wholeheartedly. We used to stand in the corridor at Dunoon, they'd come around the door by us from break and we'd be like, "Nope, you're not--" because they had a "no sugary drink" policy but if it doesn't sit within PE, where does it sit? Is that part of the responsibility of all, I don't know... but yeah, I don't know how we fix that problem moving forward.

Ross: Wider curriculum, I did loads of stuff with the SALs, or how to implement the SALs and the benchmarks... so yeah, you're trying to implement health and well-being through those so not so much focusing on physical well-being but social well-being is massive. Just teaching good communication and then it's simple for a lot of people through sport em with the lot of collaborative learning em forcing them to give quality feedback to each other is quite a mature task, which you don't really realize until you have them do it, and then you ask them to share their feedback. "Oh it was good right?" Why was it good? And it's like... blood from the stones sometime, but you can tell that they've never had to do that before so it's building those social skills which again I think is much more important than being able to do a really good forward roll... to be able to talk to peer and give them critical feedback in terms of how they did. So hopefully, that sort of building the wider person and again, a big big school is hard to sort of see the impact of that kind of has outside of the department.

Interviewer: And...we were talking--we spent a lot of time with our third years, talking about how the things that are kind of not outwith your teaching but they're just part of your daily practices, like you know, registering people and how you talk to them when they come into the class and how that can contribute to health and well-being and I guess, if you don't get that across the school, then it's almost like you have that impact for that one lesson but then they go get something else elsewhere and so I don't know how we get... I don't think that's our role

Ross: Yeah, and it's... I've felt... bad for the kids who walked around trying to give out consent form for a football game or something, and you walk through the corridors and hear the teacher roaring at them or just being rude and quite unreasonable and it's like, they get a pretty nice time when they come to the PE department. We're respectful and friendly even if you don't get it back, and my mentor, whose quite big, we talked a lot about young male relationships, and probably the biggest thing I learned, if you talked a lot about how these young guys, they're not comfortable with another young man being respectable and nice and reasonable to them because all they've known is confrontation. So they're uncomfortable, with it being a normal conversation. So to make themselves comfortable, they make it a confrontation. So they'll just start an argument because they're comfortable arguing with someone. They're not comfortable talking with someone. And that was like the biggest light bulb moment for me this year. I was like, "Oh, right, so, they want to make you confrontational." So then my job was how can I keep then doing what I wanted to be doing at that time without it being me versus them. So that was like a whole different way of behavior management... just waiting for two people to do something so that I can say, "You two stop that." instead of "You stop that." Because then it's me versus you, and then everything stops, and it's right, "Who's going to win this battle?"

Interviewer: And I suppose the underpinning part of that is that they're trying to keep themselves emotionally safe for that's how they've seen it as being like, we want to try and really interesting

Sean: There's a lot of angry young people in schools. Not just men. There's a lot of angry young ladies walking around, and again, it's the same thing. You see it, when they would just create a situation for themselves for the attention and it's really sad actually. It's like, "I don't want to be giving you that type of attention." Like, I'd like to be talking to you like just treating you like a normal human being. I don't want to be getting into trouble, but you're used to that being the only attention that you get eh at home or in the community. So, just like, "You don't need to be so angry. You're in a safe place. We're all gonna be really nice to you here. We just want you to be happy and safe. You don't have to kick off."

Interviewer: And now, again, that comes back to the idea you said there, that almost supercedes everything else.

Sean: Yeah, exactly.

Interviewer: We need you to get to a point where you feel safe and that we can have a positive relationship and that may be our only success and probably the biggest success we have in the the year I suppose in some ways that's where PE becomes much more about health and well-being, in that context, because it does supercede the teaching of the gymnastics or whatever else is going on. My final question really is just kind of a catch-all and is there anything else, when you think about the key words that we've talked about, which are preparedness, moving forward... preparedness. Last year, I guess reflecting on that health and well-being, PE, these are all the key words for the research and just thinking about the main factors that contribute to all those things there. Is there anything else that really stood out for you or really had a huge impact or didn't have any impact at all that you wanted to kind of... to share, in terms of... the topic that we've been really kind of trying to investigate--I'm trying to investigate, you're just doing the talking.

Ross: I guess, in terms of what we cover in university, I think the thing I was not prepared for was the pupil relationship side. I think that's something that could be focused on more. You know every area is different but every school is gonna have... there's more challenging pupils, and I think that that is... I've talked with the other teachers and other probationers, that's probably the thing that they felt unprepared for... was behavior management and building relationships, dealing with conflict and confrontation. I think people coming from more experience working with children or coaching backgrounds, so most, post-graduate PE teachers. We've got experience working with children and sort of dealing with those tricky situations more than maybe a maths teacher does that's coming from Uni and... so that was the feedback that I remember and that's just experience, but maybe sort of workshops you could do, like role-playing with the whole cohort I think would be really valuable--even fun, but it would also you know help give people ideas to sort of avoid confrontations, deal with conflict, to deal with different situations--I think that would have been really really valuable for us, but probably even more so for people outside PE cohort just to give them experience of dealing with tricky teenagers and mental situations.

Interviewer: You can have a lot of fun pretending to be a bit of an angry teenager. No, that's really quite interesting that.

Ross: And just sharing ideas, because everyone's got different ways of approaching things. People who approach with humor, some people would be, like trying to rule it with an iron fist, and just seeing what worked and what didn't, and then having you guys there to say, "This was really good." or give ideas to people and just kind of give you lots of tools, 'cause that was the stuff that... you have to observe, experience teacher's doing. And then classroom teachers, have a totally different way of dealing with things to like a practical subject like us you'd be able to sit someone out. Or you don't really want to sit someone out so then how do you do that? Do you change their team, so you make them work with someone the don't really wanna work with? All sorts of different stuff... and it's more of moving parts with a practical subject you know an English teacher can just send them outside and then go and talk to them outside in the corridor.

Interviewer: And it's a very clear cut way

Ross: We don't really have that if we are out on the astroturf... or you know, we are doing a cross-country run. So where do you send them?. So it's that... it's having those tools and just sort of watching what other people do, seeing how other people deal with different personalities and different pupils, learning what works, learning what doesn't. So that's one of the biggest thing--that's something that I think a lot of teachers felt unprepared for. And then some people just--they don't have the experience of working with difficult people or dealing with difficult situations like that, like working at summer camps and stuff gives you lots of experience for that then working at a really nice American summer camp that doesn't really prepared you for the realities of East Ayrshire.

Interviewer: Yeah, I guess that's probably... yes, there will be some issues, but they're probably different issues.

Ross: so and so used my hairbrush isn't quite the same as You know, "I didn't get any breakfast this morning. My dad left I stayed at my aunts Yeah, just the worst stuff.

Interviewer: OK, great. Well, that's everything that I had to kind of talk about and I'll be looking and discussing similar topics with the rest of the guys that are coming in today. And then I'll be almost done with my PhD and I think... I'm trying to remember if it was you that suggested during the focus group, but I can't exactly remember. I had it in my head that you had suggested that... last year, one of the things that we did with the teaching task was that we aligned them with Mosstons teaching sales, and I can't remember if it was you or if it was just the group that kind of suggested that but...

Ross: I remember something about...

Interviewer: Yeah.

Ross: Or forcing you to do a certain teaching style.

So we did that last year and so I'm about to have my focus group with this year's students, so I'm quite interested to see how they thought, or what they thought about that... and because we give them--basically, we give them three to pick from and they had to use it with just one within every lesson they did it was--for me, you people are like, "how's your PhD going" and I'm like why, "It's brilliant because it's just giving me new ideas for what I'm gonna do every year with my students." So... and... it's quite interesting to see what they've got to say in the focus group

[end]

Appendix 10: Focus Group Transcript with Analysis

Excerpt of Focus Group Transcript with Analysis

Group – Class of 2015
Location – AYR

Moderator – LK
June 2015

Initial Noting Key

Highlighting = text viewed as interesting during initial noting

Underlining = text viewed as important during further re-reading

Comments (in text boxes) = offer initial thoughts, followed by commentary on potential meaning and interpretations

Colour code of themes = (NB not all themes are present in this excerpt)

Influence of Context
Reflections / Reflective Practice
Influence of Experiences
Networking / Support / Relationships
Placement
Preparation
Subject Knowledge

1 M: What's the thing that will stay with you over the next year?

2

3 S: Erm ... **the placements** ...

4

5 M: Is there anything particular about the placements, or
6 particular about the placements or that we are generally
7 applying...?

8

9 S: Just the **relationships** that you build with the pupils and staff
10 **who are there**

11

12 C: I think how fast and furious, it all was. I mean, when you're
13 out on placement. If you're in university then **you're learning of a**
14 **board and how to apply that in class. Then they actually go out of**
15 **school to try and put that theory into practice, it's just a whole**
16 **other ball game.** It's so fast and furious when you've got a full
17 class in front of you. So just little **lightbulb ideas** come back to
18 you. **So you would like to probably bring more from university**
19 but the actual dealing with class management control and

Placements value linked to
relationships

Interwoven with **reflections**
differences between learning on
campus and apply learning to
practice on **placement**

Implies the two types of learning
are very different

Nature of placement means you
can't always take learning from
university into placement

20 behaviour management was actually in practice rather than
21 sitting hearing about via lecture

22

23 M: Is that what you meant?

24

25 S: Yeah, yeah. There's only so much you can take in when
26 somebody's talking to you or saying oh this is how I did it

27

28 Mu: I think for me the thing I'll take from the course is the type
29 of teacher that you're aspiring to be. Because it's still of course
30 about being on placement in schools. You know all the staff,
31 some young, some old, some are set in their ways but speaking
32 for myself I have had a very positive experience through the
33 course and kind of presented a new challenge for us made a new
34 experience for us. I actually feel quite confident as experienced
35 teachers have been taking the course.

36

37 M: And how prepared do you feel for your probation year?

38

39 Mu: I'm looking forward to it. Looking forward to getting to being
40 my own teacher. As when you are on placement you kind of only
41 there for a small segment and they are fixed in their routines
42 which you don't want to disrupt so you are just kind of there as a
43 kind of privilege so I am looking forward to being able to have
44 my own classes

45

46 M: Talking about privilege, is that how you feel?

47

48 Mu: Not really but I felt like I was there. Obviously, they were,
49 had let me come into the school to do my bit for a few weeks as
50 opposed to me actually being at the school to have positive
51 change for pupils. I was in a kind of there just as an add on.

52

53 M: Was that the nature of the placement for all of you?

54

55 C: Yeah, I'd agree with that. I feel as if the school had kind of let
56 us come into the school so I want to obviously watch their
57 practice and trying to put the practice into place rather than
58 come in and have an impact. Or a bit like Murray says when you
59 go into a class and you've got a supporting teacher you end up
60 almost becoming a version of them. You don't actually get to
61 know your own style of teaching. Because you are out on
62 placement to go and be a student.

63

Limit to learning with the ability to apply on **placement** and **reflecting** on own **experiences**

Despite taking something significant from the course **placement** are still central esp. **staff**

Confidence linked to **experience** of tutors on the course

Probation see as a **context** for becoming the kind of teacher they want to be

Challenges of **placement**

Development influenced by the **context**

Socialisation impacts development and learning in this **context**

Development limited by the **context** of placement

64 S: And they are obviously going to have to take them afterwards
65 so you don't want to disrupt what they have put in place, their
66 routines, their kind of way

67

68 M: How long were your placements?

69

70 Mu: The longest was 6 weeks. Then 5 weeks and 5 weeks.

71

72 M: Because you both said again that you feel like you've not
73 been your own kind of teacher yet but now you get a chance too

74

75 C: You definitely sample becoming a teacher but I'm looking
76 forward to my probation year where I can start to mould my own
77 teaching style. Sometimes you don't really want to push too far
78 outside the box as obviously we've got observing teachers in
79 every lesson you so you know what it's like you're not that
80 comfortable making mistakes.

81

82 M: So you play safe?

83

84 C: You play safe, yeah. So next year when you actually have your
85 own class and you can go off on your own tangents and
86 someone's not watching you, it feels like, much more
87 comfortable and I can actually put that stamp on it.

88

89 M: You were going to say something?

90

91 S: I think that example is a good example of what type of teacher
92 you want to be. I got to try out loads of my ideas and I was like
93 'this is the way I want to do it.' I was quite open to that. I don't
94 really want to fall over the other teachers and what they were
95 doing. I wanted to do my own thing and they were quite open to
96 that.

97

98 M: So perhaps a different way of learning then? Did you
99 experience that?

100

101 Mu: I think placement one, it might just be a reflection on the
102 school, but they more let me do it and allowed me to get on with
103 it. But [placement] 2 and 3 were in the same school, which was
104 more kind of, I don't want to stay dominant staff members but
105 more kind of assertive. They had been there a longer but kind of
106 set in their ways. All the feedback from them as well was kind of
107 encouraging me to be more like what they wanted you to do just

Placement provides opportunity to try being a teacher

Value attached to perceived opportunity to develop own style in probation

Challenges of placement - perceived pressure

Viewed as being more comfortable and able to develop and try new things without perceived pressure of observing teacher

Variation in experiences influence on development

Feedback was targeted to views of what the school wanted

Implied that not necessarily what they wanted to do or what the university wanted you to do

108 cause that's what they are used to that's what the kids are used
109 to that's the way they see as being the right way even though eh
110 but I don't mean that it was a negative experience, I got a lot out
111 it

112

113 C: You are just very aware that they are giving you a pass or a fail
114 at the end. So you don't want to really upset the apple cart too
115 much. Although you would love to go and try all your ideas you
116 just know they are quite set in their ways so you don't want to
117 come and start

118

119 M: So, do you feel you haven't tried a lot of things yet?

120

121 C: It's not that not trying but not trying with full confidence of if
122 this goes wrong it's not going to be recorded so it'll be nice to try
123 a new idea and new methods and almost a bit of free reign

124

125 M: What about yourself?

126

127 S: Both schools would let me, as ~~murray~~ said placement 1 and
128 placement 2 and 3 were all similar for me in terms of the class
129 teachers were like go and do what you need to do. Erm, they
130 gave me feedback if it worked or it didn't and some feedback I
131 took and I accepted but other feedback I said 'I don't agree' and
132 sometimes I kept that in my head because I don't agree for
133 certain reasons

134

135 M: And what kind of reasons were they? Is it the things that you
136 have been taught here that maybe don't necessarily aren't seen
137 as what's in school?

138

139 S: I think what we are learning here on the course, I certainly
140 believe it's the way education should be especially in PE. But
141 there's a lot of older teachers which I think is holding back the
142 full implementation of curriculum for excellence

143

144 C: If you were in with a teacher who was more recently out of
145 training, they were more open to ideas to CfE ideas. Whereas if
146 you got a more traditional teacher you were more reluctant to
147 go with the new concepts.

Despite room for improvement
placement experience still
valued highly

Feelings of not being able to try
things out linked to their success
on course – fear of failure?

Not fully confident when trying
things when observed –
experiencing perceived pressure

Value of Feedback from School
Staff – Reflection on what was
useful or not

Challenges of placement -
Negotiating being a student
teacher

Reflection on curriculum –
including HWB?

Reluctance to try to implement
experiences from university
learning

Appendix 11: Full Focus Group Transcript

Focus Group – Class of 2016 (1)
Location – GLA

Moderator - GS
July 2016

The first section of focus group transcript has been removed as the personal and professional history revealed here might compromise anonymity. The final section has also been omitted as the conversation veered off-topic, as the focus group reached its close.

Moderator: Right, you've been asked to recall the experiences in your initial teacher education. The results will be analyzed and used for the exploration of the themes from the survey and contribute towards PhD research. You were selected because you have experience with ITE program. So the guidelines are there are no right or wrong answers, only different points of view. You don't need to agree with others but you must listen respectfully as others share their views. The intention is that you will interact with each other but will be willing to listen to all views. Okay, tape recording, one person speaking at a time. Please turn off mobile phones so as not to interrupt recording. My role as moderator will be to guide the discussion as we work through the questions. All information discussed at this focus group is confidential and should remain that way after the focus groups. No discussing with other people, especially those in other focus groups. Specifics support or instances is extremely helpful within the discussion. We need to ensure confidentiality and thus generic terms should be used to describe people in schools. So the structure as an introductory question will take about 5 minutes, the discussion expansion frames, from the questionnaire that you guys filled out. We'll then have a short break and then finish up with the final question. So introductory question and see when you answer them, if you use your pseudonym. And would you like to see what stood out for you during your ITE last year?

Rachel: I thought PE was a good experience em [long pause]

Moderator: Anything specific about them?

Rachel: I thought all of them were very well organized. As soon as you went in there was something on the board for you to do. And we covered quite a lot, the only thing for me in covering quite a lot it was quite ... There's no other way we can do that so they couldn't change it, but for example we went over gymnastics and it was quite a lot you were covering and I remembering asking how long would you take to do that lesson and I can't remember if it was [tutor] or [tutor] but one of them said that's a block within two hours But it was quite -- for me, it was a wee bit more difficult so individual lessons then how would you actually set that out? but there's no another way you do it, they've no got time to do it so it's understandable

Carlos: One of the things that really stood out for me was how fast the year went by like we were busy from the first day to the last day and one of the things that was kinda memorable is how fast it goes by it literally feels like we just started the course, it doesn't seem that long ago that you got your confirmation to get on the course and then before you know it you are in your probation year em so for me the real stand out thing is that time is very very

important within that year erm and it just felt like the fastest quickest year of my life and I suppose that's cause it was enjoyable as well kinda gonna talk about what Rachel said there as well erm PE was brilliant I think the PE side of it was really good as well probably achieved as much as we could within the timeframe erm it's very difficult to write a course in a year to get us all through and get us prepared for teaching within one year post grad I would image is a very very tough remit for anyone to fulfil and with that in mind I just think we were as busy as we could have been throughout the year and that is probably why it felt so fast

Phoebe: I think the thing the thing that stood out for me most was just placements, like I think you always knew how hard placements were going to be, but you can't really explain what they are like, until you are actually on placement I think it's like when you're on placement is such a steep learning curve. If I think back to the first placement and the last placement the difference in the way I was... so just placements in general

Jonas: For me I just think when Carlos was talking about the whole PE course and the time erm I thought that everything was well organized but the people who actually took it for you, were really relaxed but made you do the work at the same time, so for me I felt like I was never scared. I could always ask questions and I think erm if you ever had any queries you could just ask

Moderator: Anyone want to add anything to that?

Keith: Like Carlos was saying it is constant. Since we did it with just the one year rather than the four years there's a lot to cram into that one year and there is going to be parts of the course that maybe you didn't have a chance to delve in as much depth as you potentially would have liked erm. but overall the course obviously what we received was a good overall and it ticked all the bases and it was more a case of us being more independent to maybe have more time eh looking at something or trying to learn more content for a certain activity so a lot of it goes on us erm on the placements as well. I think obviously the placements are eh invaluable you probably learned more in one week of a placement that you did in a couple months sometimes actually at uni, well I thought that I don't know about anyone else but eh I thought the placements were definitely the most valuable thing you could have had and having different schools as well it even just showed how vast and how two different schools can do things in a completely different way. Erm So it kinda open your eyes a little bit as well...

Moderator: So just before we move on to the main sort of questions is there anything that will stay with you as you enter your probationary year

Joseph: probably just more experiences on placement eh just when I first started just seeing the level I was at and then even after one placement the observation placement where you only took a few lessons the improvement and you felt more confident going back to uni taking lessons within class there, erm as the placement went on you were again seeing progression in yourself and the rest of the class as well

Moderator: The first main theme is preparation so we will move on to those questions now. In the survey the participants rated their level of preparation as 4 out of 5 for

beginning their probationary year. What factors do you think contribute to this rating of perceived preparedness?

Chandler: I think going to back to what everyone has said placements are huge. It's all fine and dandy someone saying to you, this is how it would look in the classroom, and this is how it should go, this is how you should deal with this but until you're actually out there and can actually deal with it, then you're not really as prepared as you could be. Until something actually happens you don't actually know how you're going to react and how the class is going to react to a behaviour issue or the way you're delivering something, so I think being on placement is probably one of the reasons why I'm so ready you look at first day on placement to last day on placement every single one of us has improved massively, because of being on placement and learning stuff like that...

Monica: I think I'm feeling prepared about starting probation. Quite possibly because of the network I've built as well so I'm like no matter what I go into, I can get in touch with anybody on the course that has specialities or get in touch with the years above because of the mentoring programme and things like that, so even the schools that I've been in on placements 1, 2 and 3, I know I can get in touch with these departments and they will be more than happy to help so networking has definitely been something that has helped me be prepared from probation.

Carlos: I feel that you couldn't ever be fully prepared, you can put five out of five prepared, but because it is such a short time as chandler said certain things will creep up there's probably teachers that will be teaching for five ten years that are still learning and they are being better prepared for situations so I did put 4 out of 5 for that one as well and I just felt that we have been really really well prepared in the time that we have had. Of course we could be more prepared, you can always be more prepared but in the time that we have had 4 out of 5 is a really good effort

Moderator: Is there anyone who perhaps doesn't feel as prepared for starting their probation year?

Keith: Personally for me one of the things that I feel less prepared for is the certificated classes erm I think that a lot of it could depend on how you get on with your placements if they're willing to give you those classes, like Nat 5 and higher and give you that experience with those classes to be honest, I didn't get much of a chance, when I was in the last two placements just because the guy who was taking the class was he was really stressed out, so he didn't then want to pass that on and they had a probationer before but they didn't do a very good job, so they were catch up. So I totally understood that and so personally for me maybe you wanted to my probation year now it's one of the things I would not say I'm nervous about but its probably one of those things I maybe need to, maybe have a bit more direction a bit more help with and so I know there are obviously people who were given the Nat 5 given higher and stuff like that and given the opportunity to do that erm I feel reasonably confident in the course and taking the classes, but for me just now I think that's one of the things that I need to definitely kind of have a bit brush up. Looking for more content trying to figure out how to structure the class and lessons and stuff

Phoebe: I would have to agree with Keith. When I was in placement I didn't get as much opportunity to take certificated classes as some other people have. so in that sense I am probably less prepared than those people and would need help and the other thing is, I've been given classes that didn't even run in the school during previous placement

Moderator: Example of those courses?

Phoebe: I am having to do uniform services. It's running with a Sport and Rec, sports leaders focus and they are kind of putting the two courses together so For example uniform services I don't have experience of that anywhere so it was just a case of getting a few contacts and trying to work it out

Moderator: So do you guys think then that, that's something that could be introduced later on in the course things like sports leaders or the kind of vocational qualifications that are available

Jonas: I don't know if they could but maybe change the placement dates because when you were given that certificated or senior phase and I went in and they were all doing practice for their one offs so you are basically walking in and watching people play sport. I'm also the same the same as Phoebe and I'm taking sport and rec class that I've never been prepared for, I'm taking some other classes that I have not been prepared for either, so certificated classes is something that I maybe wish there was more emphasis

Moderator: And so just to clarify most small will say that most of you feel prepared for getting out there but for certificated classes that's the main thing that you would like more time. School placement and experiences and subjects studies are both described as stand out experiences by participants in the survey would you say one stood over the other...

Joseph: I haven't really thought about it but I would say that subject studies helped you within the placement. So its kinda hard to say if one stood out over the other subject studies contributed to having good school experience and I wouldn't say one stood out over the other I did enjoy that we covered a lot of sports in subject studies that I hadn't took part in before or taught so it was great to have that experience to take into schools but I wouldn't say that there was a difference between the both of them

Moderator: Was there any of the activities that you learned about in PE studies class in Uni that you then used on placement? Any examples?

Keith: one of the major tones for me was volley ball was one of the ones that I never had any experience before and we had quite a bit of input from that on the subject studies. So that helped me out a lot when I went to the first placement because I had a lot of classes doing on the block. That gave me a lot of options to look at, certain practices and looking at what I could implement , the first lessons I had actually prepared for the classes, I had to rip up with two seconds because I look at the class are I realized that I had quite a high perceived ability but actually the class were nowhere near that, so I mean it was still good to have the content and all the knowledge, but we would have never had, it would not really have matter when I went to the classes as I had to change it, so I had to think in my feet

what I could actually do to get the class to have some level of success. But it did help me in terms of getting some content but like every class will be different so I think the school experience overall was maybe more important, because everything can be really good as we obviously had some really good lessons when we were in subject studies, so we taught each other and had some amazing lessons that were actually fantastic to watch and be a part of but when it comes to a school experience, there's so many different factors that come into behaviour management, facilities, class size, so there was maybe 15 of us in subject studies class but the lessons have a class of 30, so there's a lot of things to think about that practically wouldn't work in a classroom setting on school experience, so I found out a lot sorta the hard way cause there were a couple of times where I have tried lessons they just fell apart cause the kids just weren't at that level yet erm

Carlos: I'd echo Joseph there the two subject complement each other There's things you would see in the subject studies that you would take it straight into placement and so I would say they both connect and complement each other quite well. The biggest thing for me was gymnastics as that was something I didn't have a lot of experience myself some to do it myself. It's also quite a dangerous thing to teach so having the extra emphasis on that I think was a definite positive and that is something that I took from what [tutor] had organised this year.

Moderator: So just going back to what you said obviously having to change your lessons and adapt would you say that from what you did with the Volleyball for example in the subject studies you were able to adapt and made you feel more prepared for going in to teach it?

Joseph: I think that it was definitely relevant I did use basically everything that was taught within the subject studies, I just need to adapt it to a certain level and obviously the hours we had gave us the tools to do that it was more personally with me probably taking what we learned in our subject studies and thought right that's what the level that they are at. because I think that from the area I think area is quite big on volley ball and they play to quite a high standard and that is just maybe expected that level from the kids I was teaching, but they were completely different erm no but I was able to use definitely the stuff from subject studies.

Monica: I think that the trampolining course that more we done this year, was beyond valuable for me, because the schools are doing it and you had to have the qualification to teach it, so it opened a door for me in that perspective but em but perhaps the content of the trampoline course wasn't as specific to teaching it was more the coaching side and that affected the content the ports wasn't the teaching it was more coaching and I only know now the difference between teaching and coaching in terms of how you are and so it may be needs to be relooked at just slightly. Although it was a teacher tailored course it wasn't entirely on how to bring in certain things about a teacher, but as an element to that sport..

Moderator: So with the coach led stuff were you able to put the teacher slant on it when you went out to placement and see how other teachers were able to use it

Monica: Yeah, I managed to take into broad general classes as well as higher classes, but it was because of the content and knowing stuff and being able to use the correct terminology

like in the coaching side, but have the teacher side as well but having it as an additional part of the course, I know it was like optional but I strongly advise people to do it because you have to have the qualification to teach it

Chandler: Just going back to what Keith was saying earlier with lessons not going well I think all of the stuff we covered in subject studies gave you that chance that if a lesson went in the tank then you could always look back at what we did with volleyball and then you could pick things out, so you can go in with a brilliant lesson and you think this is going to work and you pick things from here and there and you think its going to work but it doesn't ... because you covered it in subject studies you can think back and you can just think of something on your feet and I think the more content knowledge you have the easier it is to do that. So looking at subject studies stuff really helped with that.

Monica: On the flip side of that though I wouldn't been able to look back at my first volleyball lesson and remember so I think we have been lucky this year as someone on our course has been injured so they scribed a lot of the time and so he's got notes on it with adaptations and progression but if you didn't have that I am really bad at remembering what we had done on week whatever so even just having some sort of scribe to just quickly write down the progression and then share the copy with everyone

Rachel: I agree with Monica as when we were doing stuff I kept running to the side to write things down as I don't learn just from experiencing it, if I have it there and I'm reading it I'll be like oh right I remember it now because I did experience it but em but yeah having someone there to do that and then copying all the notes and giving them was far better ... cause I couldn't I put it down as a weakness for me that I can't think on the spot if somethings not going that well and I know its cause my content isn't really good I don't think that's necessarily got anything to do with the course I just need to develop that in the future but I would struggle

Moderator: Do you think that part of it could be that a resource bank is developed from the beginning right through, is that what you are saying?

Rachel: We did that Chandler made up at drop box but from what we do in uni I didn't necessarily ... see for example if I was teaching basketball I didn't look back on my notes I didn't think back to what we did in basketball at uni and take it from there I would go on the internet or I would ask somebody that did basketball like [student name] erm but for a lot of it I wouldn't necessarily look back on what we did

Joey: Just go back to when it came to lessons and adapting things it think that what Rachel was saying about thinking on your feet I think it is quite erm one of those things where you have go to be quite confident with the actual activity that you are teaching and just being confident to try things and if it isn't working out ... it just comes with the experience I think and you might not know something really well like a particular activity but there's something to be done ... like class that's not working I've got to change this somehow and then just maybe try something that doesn't relate to the game, but so that the kids are getting some success but all of that comes through confidence and experience

Rachel: See on that I think I would try that now that nobody is sitting watching (yeah yeah agreement from other members of the group is heard in background), you don't want to look as if you can't do it you want to try and make every lesson the best do you know what I mean so that you are living up to their expectations but now if no one is going to be there you will be trying all sorts

Moderator: So on the whole you felt that the general consensus was that the school placements stood out more than the PE although you learnt stuff on it that you could take into placement

Multiple group members: Yeah, Yeah, I think so

Moderator: The participants in the survey highlighted time spent teaching within the teaching task and placement experiences as contributing to feelings of preparedness do you agree with this?

Chandler: I feel although there were beneficial if maybe it was a sport you didn't do and you had to research the activity to teach the lesson. The actual teaching of the lesson wasn't as valuable as a school one, I am talking about like when we did workshops to each other obviously doing research to get yourself content to design a lesson is good but is completely like different environment entirely. No one here was going to speak out of turn everyone did what you ask them to so it was a really kind of unnatural teaching environment whereas so it's good to do research but I felt, not that I could think of a better way of doing, but there could have been better ways to work on the delivery of your lessons and I felt that placements were a much better way of doing that because not only were you doing the research you were then delivering it to people who did have behaviour issues and stuff

Jonas: I agree with that and I think that maybe in the future they could, they lecturers, could maybe sneakily tell the 'pupils' before the lesson you're going to do this you're going to be badly behaved to see how the teacher is going to react or just something like that where maybe for example how chandler go to the toilet for 20 minutes to see what the teacher, or maybe if the teacher would realise, just so that you have an experience of dealing with a child who is misbehaving or is trying of bunk of class to make sure you are alert to all those kind of things instead of just teaching the lesson in a more straightforward way to make them more realistic

Rachel: I agree with that and the other thing I was going to say was See seeing for example if it was netball, I think that was one of the last ones, see seeing how everybody does it differently, so you are seeing 7 lessons or 6 lessons maybe if you were paired up which you always were sorry but that's you seeing 6 different ways. So although you are right in what you are saying that its not realistic to when you go out and you are only teaching with 14 people really and sharing it so that doesn't really happen but you are actually seeing 6 different lessons so you'll think I'll maybe steal that. Cause you did one for rugby and when I was on my placement I used it and the kids loved it but I wouldn't have necessarily know about that just reading it off the internet cause you don't know how well it could go cause we all loved it as well so ... but then again I tried it on my placement 3 and it failed miserably

Joseph: I think teaching the peers in class was good but I think the time that you got to teach it especially if you were say in a group of three and you only get 10 minutes of the lesson like if someone in your group went over or whatever you wouldn't get time to actually teach what you want to teach. Instead of maybe all having to teach the classes maybe having someone teach a half an hour lesson, everyone to teach a half hour lesson might be more beneficial rather than just getting a wee 10 minute slot where you can just take a warm up or whatever because you are not really getting enough time its just really short

Moderator: Did you guys have to do your subjects special like lead a workshop in your own sport?

Rachel: There was never another one.

Joseph: I think maybe with if there were more of those where you have to come up with something yourself would be beneficial cause then you can actually see a full lesson rom someone else rather than just splitting it

Rachel: See another thing as well see when we did it to the primary students I thought that was far better because a lot of them didn't actually ... well all of us 9 times out of ten we can do what you ask us to do so differentiation doesn't really come into it but with the primary ones a lot of them, I had javelin with them, and a lot of them couldn't do the technique right so you were going in a lot more and its more realistic. So I don't know if it something that could be set up maybe every Thursday and it's maybe spread out that way and if there is so many of them you have got the area you could just teach outside regardless of weather cause you have to do that in some schools so its on regardless. I know the primary wouldn't really love it but they would get content as well erm but it is more realistic to you actually going in to teaching

Chandler: I was the second last group to teach that day and by the time we got to 3 hours in the primary students didn't want to be there anymore , I think it would have to be structured differently

Rachel: Yeah I was last that's why I'm saying if it was a weekly thing maybe a seven week block and you knew that you were teaching every single week on a Thursday morning you and maybe three others but you are teaching for a 50 minute period but I think there is quite a lot of them so I think you could split them up and it would be more realistic. You would be getting content and you would be teaching to different people every week. I think it would be more realistic

Moderator: Just adding on to that in terms of teaching task and placement experiences making you feel more prepared feedback from tutors, mentors and teachers was highlighted as being integral to those feelings was this the case for you?

Phoebe: yes I think the feedback that we got was really good for teaching tasks and erm I kind of agree with what everyone is saying about, but I also think that the teaching tasks, that we did in Uni allows you to do try different things that you maybe wouldn't try in

school straightaway. Like different styles, maybe you want to try guided discover but you had never done it before, you might not be comfortable going into a class of 30 second year pupils and try it. Whereas you would maybe try it in teaching tasks, because you know that they are going to do what you ask and then you could see how it works out and then you would maybe be more comfortable using it in school ... so then the sort of feedback that the tutors would give you on that I thought it was really good.

Jonas: I think the feedback is really good as well and for me like constructive criticism that prepared you maybe for what you were going to receive on placement as well from the tutors. So you didn't always think what's going to be said. Another thing was on another one of our teaching tasks we were asked to give feedback on ourselves and on someone else's ability to teach, I think it was on that athletics task day, which is really good allowing you to actually analyse and to see if you could pick up on positive and negative things yourself

Monica: There was another teaching task we done, I think it was the non-traditional one, was recorded and although I hate watching myself I find that really quite beneficial. because I was able to see that I do like to wave my hands about during a lesson, so I was very much aware that okay maybe I shouldn't talk so much with my hands or the way I was saying things but I was seeing it for myself, rather than someone just saying to me you do this and I'm like okay, I don't know if I do that, so maybe record a bit more often and having the peer assessment during that

Chandler: Just on another point I think the whole recording thing was really good because you do get to see it and the same with the feedback its goes back to what Joseph said about if you were only actually teaching for 10 minutes within one of those workshops sometimes you get feedback and because you didn't do much there's not much they could give you, so your maybe getting a comment or two like good volume, good communication, but then you didn't have any anything else to really work on because they didn't see you teach for a full lesson, again it may be worthwhile the feedback being good, but over a longer period of time so they can actually pick up on a couple more things in your teaching.

Carlos: Just to kind of summarise what would make the teaching more pressurised, like you said it was more variety and someone some is told to misbehave, someone told to all of a sudden have an injury, someone's told they have to miss shots or whatever maybe just give that extra wee bit, because the research is really valuable watching your peers really valuable to see what ideas they come up with but the actual teaching yourself because you are teaching your pals its very difficult to get in that teacher, I find it very difficult to get in that teacher mindframe but if they were playing up and acting up I think that would make it that extra bit more valuable

Moderator: Participants identified three types of content that contributed to their preparedness these were PE specific content, pedagogical content and wider curricular content – what is your opinion on that?

Keith: I think overall the pedagogy was quite important and the PE specific for me was very important. Wider school issues not as important I would say erm but I think that when it came to actually the teaching actually what we're doing on placements the PE specific was

obviously most important. In terms of how we teach a class how we deal with behaviour management dealing with that various sort of issues as well. I think that was probably the most valuable having a good level of content knowledge. Some days the wider school maybe that was something I could have got more involved in on my placements erm but trying to get outside the pe department and doing more outside that sometimes gets pushed to one side a little bit. You obviously have just got your blinkers on and just focussed on the PE sort of stuff.

Monica: I'm going to disagree ever so slightly just because in placement 3 I found it benefitted me more. Just like learning, there was working groups like the tapestry group and IDL projects were going on and and developing Scotland's young work force. Like we have been saying about where teaching is going and that's maybe where opportunities are for future teachers as well. And learning about the guidance department and how they work and I just felt like that was once you got to placement three that was very beneficial for me feeling prepared because now going into this next year I felt okay, I know what the P.E department is doing and they are quite structure with that but I thought what can I do in the wider school that's going to help me for the following year when I am going for jobs and looking at what I can be putting on application forms and stuff. I think looking at wider school stuff is good but it was only on placement that I realised that because the stuff you got on the course I wouldn't say it's particularly great, to put it politely. With some things you were like there was one topic the controversial issues stuff and it just felt that was a little bit too broad and ridiculous it could maybe be a little bit more focused on what issues your actually going to get in schools, like poverty levels. I was on a placement were the poverty levels were very high, the facilities your going to get, things like that mean a little bit more.

Rachel: For me, see the generic issues log we have to do. See at first when I looked at that I was like oh my god. It looked like so much and it looked so boring. But I started that on my first placement and I had loads in it but I actually just went over with the department and I went to the different departments and it got me up off my bum to go and meet people. And I remember a teacher told another teacher that she's about the school everywhere. I don't know if I would have necessarily done that without having to say look, I need to go find this information could you help me. And you just network with loads and loads of different people. So, you were seen to be doing really really well but without it I don't know if I would have. So you have no reason to be talking to them without having to find this out so I thought that booklet was really really good in the end up. I completely agree with Monica with some of the stuff that we had to do. Particularly the one on a Thursday that you had to do it at home for me I thought it was an absolute waste of time and I think we could have maybe even been given tasks to do on placement on a Thursday. You need to be in school for a morning ideally its National 5 and Higher stuff that you are looking at rather than broad general education and report on it. It doesn't have to be anything major but for me that would have been so much more beneficial because you are networking with schools, you are having to find out about higher and national stuff and again it's a third school on to what you are doing, you know in addition to your two schools.

Moderator: So you would say then that the wider curricular content that you covered on the Thursday that that wasn't really, you don't feel that that's impacted on your teaching then? You don't feel that this has prepared you?

Rachel: At one point we learned about the holocaust and I don't understand how that is going to come into PE whatsoever, so it was an absolute waste of time for me. You ended up not liking the course because of it, well I did at one point. You would go home and think waste of time. At one point we got taught how to count in a ladder for numeracy, again absolutely pointless for me. Literacy some of the times, we'd leave on a Monday afternoon going it's a complete waste of time and people didn't want to go to the subject because it was a complete waste of time.

Moderator: Is this something that was felt across all curricular areas like in terms of other subjects?

Rachel: Yeah, the uni would be able to tell that because see even with attendance, slowly but surely nobody would go to the classes.

Jonas: On the online tasks as well I know there was someone who complained they were did it in like 20 minutes just from copy and pasting other people's answers so you're not actually learn at all. Some people would have spent like 4 hours on it which you were told to do or you would spend like 20 minutes and even with people who spend 20 minutes where never picked up on because it never felt like it was being watched by anybody. I also remember a class on gangs but can't remember why that was relevant at all. I mean It was interesting but,

Rachel: It never was related to wider issues [cross talk].

Jonas: Yes I don't know. I would have wished to know about gangs in schools like I'm supposed to.

Monica: There was this one Thursday that I did find really really valuable and that was the IDL one. When we had to mix ourselves up in different subjects and come up with an IDL project. Now some of them you know were for it garbage, but being able to interact with different subjects and come up with a plan that you would perhaps go into school with. I did actually end up going into my placement three school and implement an IDL well it was cross curricular but that was valuable.

Keith: That was cause it was something you could use in a school.

Monica: Exactly.

Keith: Sitting in a lecture, looking at counting on a ladder. You could never use that.

Rachel: Unless I'm covering a Maths class.

Moderator: Would you say that in terms of all these other curricular areas and agendas from Education Scotland like developing the you work force like the responsibility of all would be better served if you spent time on it in your subject specific sessions?

Rachel: Uh-huh because then you are literally relating it to your subject

Jonas: That ladder one was being take by a maths specialist

Rachel: I think a few of them, she took quite a few of the lectures.

Moderator: Would you say then that that could quite possibly make you quite insular because you are not getting the experience of being with other subject studies

Rachel: But then.

Keith: Just one point, it was just the fact that - it is all very well learning the stuff and we understand that we have to be cross curricular we can't all like I said before I did find myself getting pushed in to PE and maybe not as involved int eh wider school as I would have liked. Some of the stuff we did do on the Thursday might have been a bit why are we learning this, this is pointless. It was interesting, it did kind of help me sometimes when it came to looking at the generic logs and you see something on sustainability or enterprise education stuff like that and obviously things we did on the Thursday gave you a little bit of content knowledge about it. So when I did come to maybe speak something in the school about it I did have a bit of back and forth with them rather than me just asking questions so it kinda gave me an idea about. But I did feel some of the stuff was a bit... it could have been better served in more of like a seminar or like we are actually together talking about it and stuff like that. and especially with literacy when we were just learning the main question we always asked was how is that going to make me a better teacher, how's that going to help me in my classroom and when I'm on my placement in school and it's just trying to be okay. So it's not good for me to knowing this is this going to make me any better and I kept wanting to scream that at the person taking the lecture. Why is this relevant to me? why is this important to me as a teacher? So I kinda just felt that we were learning it for the sake of learning it if that makes sense.

Phoebe: I just, I disagree a little bit that because I think that some of the things we did on the Thursday some of the inclusion stuff I think did help me when I was in school, because I could see in class you kind of see how it affected the different pupils. I think when it came to writing our essay on that course I think it all linked together a bit better and you linked it to the school stuff and you could kind of see how you might use some of it or you might be able to use some of it. So I'm not saying ti was all necessarily worthwhile but I think you could link it to schools if you kind of made an effort to look for the links. Some of the other ones I do agree it was a bit ridiculous.

Rachel: Even the lecturer making the link for you so that you kind of go oh right... in the actual class when you are doing it

Carlos: I agree with what Phoebe has just said. It was all relevant. The stuff was all relevant, it was all stuff you needed to know to be a teacher. Erm but it is how you deliver it. Like

sometimes like the online thing very difficult for people to really engage with it and as Jonas pointed out certain people got different experiences from that. I think the way it was delivered, it didn't work for me personally. I didn't really feel like I could engage with that the structure. I actually think the lecture we had on the gangs was really good. I actually enjoyed it because it showed the kind of demographic it showed that experienced some of the pupils that will be in your class kind of what their opportunities are like what their life's like. And you know growing up in Glasgow you do see people who have really difficult lives and personally I think that's quite interesting to see that side of it that was one of the stands out lectures that we had throughout the year for me personally. I think that type of thing, obviously everyone learns in different ways but I think we are all in agreement that the Thursday class didn't work for everybody. I think it didn't work for most people. So I think the topics definitely are relevant but it is finding a way to engage us in it better

Keith: When you were talking about would it be worthwhile having like subjects specific this is literacy so PE would cover this is literacy and this is how you deal with it. It would be good but then if you could then meet with other disciplines and see how they are doing it rather than having a lecture where you teach everyone the same thing and half the people are sitting there going how can I use this? maybe have a lecture be say this is how PE are doing literacy and the other subjects are having their own and then you come together and then discuss what we were doing and hear what others are doing so you can crossover there rather than just saying that there's just one way of doing it.

Monica: We done that in health and wellbeing like when we done, it can't really remember what the title was but it was how does health and wellbeing related to the Scottish Culture in your subject and then we had to go out to the other different ones and that was, it was good

Carlos: The thing for me as well that could be really exciting, but it was really flat and I think that was what was disappointing this year that it was a really flat class and it just wasn't exciting.

Moderator: So what we are saying is that in terms of PE specific content and pedagogy content done in PE subject studies makes you prepared but wider curricular content wasn't stimulating and it didn't really impact what you did in a class, not for everyone but it wasn't as beneficial as other things.

Phoebe: I think another thing I was thinking of about the Thursday class I think it's partly because it was with primary as well so a lot of the time when they were answering way you could use it, like controversial issues topics in the class were primary examples, obviously the secondary students couldn't really use it so I think the Thursday class maybe worked better for the primary

Jonas: And you would also see online that there answers would be a lot more detailed actually

Phoebe: And it fitted a lot better with what they were doing in school.

Moderator: So you could be more tailored to secondary and also more to how you would experience it in class rather than just discussing a topic. Participants in the survey equated their level of confidence for teaching to feelings of preparedness what factors do you feel contribute to your confidence?

Chandler: Placements that's like the huge thing as we said before workshops you can stand in front of your pals and do it but until you are in front of the class and you are taking lesson week after week and things are working or working or not and you adapt I think that's where my confidence just grew. You know yourself when you finish a good lesson you are like yes! That worked perfectly, How can I take that forward and like even if you get knocked back there's always someone who's like but this worked well or this work well. So I think the placements were absolutely huge for building my confidence as a teacher.

Moderator: Were there any incidents where you maybe didn't do as well in the class and you tried it again later on and that helped boost your confidence?

Chandler: Yeah I had done similar things in my crit that I had done before. They had worked really really well before and they absolutely tanked in my crit. So I was like that's a nightmare but I knew it was a good thing to be using so I used it again and it worked so I knew it was just kind of a one-off thing. I think persevering with things that you know are going to work is a way to help build your confidence

Moderator: That's something your going to see in all teaching because two different classes could totally change the success of the lesson. Anything else?

Carlos: I think getting into the course, number one, competing against all those people was a huge confidence builder. Also I think just having the support as you touched on earlier, people you can talk to so your mentors, tutors, people at school, different colleagues, even each other that type of thing like you know if you ever had any doubts, a conversation with somebody. You know I think the mentors particularly the ones you can phone and text within the sort of mentoring group that we had they were brilliant so things like that I felt was really confidence building cause you know what its like if you are stuck on your own and its maybe you've had a bad day or you need someone to bounce that off you need somebody to bounce those ideas off so they way that we work together and we were able to collaborate throughout the year. I think that helped me to become more confident throughout the year.

Rachel: I think the placements definitely, but sometimes when you go talking to teachers, you would maybe ask a question, I would have the answer in my head of what I maybe thought it would be and then there telling you the answer which was good because you knew that you were on the right track, I'm not way off. Sometimes I was way off but majority of the time when I did speak to them I wasn't which was good because it gave you confidence going in that you actually kinda know what you are doing. You know from reading stuff and talking to teachers.

Jonas: I was just thinking that its everybody around you, that's about it, just to know that you can talk to people and I think the main thing for me is I had an awful first placement,

but everybody around me seem to believe in me which made me believe in myself and then the second and third placement was a lot better. So that's it really the people around you I think, cause if others have a good level of confidence in you then you'll have confidence in yourself. Yeah especially from the like lecturers and stuff who then had a meeting with me and made me feel confident

Moderator: So then you were quite well supported throughout the year and that built your confidence?

Jonas: Early on we had a good wee day out at Blairvaddach which I think everybody we had to share cars and do things together and I think that grew our wee friendship group and then it was better for everyone. That grew your confidence.

Monica: I think I got a lot of confidence ... I had a lot of confidence in the university tutors that we had and I think that definitely made a difference, because I think that some of the other disciplines didn't have as much confidence in their tutors and just their experience and their content knowledge you could or the things that they were delivering you were pretty sound in the knowledge that it was coming from a good place

Joseph: I was thinking on placement erm with us being new teachers and trying new ideas and then seeing other teachers use your ideas and that happened a few times and that was good cause at least you know what you're doing is good and they think it's good to include in their teaching so I thought of that people copying ideas that you gave into their classes. Made you think you had come up with good ideas and that can be a confident booster.

Carlos: I also think the weekly prop forms because you had opportunity to meet with your mentor at the school every single week. If you were going slightly of course they would be able to say to you, we need you to pick this up or if you were doing really well they were able to say what you were doing well. So I think that weekly meeting although it maybe seemed like a bit of a hassle a first. I think that was really important because in your head you need to know that you are not pleasing the people you need to know you are doing a good job or I need to anyway. So having that weekly meeting kind of helped me to think that they are happy with me they are not complaining they are not telling me to change to much or whatever so for me that was quite helpful.

Moderator: So having a good network dialogue with your peers and tutors is what you are saying has made you feel confident. Across the curriculum who do you think has the responsibility for the delivery of health and wellbeing?

Phoebe: in school? everyone

Moderator: Why do you feel that way?

Phoebe: Erm, sorry, erm, yeah

Jonas: Surely it has to be every teacher, because you're not only teaching your own subject your teaching them how to get through life as nice people ... I think everybody should be doing that

Rachel: It is the same as literacy and numeracy, responsibility of all

Joseph: I think that it is the responsibility of all but the onus is on PE, it would be the same that the onus for Numeracy is Maths. From my experience I would try and see if lessons took literacy and numeracy into account but I didn't really see anything like that on placement

Carlos: I know what you mean like it was involved somehow but in terms of it being like the focal point of a lesson along with something else it wasn't always there

Moderator: Do you think people maybe shirk responsibility of HWB for example in history or modern languages or other disciplines?

Keith: I think so when I was on my second placement, the first years had to come down to a HWb period each week which was really good. So they, I think it was the home economics, the PE department and social education as well. and the kids had to go to either one of the three each week. One was maybe looking at nutrition and eating healthy. Health and wellbeing when they were in the P.E department work was more a case of sort of like fitness tests and it was just a variety of different stuff. But then obviously it is just those three subjects and they had nothing really outwith that. So I think that the school just sort of thought that it was just for them to sort of deal with it rather than a whole school thing. But I mean health and wellbeing it covers so many things and its something that, okay maybe not as academic as literacy and numeracy, but in terms of you being yourself its probably one of the most important ones. It is being safe being healthy and that's something that should be overall at the top of the list.

Moderator: So adding on to that then, do we think that P.E was is enough to ensure health and wellbeing?

Carlos: I think no because some people don't engage with PE and some pupils don't like going to PE. If they don't engage with that class then they are not going to get anything out of it. You need support mechanisms throughout the school you maybe need a subject that they do like, maybe need that teacher to emphasize the importance of healthy living and exercise that type of thing. So, if they are not going to listen to P.E teacher then they need other support mechanisms throughout the school. And I think that's why talking about teaching through the curriculum because there are more opportunities to teach important parts that they need.

Keith: Just one other thing just that I think that health and wellbeing will be something that will probably seen as more P.E and obviously with issues in this country with a obesity and health problems and all this sort of stuff obviously I mean the government putting health and wellbeing at the centre of its curriculum it's one of those things if we don't see improvement with health or obesity or that sort of thing is it going to be something that P.E teachers going to be blamed for or is it something that the whole school is taken into consideration? So eh if it something that doesn't get any better it can be quite worrying.

Moderator: Overall, do you think you are prepared for the responsibility of delivering health and wellbeing?

Jonas: From a PE perspective, yes. For other subjects, I have no idea.

Chandler: I think it is important that you make yourself available to other subjects maybe not individually but as a department. You might have people that come down from English and Maths and be like we are covering this how would we do it? So as long as you are clued up enough where you can pass some knowledge on to someone else that's important. Even as a department if you are willing to take time and say this is how they we would like you to be doing things. I think that it is important as a department to be ready to give out knowledge to other subjects.

Monica: I think working groups are beneficial for that purpose. I experienced a member of the P.E department being part of one of the working groups on placement three. One of the groups was to do with health and wellbeing but it didn't have to be but that particular teacher made sure it was, so, that other people would benefit. It was about even encouraging more active learning within the classroom and getting the kids up and doing different things and because of this working group it was based on a book called making thinking visible and it was very good in terms being able to like you say help other people like that. Instead of them coming to you, you were a part of that group so you could transfer it to them, just an encouragement if you want to be part of a groups like that in schools.

Moderator: So on a whole then we would say that you feel prepared in terms of the physical element of health and wellbeing but when it comes to you maybe the mental side of things or what you are doing can impact on other subject you are maybe not as confident or prepared?

Phoebe: Yeah

Carlos: In some parts yes

Moderator: So, I'll just ask the last question. The purpose of the focus group was to recall your experiences within your initial teacher education course and your feelings of preparedness with that in mind, is there anything else you would like to share on the topic?

Group Silence

Moderator: For example, would you like more or less of things to help you feel prepared?

Rachel: I thought it was really good when the probationers came down and had a talk with us.

Joseph: I think that could happen maybe at the start as well. So you know what you are going to be facing. So possibly have a lecture from the previous years students.

Monica: It was also good having the one above as well cause they were a year ahead and were able to feed in as well.

Keith: I think that speaking to some of the teachers on placement us going through the one year did have its benefits rather than four years. Because I think that there's lot of teachers that when I was on placement said that they when they are younger maybe eighteen or nineteen and that was really difficult and basically, they felt like we were maybe a bit more mature and bit more eh life experience. I think that benefitted us a lot better and obviously a lot of that came from a coaching background and we had developed quite a high level of being able to coach and lead a session and that sort of stuff for that. So, because I think initially, they didn't think it was a very good programme but I think it helped us and it was quite a beneficial thing.

Jonas: On that for me it's the complete opposite because on my first placement, the guy gave up on me because he didn't believe in this one-year course and something like that. So, it made it extremely difficult, that was his opinion and he wasn't really giving me a chance. If I was going to give a chat to people next year who has just been, just tell them that each department is different and if you have maybe an awful first experience in the school don't give up because I know I am not the only one who had bad experience if you just get through and persist it will help you in the long run.

Moderator: Would you say that you feel prepared then to enter your school not really knowing what's ahead of you even though you have done a bit of research on it? From the experiences that you had on placement that you are good to and you will be able to deal with any of the challenges?

Carlos: I think coming through a year like last year is great got preparation for what's coming. You know it was such a busy and intense year coming through it and you have good experiences through it you know it kind of stand you in good stead. Like we've all worked really hard and we've had sleepless nights getting through placements and stuff and once you have gone through that you can disagree with me but your probation year can't get any harder than that I don't think. Maybe it can, maybe it can't, but it still puts you in good stead I think to deal with what's coming up.

Chandler: One of things I noticed was and this is again personal every time I went into a new school, I know especially my first placement, I was sitting there thinking that I have to know everything on the whole course and I have to be the finished article already. And I went through the first three or four weeks like just panicking every time I had to deliver a lesson as I thought his has to be like 10 out of 10 otherwise these teachers are going to be like feeding back but then I realised, as you go in and speak to people that they are all so supportive of you and you are still developing as a teacher. You don't have to worry about like lesson going well or asking a question or something like that.

Joseph: I think that when you are taking a lesson and the teacher is a bit younger and kind of share the same ideas with you, it is easier than it is taking a lesson for someone who is getting ready to retire. A lot of the class teachers I had were really close to UWS and so they knew everything that we went through and they knew what to expect from the start. They were also saying well this was your first lesson outside so this was maybe going to happen. I think having someone who is giving you feedback sharing the same ideas as you is better than someone who is set in their routines.

Rachel: don't think that I am necessarily going to do anything different than what I have done as a student. I think I'll still gonna go, cause my content needs work, watch teachers in my free periods especially at the higher and national. I'm still going to ask questions cause it is the only way that I learn. So I don't think although I feel excited and I feel as if I kinda know a wide amount, a good amount about schools now. Because I was in a really, really bad school with regards to behaviour and in a really good high attaining school so I've seen both ends of the spectrum. So I am going in thinking if I have someone who is behaving like this I kinda know what I am going to do. I'd still ask, what would you do? But again I think I have a better idea and if I am struggling with content I know I can ask that as well. So I don't think I'll do anything really different.

Moderator: Thanks for your participation.

Appendix 12: Piloting Review Form

Piloting Review - Survey

- How long did it take to complete
- Were the instructions clear?
- Were any questions unclear or ambiguous
- Did you object to answering any of the questions?
- Has any major topic been missed or omitted?
- Was the layout of the questionnaire clear / attractive?
- Any additional comments

Focus Group

- Were the instructions clear?
- Were any questions unclear or ambiguous?
- Did you object to answering any of the questions?
- Has any major topic been missed or omitted
- Any additional comments

Interviews

- Were the instructions clear?
- Were any questions unclear or ambiguous?
- Did you object to answering any of the questions?
- Has any major topic been missed or omitted?
- Any additional comments

Appendix 13: Completed Piloting Review Form

Piloting Review - Survey

- How long did it take to complete
~~20 mins~~ 10 mins
- Were the instructions clear?
Yes
- Were any questions unclear or ambiguous?
None
- Did you object to answering any of the questions?
No
- Has any major topic been missed or omitted?
No
- Was the layout of the questionnaire clear / attractive?
Yes
- Any additional comments
No

Focus Group

- Were the instructions clear? *Very*
- Were any questions unclear or ambiguous? *No, they were expanded when necessary*
- Did you object to answering any of the questions? *No*
- Has any major topic been missed or omitted? *No*
- Any additional comments - *Interesting to hear other opinions, especially those different to mine*

- Were the instructions clear? *YES, THEY WERE EXPLAINED PRIOR TO THE INTERVIEW*
- Were any questions unclear or ambiguous? *NO*
- Did you object to answering any of the questions? *NO*
- Has any major topic been missed or omitted? *NO*
- Any additional comments

Appendix 14: Gant Charts / Plan of Work Example

	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUG	SEPT	Word Count
1. <u>Methodology & Methods</u> Chapter													18000 redraft Cut to 15000
2. Findings Chapter													5000 redraft 5000 new
3. Discussion Chapter													6000 redraft 6000 new
4. Reading for Literature Review													n/a
5. Literature Review Chapter													9000 redraft 3000 new
6. Reflexive Chapter													10000
7. AIESEP Conference Submission													500 words
8. BERA Conference Submissions													500 words
9. SERA Conference Submission													500 words
10. ECER Conference Submission													500 words
11. Prep for Submission													
12. Draft Submission													
13. Submission													
14. VIVA													
15. Writing Retreat dates TBC													9000 per retreat

Appendix 15: Ethical Approval

School of Education Ethics Committee Report

Applicant: - Elaine McCulloch

Project: - Health and Wellbeing - Responsibility of All: Are all ready for the responsibility? - A critical examination of the levels of preparedness in the UWS Physical Education Initial Teacher Education

SOE Ethics Number: - STAFF04

Dear Elaine

I am pleased to inform you that ethical approval has now been granted.

Please keep the Committee informed should there be any changes to your study that may require further ethical consideration

Yours sincerely

Best Wishes

Dr Beth Cross
(Chair) School of Education Ethics Committee

Appendix 16: Overview of Participants Undergraduate Degrees

	Participants	Sport and Exercise Science	Sport and Physical Activity	Sports Coaching	Other
Class of 2015	Possible(14)	3 (21.4%)	4 (28.6%)	6 (42.9%)	1 - Sport Studies (7.1%)
	PSE (12)	3 (25%)	2 (16.7%)	6 (50%)	1 (8.3%)
	FG (11)	3 (27.3%)	2 (18.2%)	5 (45.5%)	1 (9.1%)
	INTS (4)	1 (25%)	1 (25%)	2 (50%)	0 (0%)
Class of 2016	Possible (16)	6 (37.5%)	5 (31.25%)	4 (25%)	1 – Sport Development (6.25%)
	PSE (9)	3 (33.33%)	3 (33.33%)	3 (33.33%)	0 (0%)
	FG (8)	2 (25%)	3 (37.5%)	3 (37.5%)	0 (0%)
	INTS (4)	1 (25%)	2 (50%)	1 (25%)	0 (0%)
Class of 2017	Possible (12)	3 (25%)	4 (33.33%)	4 (33.33%)	1 – Sports Coaching and Development (8.33%)
	PSE (9)	2 (22.2%)	3 (33.33%)	3 (33.33%)	1 (11.1%)
	FG (6)	1 (16.7%)	2 (33.33%)	2 (33.33%)	1 (16.7%)
	INTS (3)	0 (0%)	1 (33.33%)	1 (33.33%)	1 (33.33%)
Overall	Possible (42)	12 (28.6%)	13 (30.95%)	14 (33.33%)	3 (7.1%)
	PSE (30)	8 (26.7%)	8 (26.7%)	12 (40%)	2 (6.7%)
	FG (25)	6 (24%)	7 (28%)	10 (40%)	2 (8%)
	INTS (11)	2 (18.2%)	4 (36.4%)	4 (36.4%)	1 (9.1%)

Appendix 17: PGDE Programme Content

The following gives an overview of the programme content and the three core modules within the programme: School Experience, Subject Studies and School and Professional Studies.

Professional Values and Personal Commitment

The core values defined as Social Justice, Integrity, Trust and Respect, and Personal Commitment, which are integral to, and demonstrated through, all professional relationships and practices.

Professional Knowledge and Understanding

The knowledge and understanding of the relevant areas of the secondary curriculum, including contexts for learning to fulfil their responsibilities in literacy, numeracy, health and wellbeing and interdisciplinary learning; the principal features of the education system and their own professional responsibilities within the learning communities in which they will teach; relevant educational principles and pedagogical theories; and the importance of research in informing professional practice.

Professional Skills and Abilities

The ability to design, deliver and assess effective, appropriate and stimulating programmes of work in one or two subject areas within the secondary curriculum that are suitable for children at different stages of secondary education; and to use reading, research and feedback from a range of sources to inform effective self evaluation and maintain a record of professional learning and development culminating in an Initial Professional Development Action Plan.

The programme will encourage the student to engage in lifelong learning, study and enquiry and to appreciate the value of education to society. It will also assist the student to develop the skills required for both autonomous practice and team-working.

School and Professional Studies

This module will enable students to develop a thorough understanding of the Scottish education system and to engage critically with complex issues arising from recent national policy in relation to pre school, primary and secondary education. Throughout the module, students will be encouraged and supported to develop the professional qualities and capabilities probationer teachers are expected to attain. Students will develop an understanding of the principal influences on Scottish education and develop some awareness of international systems. Consideration will be given to the ways in which natural, social, cultural, political and economic systems function and how they are interconnected.

The module will enable students to develop a critical understanding of socially just and inclusive education. An understanding of current, relevant legislation and guidance such as the Standard in Scotland's Schools etc Act (2000), Education (Additional Support for Learning) (Scotland) Act 2004, the Equality Act 2010 and GIRFEC will be encouraged. Educational issues arising from diversity relating to disability, gender and gender identity, race, ethnicity, religion and belief and sexual orientation will be explored. Consideration will be given to the experiences of learners at points of transition, particularly from primary to secondary education. The importance of engaging learners in real world issues to enhance learning experiences and outcomes will be emphasised through the exploration of learning for sustainability, local and global citizenship, enterprise and financial education. Students will explore how to develop realistic and coherent interdisciplinary contexts for learning and opportunities to take learning out of the classroom.

Subject Studies

This module will enable students to develop knowledge and understanding and skills and abilities in relation to the curriculum, pedagogy and assessment of a subject area within the secondary curriculum within the primary curriculum. It will enable the contextualising within specific curricular areas of some of the broader principles explored in the PGDE (S) School Experience module.

Curriculum: The module will explore the principles of curriculum design, contexts for learning, and the processes of change and development in the curriculum.

Pedagogy: Students will understand the methods and underlying theories for effective teaching and learning and learn how to plan appropriately in order to meet the needs of all learners, across different contexts and experiences.

Assessment: Students will develop knowledge and understanding of the principles of assessment and how to use a range of approaches for formative and summative assessment purposes, appropriate to the needs of all learners and the requirements of the curriculum and awarding and accrediting bodies, record assessments appropriately, use assessment information to review progress, inform and enhance teaching and learning, identify strengths and development needs which lead to further learning opportunities, and produce clear, informed and sensitive reports.

Professional qualities and capabilities: The module will enable students to engage in professional dialogue with peers and university staff and to work collaboratively. Throughout the module, students will be expected to model appropriate levels of literacy and numeracy in learning activities and to reflect on the impact of their personal communication on others.

School Experience

This module will prepare students for their school experience placements. It will explore generic aspects of curriculum, pedagogy and assessment, as well as facilitating understanding of the schools and learning communities in which students will teach and their professional responsibilities within them. Students will know and understand the content of the curriculum in relation to literacy, numeracy and health and wellbeing, and the methods and underlying theories for effective teaching of these cross curricular priorities. Students will learn about specific learning needs and how to remove barriers to learning from classroom practice.

A variety of strategies to build relationships with learners, promote positive behaviour and celebrate success will be explored and the importance of applying the school's behaviour policy, including strategies for understanding and preventing bullying, emphasised. Students will develop knowledge and understanding of the principles of assessment for formative and summative assessment purposes.

Students will be directed to read and analyse a range of appropriate educational and research literature and encouraged to engage with wider reading through accessing literature independently. Students will be supported to use what they have learned to critically examine their personal and professional attitudes and beliefs, to challenge, justify, evaluate and inform practice and to ask critical questions of educational policies. Learning activities will encourage students to reflect and engage in self-evaluation using the Standard for Registration. Students will maintain a record of their own professional learning and development, culminating in an Initial Professional Development Action Plan.

Education systems and professional responsibilities: Students will develop an understanding of the sector and schools in which they will be working, including: the role of education authorities, the organisation and management of schools and resources, improvement planning, professional review and development, and how these connect to teachers' professional practice. The module will provide a working knowledge of the teacher's contractual, pastoral and legal responsibilities and enable students to develop an understanding of the legal and professional aspects of a teacher's position of trust in relation to learners. The roles and responsibilities of various members of staff within learning communities will be explored.

Curriculum: Students will know and understand the content of the curriculum in relation to literacy, numeracy and health and wellbeing as set out in national guidance, and the methods and underlying theories for effective teaching of these cross-curricular priorities. The module will make students aware of connections between different curricular areas, stages and sectors and consider how to plan for effective teaching and learning across different contexts and experiences.

Pedagogy: The module will introduce students to theories of learning and the importance of these in planning, teaching and learning. Students will develop knowledge and understanding of the stages of learners' cognitive, social and emotional development and how to promote and support the cognitive, emotional, social and physical wellbeing. Students will learn about specific learning needs and how to remove barriers to learning from classroom practice. How to work co-operatively in the classroom and the wider learning community, in ways that develop a culture of trust and respect, with staff, parents and partner agencies to promote learning and wellbeing will be explored. Students will consider how to plan and provide a safe and secure, well organised learning environment; make appropriate use of available space to accommodate whole class lessons, group and individual work and promote independent learning; and apply health and safety regulations as appropriate to their role. A variety of strategies to build relationships with learners, promote positive behaviour and celebrate success will be explored and the importance of applying the school's behaviour policy, including strategies for understanding and preventing bullying, emphasised.

Assessment: Students will develop knowledge and understanding of the principles of assessment for formative and summative assessment purposes.

Professional qualities and capabilities: The module will enable students to engage in professional dialogue with peers and university staff and to work collaboratively, at times taking a leading role, in a culture of trust and respect, to share their professional learning and development with others. Students will be expected to engage with all aspects of the module with enthusiasm, adaptability and constructive criticality. Learning activities will encourage students to adopt an enquiring approach to their professional practice and to reflect and engage in self-evaluation using the Standard for Provisional Registration. Students will maintain a record of their own professional learning and development, culminating in an Initial Professional Development Action Plan. Students will be directed to read and analyse a range of appropriate educational and research literature and encouraged to engage with wider reading through accessing literature independently. Students will be supported to use what they have learned from reading and research to critically examine

their personal and professional attitudes and beliefs, to challenge, justify, evaluate and inform practice and to ask critical questions of educational policies. Throughout the module, students will be expected to model appropriate levels of literacy and numeracy in learning activities and to reflect on the impact of their personal communication on others.